

2nd International Congress on Biotech Solutions for Sustainability

Oct 21-24th, 2025

**Congress Hall
Gebze Technical University
Kocaeli, Türkiye**

#Biotech4sus

2nd International Congress on Biotech Solutions for Sustainability

Oct 21-24th 2025, Congress Hall, Gebze Technical University, Kocaeli,
Türkiye

Scope

Our conference aims to bring together academic research and industrial innovations in different areas of biotechnology, such as health, plants, industry, environment, and marine. Our goal is to bring these diverse disciplines together to create an interdisciplinary interaction environment among researchers and industry leaders worldwide and to share the latest scientific and technological developments in the field. We are enthusiastic to host our esteemed guests at this international gathering.

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Letter of Conference Chair

Dear Colleagues,

Dear Rector, Vice Rectors, all the distinguished protocol members, all our esteemed speakers, colleagues, all our participants and guests...

We are delighted to host the 2nd International Congress on Biotech Solutions to Sustainability, which Gebze Technical University (GTU); it has been an honour to have you all at our beautiful green and sustainable campus.

GTU Institute of Biotechnology is a young but vibrant community of researchers, trying to find feasible solutions to tomorrow's problems, together with our industry partners. It is long known that biology is among the sectors that will not become redundant in the future due to AI, showing once more the importance of biology and biotechnology-based solutions to tomorrow's world, which is what this congress is about. For that reason, the MoU between Biotech Industrialists Association (BIYOSAD) and GTU, as well as our newly approved Biotechnology and Bioeconomy Cluster (BiKUME) is infinitely exciting new endeavours for us. I would like to thank all our faculty members, students, collaborators, and industry partners for making this possible, as well as our Rector and the Ministry for believing in us. And a huge thanks to our Vice Rector Prof. Dr. Elif Damla Arisan, who is the mastermind behind both BiKUME cluster, and the "godmother" to this Biotech4Sus congress.

Last year we organized the 1st Biotech4Sustainability in collaboration with MNS University in Pakistan. This year we are happy to expand our international reach, with many renowned international speakers across disciplines, and to receive contribution from well-known global institutions such as Food and Agriculture Association (FAO). GTU Institute of Biotechnology is also a partner of UN Sustainable Development Solutions Network (UN SDSN) Türkiye chapter. And today, signing the MoU with Biotech Industrialists Association will bring us closer with partners of the newly established Biotech Valley, for which we are extremely excited.

We believe that these connections and partnerships will make all of us stronger globally.

We are also proud to have received so many abstract applications to this year's congress. We do therefore apologize that not every abstract was accepted as oral presentation due to time constraints, nonetheless all presentations are equally important and competitive, so thank you for your genuine interest and cutting-edge research solutions, and please let us all use this opportunity to start new collaborations!

We are also happy that this congress was also full of other parallel-running scientific activities. We hope we will grow in number and diversity of workshops in the coming years.

I would like to finish my brief welcoming speech by thanking the principal organizers, Nihal hanım and her team; and another heartfelt thanks to all our organizing committee members, faculty members, research assistants, grad students, and all the administrative and service departments of our university and all our partner municipalities.

Of course such events will not be possible without funds; so I would like to thank all our sponsors, in particular our platin sponsor IGSAS.

Prof. Dr. Işıl AKSAN KURNAZ Congress Chair, On behalf of the Organizing Committee

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Şükrü Anıl Doğan (Beykoz Institute of Life Sciences and Biotechnology
(BILSAB), Bezmialem Vakıf University)

Taner Sar (Biotechnology Engineer, Bioextrax AB, Lund, Sweden)

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Berna SARIYAR AKBULUT (Marmara University)

Besim Ogretmen (Medical University of South Carolina)

Zeynep Bal (Osaka University)

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Zeynep Gunes Di Marcoberardino, Head of Project & Portfolio Management,
CMC at Menarini Biotech

Hasan Matsumoto (Ucar), Boehringer Ingelheim, Kobe, Japan

Bilgen Ekim, Research Group Leader at University Hospital Heidelberg (UKHD)

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Congress Program

	Day 0: Oct 21, 2025 (Tuesday)
09.00-18.00	Workshops
	Day 1: Oct 22, 2025 (Wednesday)
08.30-09.30	Registration
09.00-09.50	Opening Ceremony
09.50-10.00	GTU-BIYOSAD Signing Ceremony
10.00-10.40	<i>Keynote Speaker – Ercan Varlıbaş, Dr., Association of Biotechnology Industrialists (BIYOSAD)-Chairman of Board A Sustainable Future through Biotechnology: The Transformation Voyage of Türkiye</i>
10.40-11.30	Coffee break and poster hall visit
	Session 1: Medical Biotechnology (ATABAY Pharmaceuticals Session)
11.30-12.10	<i>Plenary lecture 1 - Utkan Demirci, Prof. Dr., Stanford University, USA Impacting Medicine with Innovative Technologies: Advancing Medicine & Diagnostics</i>
12.10-12.30	<i>Doğan Taşkent, ATABAY Pharmaceuticals and Fine Chemicals, Türkiye Strength of Turkish Pharma Sector and How to Use It to Develop Novel Drugs</i>
12.30-12.50	<i>Invited Speaker - Begüm Zeybek, Dr., University of Oxford, UK Towards Sustainable and Adaptive Prosthetic Sockets</i>
13.00-14.00	Lunch break and poster hall visit - Music Recital
	Session 2: Plant Biotechnology

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14.00-14.40	<p><i>Plenary lecture 2 - Søren Husted, Prof. Dr., University of Copenhagen</i></p> <p><i>“How do we unleash the potential of nano-fertilization to improve nutrient use efficiency in modern crop production?”</i></p>		
Parallel Sessions			
Plant Biotechnology		Medical Biotechnology	
15.00-15.15	<p>OP1 – Zaeema Khan</p> <p><i>Harnessing sulfur-oxidizing bacteria for sustainable plant sulfate nutrition</i></p>	15.00-15.15	<p>OP7 – Abdullah Karadağ</p> <p><i>Identification of Novel Long Non-Coding RNAs as Diagnostic and Prognostic Biomarkers in NSCLC</i></p>
15.15-15.30	<p>OP2 – Rıfat Buğra Bildiri</p> <p><i>Effects of Duckweed Amendment on Cucumber Shoot Growth Under Varying Soil Boron Conditions</i></p>	15.15-15.30	<p>OP8 - Tzonka Godjevargova</p> <p><i>Immunomodulatory effect of grape seed extract on immune cells</i></p>
15.30-15.45	<p>OP3 – Atakan Yıldız</p> <p><i>The Role of Soil Microbiota in Ecosystem Health and Sustainable Tea Cultivation: Insights from eDNA and Metagenomic Approaches</i></p>	15.30-15.45	<p>OP9 – Büşra Bıçak</p> <p><i>Metabolism-Associated Transcriptomic Alterations Reveal Novel Therapeutic Targets in a Parkinson’s Disease Cellular Model</i></p>

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15.45-16.00	OP4 – Sena Kızılboğa <i>Molecular Dialogue Between Maize (Zea mays) and Fusarium verticillioides: A Cross-Kingdom RNAi Perspective for Sustainable Disease Resistance</i>	15.45-16.00	OP10 – Yüksel Çetin <i>Exploring the Suitability of Ti–Nb–Zr Alloys for Load-Bearing Implants Through Microstructural, Mechanical, and Biological Analyses</i>
16.00-16.15	Coffee Break	16.00-16.15	Coffee Break
16.15-16.30	OP5 – Abdullah Hilmi Coşar <i>Molecular Dialogue Between Maize (Zea mays) and Fusarium verticillioides: A Cross-Kingdom RNAi Perspective for Sustainable Disease Resistance</i>	16.15-16.30	OP11 – Burcu Taluğ Taştan <i>Uncovering the Mechanisms of Korean Ginseng in Atopic Dermatitis via Network Pharmacology and Molecular Docking</i>
16.30-16.45	OP6 – Esmâ Koca <i>Modulation of resveratrol production by methyl jasmonate and melatonin in callus and organogenic cultures of morus species</i>	16.30-16.45	OP12 – Büşra Nur Çıtır <i>Investigation of the Toxicity of Osimertinib and/or Enzalutamide as Potential Drug Candidates for Glioblastoma in Caenorhabditis elegans</i>
		16.45-17.00	OP13 – Alper Cesur <i>Structure-Based Virtual Screening for Novel GLTP Inhibitors</i>

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		17.00-17.15	OP14 – Evren Saban <i>Proteomic Profiling Identifies Novel Non-small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) Biomarkers</i>
19.30-23.00	Gala Dinner		
Day 2: Oct 23, 2025 (Thursday)			
Session 3: Environmental Biotechnology			
09.30-09.45	OP15 – Mustafa Can Uygun <i>Photoelectrocatalytic Degradation of Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) Utilizing a Novel TiO₂/WO₃ Nanostructured Photoanode Enhanced with Carbon Quantum Dots (CQDs)</i>		
09.45-10.00	OP16 – Tuğba Keskin Gündoğdu <i>Optimization of Medium Chain Fatty Acid (MCFA) Production Via Co-Culture Microbial Fermentation using Plackett–Burman Design</i>		
10.00-10.20	Invited Speaker – Beste Turanlı, Assoc. Prof. Marmara University, Türkiye <i>Deciphering Molecular Mechanisms of Environmental Pollutant Exposure through Systems Toxicology</i>		
10.20-10.40	Coffee Break		
10.40-11.20	Plenary Lecture 3 – Güleda Engin, Prof. Dr., Yıldız Technical University, Türkiye <i>Sustainable Management Approaches for Microplastic Pollution</i>		
11.20-11.35	OP17 – Mirkan Emir Sancak <i>From Human Perception to Computer Vision: A Comparative Study on Titration Analysis</i>		
11.35-11.50	OP18 – Yavor Ivanov <i>The effect of grape seed extract on lipid oxidation in a beef–pork sausage model system</i>		
11.50-12.10	Invited Speaker – Erdem Günsür, Ford Otosan, Türkiye <i>Material Genomics: Rethinking How We Build Our World</i>		

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12.10-12.20	<i>Gen Era Sponsor Talk</i>
12.20-13.20	Lunch Break – Music Recital
Session 4: Industrial Biotechnology	
13.20-14.00	Plenary Lecture 4 – Eyüp İlker Saygılı, Prof. Dr., SANKO University, Türkiye <i>Algae as a Promising Organism for The Environment and Health</i>
14.00-14.20	Invited Speaker – Luigi Nataloni, Cereal Docks, Italy <i>From Disruption to Direction: Cerealdocks' Vision for the Future of Plant-Based Proteins</i>
14.20-14.35	OP19 – Mehmet Can Durmuş <i>Chitosan–Alginate Based Edible Coatings Reinforced with Green-Synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles for Shelf-Life Extension of Bananas</i>
14.35-14.50	OP20 – Milka Atanasova <i>Nutritional and functional values of grape seed extracts for production of antioxidative dietary supplements</i>
14.50-15.05	OP21 – Özlem Aslan, Dr., TÜBİTAK MAM, Climate and Life Sciences, Food Technology Research Group <i>Benchmarking of Protein-Rich Crops Grown in Türkiye: Functional, Technological and Economic Evaluation of Innovative Extraction Approaches</i>
15.05-15.20	Coffee Break
15.20-15.40	Invited Speaker – Emine Aytunga Arık Kibar, Dr., TÜBİTAK Marmara Research Center, Türkiye <i>From Vision to Action: The Story of the PROTWIN Project</i>
15.40-16.00	Asena Atay – UNOPEX Sponsor Talk <i>Scale-up in Bioreactors: Challenges and Solutions</i>
16.00-16.15	OP22 – Halil Daşgın <i>Potential Health Benefits of Potato Protein-derived Peptides</i>
16.15-16.30	OP23 – Furkan Yeneroğlu <i>Slient Bioconversion Force of Nature</i>

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Day 3: Oct 24, 2025 (Friday)	
Session 5: Aquatic Biotechnology	
09.30-10.00	<i>Plenary Lecture – Aytaç Özgül, Prof. Dr., Ege University Acoustic Telemetry Applications in Turkish Seas</i>
10.00-10.20	<i>Invited Speaker - Zekeriya Ar, Bolu Directorate of Provincial Agriculture and Forestry, Türkiye Conservation of Blue Sources: Our Experiences in Fisheries</i>
10.20-10.40	<i>Invited Speaker - Levent Bat, Prof. Dr., Sinop University, Türkiye Sustainable Macroalgae Management in the Black Sea Basin: Utilizing Blooms for Environmental Protection and Bioeconomy</i>
10.40-11.00	<i>Coffee break and poster hall visit</i>
11.00-11.30	<i>Plenary Lecture 6 - Haydar Fersoy, FAO Regional Office for Europe and Central Asia, Türkiye Biotechnology for Sustainable Aquatic Food Systems: Insights from FAO's Science and Innovation Strategy</i>
11.30-11.50	<i>Invited Speaker - Yunus Emre Fakioglu, Dr., General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean, FAO Black Sea Technical Unit, Bulgaria Learning from fishers: Use of local ecological knowledge to better understand sturgeon-fishery interactions in the Black Sea</i>
11.50-12.10	<i>Invited Speaker - Murat Dağtekin, Dr., Central Fisheries Research Institute, Türkiye Can Awareness-Raising Activities Contribute to the Recovery of Sturgeon Stocks in the Black Sea?</i>
12.10-13.00	<i>Lunch Break – Music Recital</i>
Biyogirişimcilik Paneli	
13.00-13.15	<i>Açılış Konuşması ve Panel Tanıtımı</i>
13.15-14.00	<i>Panelist Konuşmaları</i>

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14.00-15.30	<i>Biyogiriřimcilik Yarışması</i>
15.30-16.00	Kahve Arası
16.00-17.00	Award Ceremony and Closing Remarks

OP: Oral Presentation

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Keynote Speakers

Utkan Demirci

Prof. Dr., Stanford University

*“Impacting Medicine with Innovative
Technologies: Advancing Medicine &
Diagnostics”*

Søren Husted

Prof. Dr., University of Copenhagen

*“How do we unleash the potential of nano-
fertilization to improve nutrient use efficiency in
modern crop production?”*

Güleda Engin

Prof. Dr., Yıldız Technical University

*“Sustainable Management Approaches for
Microplastic Pollution”*

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Eyüp İlker Saygılı
Prof. Dr., SANKO University
“Algae as a Promising Organism for The
Environment and Health”

Aytaç Özgül
Prof. Dr., Ege University
“Acoustic Telemetry Applications in Turkish
Seas”

Haydar Fersoy
**FAO Regional Office for Europe and
Central Asia, Türkiye**
“Biotechnology for Sustainable Aquatic Food
Systems: Insights from FAO’s Science and
Innovation Strategy”

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Abstracts for Keynote Presentations

The abstracts for keynote presentations are listed according to the congress program

KP1- Medical Biotechnology

IMPACTING MEDICINE WITH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES: ADVANCING MEDICINE &
DIAGNOSTICS

PROF. DR. UTKAN DEMİRCİ

KP2- Plant Biotechnology

HOW DO WE UNLEASH THE POTENTIAL OF NANO-FERTILIZATION TO IMPROVE NUTRIENT USE
EFFICIENCY IN MODERN CROP PRODUCTION?

PROF. DR. SOREN HUSTED

KP3- Environmental Biotechnology

SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT APPROACHES FOR MICROPLASTIC POLLUTION

PROF. DR. GÜLEDA ENGİN

KP4-Industrial Biotechnology

ALGAE AS A PROMISING ORGANISM FOR THE ENVIRONMENT AND HEALTH

PROF. DR. EYÜP İLKER SAYGILI

KP5- Aquatic Biotechnology

ACOUSTIC TELEMETRY APPLICATIONS IN TURKISH SEAS

PROF. DR. AYTAÇ ÖZGÜL

KP6- Aquatic Biotechnology

BIOTECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUATIC FOOD SYSTEMS: INSIGHTS FROM FAO'S
SCIENCE AND INNOVATION STRATEGY

HAYDAR FERSOY

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KP1

IMPACTING MEDICINE WITH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES: ADVANCING MEDICINE & DIAGNOSTICS

Utkan Demirci

*Bio-Acoustic MEMS in Medicine (BAMM) Laboratories, Department of Radiology, School of
Medicine, Stanford University, Palo Alto, CA, USA*

Micro- and nanoscale technologies hold transformative potential for medicine and biology, particularly in diagnostics, cell sorting, and patient monitoring. At the intersection of engineering and biology, our research focuses on developing real-world solutions to clinical challenges. We explore the integration of microfluidics and nanotechnology with biological systems to engineer intelligent lab-on-a-chip platforms that could revolutionize diagnostics, monitoring, microrobotics, biofabrication, and regenerative medicine. In this talk, I will present our work on microfluidic technologies, with a focus on their clinical applications in *in vitro* fertilization (IVF), cancer diagnostics, and the emerging role of extracellular vesicles in early disease detection.

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KP2

HOW DO WE UNLEASH THE POTENTIAL OF NANO-FERTILIZATION TO IMPROVE NUTRIENT USE EFFICIENCY IN MODERN CROP PRODUCTION?

Søren Husted *, Maja Arsic, Morten Vestenaa, Francesco Minutello, Pauline Møs, Max Frank, Daniel Persson

*University of Copenhagen, Department of Plant and Environmental Sciences, Thorvaldsensvej
40, DK-1871 Frederiksberg C, Denmark*

Conventional strategies for soil fertilization are remarkably inefficient, as only a fraction of most mineral elements added with fertilizers are taken up by plants, the rest are typically trapped in the soil or leached to the aqueous environment, causing eutrophication. Thus, one of the most important current challenges of agriculture is to improve the sustainability of food production via an improved fertilizer efficiency. However, fertilizers have practically not improved for decades and this calls for an acute rethinking of fertilization procedures.

We have proposed a novel approach that bypasses nutrient fixation and microbial immobilization in the soil. We take advantage of the most recent breakthroughs within bio-nanotechnology, which allow us to produce biocompatible fertilizers based on smart nanomaterials, tailored to more effectively deliver nutrients to agricultural crops, both when applied to the soil or via the foliage.

To study uptake and distribution of mineral ions and nanoparticles in plants we use a range of powerful multi-elemental imaging technologies, including laser ablation-ICP-MS (LA-ICP-MS), Nano-Computed Tomography (Nano-CT) and Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM).

I will demonstrate a range of recent cases where we have used elemental bioimaging techniques to study how essential mineral ions and nanoparticles interact with plant tissue. I will show how these techniques can be used to study the fundamental processes controlling uptake and assimilation at the single cell level. I will also show how we can extrapolate this information to produce a new generation of more efficient fertilizers for the benefit of farmers economy, environment and climate.

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KP3

SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT APPROACHES FOR MICROPLASTIC POLLUTION

Güleda Engin

*Faculty of Civil Engineering, Department of Environmental Engineering, Yildiz Technical
University, Istanbul, Turkey*

Over the past two decades, the uncontrolled production, use, and disposal of plastics have resulted in the widespread occurrence of microplastics (MPs), emerging as a persistent global pollutant. MPs are now detected from the deepest oceans to the highest mountains, including remote and pristine regions such as Antarctica, where I recently had the opportunity to conduct field investigations. This global ubiquity highlights their environmental persistence and the urgent need for sustainable management. While wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) can remove a significant fraction of MPs, they also act as point sources, discharging considerable amounts into aquatic systems. Conventional and advanced processes, such as membrane bioreactors, primarily transfer MPs into sludge streams without achieving complete degradation. Therefore, innovative approaches focusing on oxidative and enzymatic degradation of MPs, which avoid secondary waste generation, are essential for effective and sustainable management strategies. This presentation will discuss the global challenge of MP pollution, insights gained from the Antarctica Expedition, and novel degradation pathways for mitigating this pressing environmental threat.

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KP4

ALGAE AS A PROMISING ORGANISM FOR THE ENVIRONMENT AND HEALTH

Eyüp İlker Saygılı

*Department of Medical Biochemistry, School of Medicine, SANKO University, Gaziantep,
Turkey*

Nowadays, the bioeconomy strategies are increasingly recognized as a key approach to balancing economic development with social well-being and environmental integrity. Achieving sustainability in food and agricultural systems requires a multidisciplinary transformation that integrates resource efficient biomass processing, optimized energy and water use, improved packaging and waste management, greenhouse gas mitigation, and circular economy principles across the value chain. In the context of persistent food loss and waste, global food insecurity, and rising demand for natural resources, bio-based and biodegradable raw materials are becoming essential inputs for future production models.

Within the broader bioeconomy, the blue bioeconomy emphasizes marine bioresources as renewable feedstocks for high value-added products and industrial solutions. Marine algae encompassing microalgae and macroalgae (seaweeds) are particularly promising due to their potential for carbon dioxide fixation and their diverse biochemical composition, including proteins, lipids, minerals, and bioactive compounds. These features support a wide range of applications, including functional foods, nutraceuticals, cosmeceuticals, pharmaceuticals, biomaterials, sustainable packaging, and bioenergy. Türkiye's geostrategic position, surrounded by four seas, provides significant opportunities to initiate and scale blue bioeconomy initiatives based on marine resources.

This study further highlights the enabling role of smart agriculture technologies such as sensors, remote sensing, artificial intelligence, robotics, and image processing in enhancing productivity and sustainability. Finally, as climate change intensifies pressure on ecosystems, life sciences driven innovation is expected to play an increasingly central role in shaping resilient, knowledge-based economies through novel processes, products, and services across health, energy, and food systems.

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KP5

ACOUSTIC TELEMETRY APPLICATIONS IN TURKISH SEAS

Aytaç Özgül

Faculty of Fisheries, Ege University, İzmir, Türkiye

We urgently need scientifically based methods, integrated research platforms, and international collaborations to protect and manage marine species and their habitats. Acoustic telemetry, one of these methods, is a tracking method that works by detecting signals from acoustic transmitters with acoustic receivers. It is widely used to determine the habitat and behavioral patterns of aquatic organisms. Acoustic telemetry was first used in tracking of salmon migration in the early 1960s. With the development of this technology, the habitats and behavioral patterns of many ecologically and economically important aquatic organisms are determined with more than 20,000 active receivers worldwide.

The first use of this technology in Türkiye was in 2015. The movement patterns of some fish species in the artificial reef area of Edremit Bay were examined using this technology for fisheries management. Subsequently, the Strategic Infrastructure for Advanced Animal Tracking in European Seas (STRAITS) project, funded by the EU Horizon Programme, has installed acoustic telemetry arrays in the Denmark Strait, the North Channel, the Strait of Gibraltar, and the Turkish Straits System. With this project, flagship species are being tagged with acoustic transmitters to track their migrations across Europe. Within the STRAITS, 25 acoustic receivers were placed on the Turkish coasts, starting from the Edremit Bay to the Gulf of Saros, the Çanakkale Straits, both coasts of the Sea of Marmara, the İstanbul Strait, and the Western Black Sea. In addition, acoustic telemetry studies are ongoing to track sturgeon in the Black Sea, lionfish in the Gulf of Gökova, bluefin tuna around sea-cage fish farms in the Aegean Sea, and shark species in the Eastern Mediterranean region.

This study, which examines the development of acoustic telemetry studies in Turkish seas from past to present, aims to contribute to the protection of biodiversity by raising awareness of the use of acoustic telemetry technology in understanding the habitats and movement patterns of aquatic organisms.

Keywords: Acoustic telemetry, STRAITS, Fish migration, Fisheries management, Türkiye

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KP6

BIOTECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUATIC FOOD SYSTEMS: INSIGHTS FROM FAO'S SCIENCE AND INNOVATION STRATEGY

Haydar Fersoy

FAO Regional Office for Europe and Central Asia

Science, technology, and innovation are foundational to transforming aquatic food systems and achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. Within this context, the FAO Science and Innovation Strategy emphasizes the strategic importance of harnessing a wide spectrum of scientific disciplines and knowledge systems to drive sustainable change. Biotechnology, in particular, stands out as a powerful tool for advancing fisheries and aquaculture, offering solutions that improve productivity, enhance nutritional outcomes, and reduce environmental pressures.

FAO's approach to biotechnology in aquatic food systems encompasses technical support, capacity building, policy guidance, and the facilitation of inclusive dialogue among Members. This ensures that the benefits and risks of biotechnological applications are transparently assessed and responsibly managed. From traditional practices such as microbial fermentation and bio-based water treatments to cutting-edge innovations like gene editing and synthetic biology, biotechnology is reshaping how aquatic species are bred, managed, and harvested. These technologies enable precise genetic improvements, support disease resistance, and contribute to the development of alternative feed sources, all of which are critical for sustainable aquaculture.

Emerging tools such as precision fermentation and digital platforms powered by artificial intelligence are further expanding the frontiers of biotechnology in fisheries and aquaculture. These innovations allow for real-time diagnostics, genomic mapping, and predictive analytics, enhancing decision-making and operational efficiency. However, the rapid evolution of these technologies also calls for robust policy frameworks to ensure safety, equity, and accessibility, particularly for small-scale producers and vulnerable communities.

By embedding biotechnology within its strategic pillars, the FAO Science and Innovation Strategy provides a coherent and inclusive roadmap for integrating scientific advances into aquatic food systems. It supports Member States in developing context-specific solutions, fosters interdisciplinary collaboration, and promotes responsible innovation aligned with sustainability goals. This strategic alignment reinforces FAO's Blue Transformation vision, positioning biotechnology as a catalyst for healthier oceans, improved livelihoods, and resilient aquatic ecosystems.

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Invited Speakers

Doğan Taşkent, ATABAY Pharmaceuticals and Fine Chemicals, Türkiye
Strength of Turkish Pharma Sector and How to Use It to Develop Novel Drugs

Begüm Zeybek, Dr., University of Oxford, UK
Towards Sustainable and Adaptive Prosthetic Sockets

Beste Turanlı, Assoc. Prof. Marmara University, Türkiye
*Deciphering Molecular Mechanisms of Environmental Pollutant Exposure through
Systems Toxicology*

Erdem Günsür, Ford Otosan, Türkiye
Material Genomics: Rethinking How We Build Our World

Luigi Nataloni, Cereal Docks, Italy
*From Disruption to Direction: Cerealdocks' Vision for the Future of Plant-Based
Proteins*

**Emine Aytunga Arık Kibar, Dr., TÜBİTAK Marmara Research Center,
Türkiye**
From Vision to Action: The Story of the PROTWIN Project

**Zekeriya Ar, Bolu Directorate of Provincial Agriculture and Forestry,
Türkiye**
Conservation of Blue Sources: Our Experiences in Fisheries

Levent Bat, Prof. Dr., Sinop University, Türkiye
*Sustainable Macroalgae Management in the Black Sea Basin: Utilizing Blooms for
Environmental Protection and Bioeconomy*

**Yunus Emre Fakıoğlu, Dr., General Fisheries Commission for the
Mediterranean, FAO Black Sea Technical Unit, Bulgaria**
*Learning from fishers: Use of local ecological knowledge to better understand
sturgeon-fishery interactions in the Black Sea*

Murat Dağtekin, Dr., Central Fisheries Research Institute, Türkiye
*Can Awareness-Raising Activities Contribute to the Recovery of Sturgeon Stocks in
the Black Sea?*

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Abstracts for Invited Presentations

The abstracts for invited presentations are listed according to the congress program

IP1- Medical Biotechnology

STRENGTH OF TURKISH PHARMA SECTOR AND HOW TO USE IT TO DEVELOP NOVEL DRUGS
DOĞAN TAŞKENT

IP2- Medical Biotechnology

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE AND ADAPTIVE PROSTHETIC SOCKETS
DR. BEGÜM ZEYBEK-SAĞLAM

IP3- Environmental Biotechnology

DECIPHERING MOLECULAR MECHANISMS OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTANT EXPOSURE
THROUGH SYSTEMS TOXICOLOGY
ASSOC. PROF. BESTE TURANLI

IP4-Environemtal Biotechnology

MATERIAL GENOMICS: RETHINKING HOW WE BUILD OUR WORLD
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FROM DISRUPTION TO DIRECTION: CEREALDOCKS' VISION FOR THE FUTURE OF PLANT-BASED
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IP7- Aquatic Biotechnology

CONSERVATION OF BLUE SOURCES: OUR EXPERIENCES IN FISHERIES
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IP8- Aquatic Biotechnology

SUSTAINABLE MACROALGAE MANAGEMENT IN THE BLACK SEA BASIN: UTILIZING BLOOMS
FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND BIOECONOMY
PROF. DR. LEVENT BAT

IP9- Aquatic Biotechnology

LEARNING FROM FISHERS: USE OF LOCAL ECOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE TO BETTER
UNDERSTAND STURGEON-FISHERY INTERACTIONS IN THE BLACK SEA
DR. YUNUS EMRE FAKIOĞLU

IP10- Aquatic Biotechnology

CAN AWARENESS-RAISING ACTIVITIES CONTRIBUTE TO THE RECOVERY OF STURGEON
STOCKS IN THE BLACK SEA?
DR. MURAT DAĞTEKİN

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IP1

STRENGTH OF TURKISH PHARMA SECTOR AND HOW TO USE IT DEVELOP NOVEL DRUGS

Doğan Taşkent

ATABAY Pharmaceuticals and Fine Chemicals, Türkiye

The pharmaceutical sector is recognized as one of the most strategic pillars for national resilience, alongside education, defense, energy, and agriculture, particularly in an era marked by global political, economic, and natural challenges. Ensuring self-sufficiency in pharmaceutical production is therefore critical for public health security and sustainable development. This presentation provides a comprehensive overview of the pharmaceutical and biotechnology landscape in Türkiye, framed through both industrial experience and ecosystem-level analysis.

A key focus is placed on Atabay Pharmaceuticals as a representative example of Türkiye's well-established pharmaceutical industry. With a multi-generational history, robust manufacturing infrastructure, and a broad therapeutic portfolio encompassing analgesics, cough and cold products, antibiotics, antivirals, and treatments for chronic diseases, Atabay demonstrates the strength and continuity of domestic pharmaceutical production capacity.

In parallel, the presentation examines the evolving pharmaceutical and biotechnology ecosystem in Türkiye, highlighting positive trends such as increasing patent activity, the expansion of industrial R&D centers, the emergence of biotechnology startups, and the growing role of national R&D institutions and clinical research centers. Despite these advancements and existing governmental support mechanisms, significant challenges remain, particularly in the development of novel drugs. High costs, long timelines, and the complexity of clinical trials continue to limit innovation.

The presentation concludes by emphasizing the need for more supportive, flexible, and innovation-oriented regulatory frameworks to accelerate novel drug development and strengthen Türkiye's position in the global pharmaceutical and biotechnology arena.

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IP2

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE AND ADAPTIVE PROSTHETIC SOCKETS

Begüm Zeybek-Sağlam

Surgical Intervention Trials Unit (SITU), Nuffield Department of Surgical Sciences, University of Oxford, Botnar Research Centre, Windmill Road, Oxford, OX3 7LD

Background/Introduction

Globally, over 40 million people live with amputations, profoundly affecting mobility and quality of life. The prosthetic socket, connecting residual limb and prosthesis, determines comfort, control, and function. Traditional manufacturing often requires multiple castings, causing material waste, delays, and high clinical burden. Clinical trials validating these technologies also face sustainability challenges from resource-intensive workflows.

Purpose

The SocketSense project set out to explore whether smart, sensor-enabled sockets could offer a more efficient and sustainable alternative. The goal was twofold: to improve the socket fitting process for patients and to demonstrate how digital tools could streamline clinical evaluations.

Methods

At the heart of the system were Quantum Technology Supersensors™ (QTSS™) - flexible sensors capable of measuring pressure, shear, and friction inside the socket. These sensors fed real-time data into biomechanical algorithms, which helped clinicians make precise adjustments without needing to recast the socket. A digital interface allowed clinicians to visualise patient data and manage the fitting process more efficiently. The system was tested with volunteer participants to assess its usability and impact.

Results and Future Directions

Outcomes included environmentally friendly QTSS™ sensors, a low-power sensory system for real-time monitoring, advanced algorithms for fit assessment, and a software platform streamlining workflows. Preliminary observations from participants suggest the system may assist in improving socket fit and usability. Sensor-guided adjustments reduced castings and material use, enabling faster fitting.

Conclusion

Sensor-enabled sockets, combined with advanced analytics and digital tools, offer a promising approach to sustainable prosthetic fitting and evaluation. Future developments may include dynamic socket rectification, enabling real-time geometry adaptation to redistribute pressure, enhance circulation, and improve long-term comfort.

Funder

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IP3

DECIPHERING MOLECULAR MECHANISMS OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTANT EXPOSURE THROUGH SYSTEMS TOXICOLOGY

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Pesticides, heavy metals, nanoplastics, and endocrine disruptors are among the environmental pollutants whose toxicity is extensively studied today. Pesticides, one of these pollutants, are chemicals used to enhance agricultural productivity; however, certain types, such as organophosphates and pyrethroids, are known to be used extensively despite their toxic effects. Nanoplastics, particularly materials like polystyrene, can not only impact the biological functions of organisms but also facilitate the transport of other toxic substances. Both pollutants are actually materials with residues frequently present in the foods and products we use daily, as well as throughout our environment. Considering their wide spread use, these pollutants pose significant threats to public health and ecosystems due to their acute and chronic effects.

In our recent projects, we follow a similar workflow to understand the molecular effects of acute and chronic toxicity of polystyrene as a nanoplastic and deltamethrin as a pesticide. We applied pollutants to the model organism *S. cerevisiae* at different concentrations in YPD medium. Later, mRNA sequencing was employed to identify differentially expressed genes (DEGs). The datasets in GEO database were collected if a dataset includes both diseased and healthy samples without any manipulation or treatment (drug, mutation, siRNA, etc.) and with at least three samples in each group. Transcriptome data from 120 microarray datasets comprising 45 different diseases and more than 20 tissues were collected. DEGs were analyzed and considered significant due to the criteria of adjusted p-value <0.05. Regarding the expression patterns of pollutants we found in our projects, we conducted a comparative evaluation of all disease gene expression profiles to identify similarities.

Overall, the comprehensive evaluation of the underlying molecular mechanisms after exposure to these pollutants may pinpoint a broad perspective on the progression of diseases comprising pediatric cancers.

Keywords: systems toxicology, transcriptome, environmental pollutants, disease mechanism

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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IP4

MATERIAL GENOMICS: RETHINKING HOW WE BUILD OUR WORLD

Erdem Günsür

Ford Otosan, Türkiye

We stand at a pivotal moment in history — one where failing to address the grand challenge of climate change may result in the collapse of human civilization alongside countless other species. This crisis is deeply rooted in many sources, one of the most significant being our fundamental need for shelter and protection: the built environment.

Today, the construction sector alone accounts for nearly 40% of global CO₂ emissions, consumes half of all raw materials extracted, and generates more than a third of the total waste we produce. Each wall, each tile, carries an invisible ecological cost that stretches from the depths of mines to the upper layers of the atmosphere.

In building to protect ourselves from nature, we have built an environment from which nature now needs protection. To break this paradox, we must reframe the challenge as a materials problem — one defined not only by *what* we build, but *what we build with*, and *how* we make it.

Although often called the “sleeping giant” of innovation, the construction sector remains slow-moving, risk-averse, and bound by low profit margins. Yet the shockwaves of two transformative deep-tech domains — biotechnology and artificial intelligence — now have the potential to awaken this giant.

Material Genomics proposes a cross-disciplinary approach to re-imagining our man-made world from the molecular level up. It seeks to understand, design, and build *with* nature — leveraging the generative power of biotechnology and the analytical intelligence of AI to discover new material systems that are efficient, regenerative, and alive to their context.

If we learn to read and design with this genetic language of matter, we may rediscover how to build — not apart from the planet, but as part of it. The built environment — humanity’s search for shelter — has become one of the planet’s greatest sources of harm, accounting for nearly 40% of global CO₂ emissions, half of all raw material extraction, and over one-third of total waste. In building to protect ourselves from nature, we have built an environment that now threatens it.

Material Genomics reframes this paradox as a materials problem, proposing a cross-disciplinary approach that merges biotechnology and artificial intelligence to reimagine our man-made world from the molecular level up. By decoding how material composition, structure, and processing shape environmental impact, this framework aims to create regenerative, intelligent materials that work *with* nature’s logic — not against it.

If we learn to read and design with this genetic language of matter, we may rediscover how to build — not apart from the planet, but as part of it.

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IP5

FROM DISRUPTION TO DIRECTION: CEREALDOCKS' VISION FOR THE FUTURE OF PLANT-BASED PROTEINS

Luigi Nataloni

Cereal Docks, Italy

Cereal Docks is a leading Italian company and one of Europe's top players in grain trading and oilseed crushing, especially soy and sunflower. The oils are sold in the food market, while the proteins are mainly used in feed.

Six years ago, we began diversifying with the goal of becoming a leader in sustainable human nutrition. Entering the plant-based protein market was a strategic opportunity, especially during a time of global excitement around alternative proteins. We studied the market, focusing on the U.S. and Canada, but noticed many companies were failing due to economic challenges.

We investigated consumer resistance to plant-based products and identified four key purchase drivers: 1) taste, 2) sustainability, 3) price parity with meat-based products, and 4) nutritional density. At the time, most plant-based proteins were used in meat analogues targeting flexitarians. Many companies, especially in the U.S., launched overly complex products with 20+ ingredients, which negatively impacted cost and sustainability—slowing market growth and triggering crises.

At Cereal Docks, we believe the future of plant-based proteins lies in simpler products with fewer ingredients, such as pasta, bakery items, and snacks. We recently acquired Prista Commerce, a Bulgarian company producing sunflower protein flour for the food market. We are also developing an innovative pasta product called Pasta Sole, in collaboration with Italian pasta maker Sgambaro. It contains 28% protein and is designed to meet consumer expectations for taste, nutrition, and simplicity.

We are actively expanding into the bakery and snack segments, which we believe offer the highest growth potential in the coming years.

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IP6

FROM VISION TO ACTION: THE STORY OF THE PROTWIN PROJECT

Aytunga Arık Kibar

*TÜBİTAK MAM, Climate and Life Sciences, Food Technology Research Group, Gebze Kocaeli,
Türkiye*

The global transition towards sustainable food systems has intensified interest in plant-based proteins, driven by population growth, environmental pressures, and the need for nutritionally adequate and resilient protein sources. In this context, the Horizon Europe Twinning project PROTWIN (Twinning Towards Scientific and Technological Excellence in Plant Protein Research; GA: 101186662) aims to strengthen scientific excellence and research capacity in Türkiye by advancing knowledge on plant protein functionality, nutritional quality, and sustainability.

PROTWIN focuses on protein diversification through the valorisation of locally grown protein-rich crops and agro-food by-products, including legumes, oilseeds, cereals, and industrial side streams. A comprehensive benchmarking framework is applied to identify promising protein sources based on agricultural adaptability, nutritional composition, processing potential, environmental impact, and regulatory and consumer acceptance.

The project integrates advanced analytical approaches to evaluate protein quality and digestibility, including standardized in vitro digestion models, metabolomics and proteomics, and structure–function relationship studies. Furthermore, the effects of selected plant protein ingredients on gut microbiota composition and metabolic activity are investigated using static and dynamic gastrointestinal models, including the SHIME system. Knowledge generated is translated into pilot-scale development of plant-based food products, demonstrating real-world applicability across diverse food categories.

Through its interdisciplinary and capacity-building approach, PROTWIN contributes to the development of nutritious, appealing, and environmentally sustainable plant-based food ingredients, while reinforcing international collaboration and excellence in plant protein research.

Keywords:

Plant-based proteins; Protein diversification; Innovative protein extraction; Digestibility and gut microbiota

Acknowledgement:

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IP7

CONSERVATION OF BLUE SOURCES: OUR EXPERIENCES IN FISHERIES

Zekeriya Ar

Bolu Directorate of Provincial Agriculture and Forestry, Türkiye

Gölköy Aquaculture Production Station, operating under the Bolu Provincial Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry, has been actively contributing to the conservation of blue resources and sustainable fisheries management since 1974. The facility, transferred to the Provincial Directorate in 2021, covers an area of approximately 20 hectares and includes hatchery units, concrete and earthen production ponds, and modern aquaculture infrastructure. In 2024, a 30 m³/h capacity closed-loop aquaculture filtration system was installed, enabling efficient water reuse, energy savings, and fully controlled production conditions. The first production using this system was successfully carried out in 2025.

Within the framework of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry's "Fisheries of Water Resources Project," the station plays a significant role in stock enhancement, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable fisheries. In 2025, over 5.5 million juvenile scaly carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) were produced using fully controlled reproduction techniques and released into 63 water resources across 10 provinces, exceeding planned production targets.

In addition to carp production, the facility is engaged in the conservation-oriented culture of endangered sturgeon species. Roe deer sturgeon (*Acipenser gueldenstaedtii*) broodstock were successfully induced to spawn for the first time in 2024–2025, resulting in approximately 50,000 larvae. Juveniles are being reared under controlled conditions and are planned for release into the Black Sea and its tributaries as part of national stock restoration programs.

Overall, the activities carried out at Gölköy Aquaculture Production Station contribute to ecological sustainability, economic development, and food security, highlighting the importance of scientifically based stock enhancement practices for the preservation of aquatic biodiversity.

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IP8

SUSTAIBALE MACROALGAE MANAGEMENT IN THE BLACK SEA BASIN: UTILIZING BLOOMS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND BIOECONOMY

Levent Bat

Sinop University Fisheries Faculty, Department of Hydrobiology, 57000 Sinop, Türkiye

Macroalgae (seaweeds) play a critical role in marine ecosystems by providing habitat, food, and oxygen. However, in certain cases, they grow rapidly, causing macroalgal blooms (excessive growth). This phenomenon is caused by eutrophication due to excessive nitrogen and phosphorus input. Eutrophication causes the death of marine organisms, contaminates waters, and negatively impacts coastal tourism and recreational activities. In the Black Sea region, the rapid growth of seaweeds also creates an economic problem, since cleaning and controlling them requires extra costs.

The MACRO CLEAN Project, funded by the European Union, works to solve these problems by using macroalgae in useful ways and reducing human-induced eutrophication and blooms. Its objectives are to establish a standardized research methodology, strengthen laboratory infrastructure, and explore the potential of macroalgae in sustainable products such as fertilizers and bioplastics. It also focuses on increasing awareness and encouraging cooperation between countries for better coastal management. Project partners are Sinop University and the Union of Marmara Municipalities (Türkiye), Batum State University (Georgia), and Shumen University (Bulgaria).

A multidisciplinary team has developed a methodology involving seasonal sampling of dominant seaweeds (*Ulva* spp. and *Cystoseira* sp.), seawater and sediment analyses, fertilizer trials in greenhouses, and preliminary bioplastic testing. Protocols for data collection and quality assurance have been developed, while stakeholder engagement has been promoted through surveys, international study visits, and outreach activities.

In the first year, laboratory equipment was procured, a greenhouse established, two seasonal samples collected, and fertilizers (solid, liquid, and compost) prepared and bioplastic studies were started. Awareness was raised through websites, social media, press releases, and university events. Study visits to France and China were carried out.

All efforts created a foundation for sustainable macroalgae management in the Black Sea Basin. Initial results show macroalgal blooms can become useful resources, contributing to environmental protection and the bioeconomy. Future steps will test fertilizers on strawberry and lettuce plants in greenhouses, and detailed bioplastic characterization and pilot action plans will be implemented.

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Keywords: MACRO CLEAN Project, eutrophication, fertilizer, bioplastics, Black Sea Basin,
sustainable resource utilization

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IP9

LEARNING FROM FISHERS: USE OF LOCAL ECOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE TO BETTER UNDERSTAND STURGEON-FISHERY INTERACTIONS IN THE BLACK SEA

Yunus Emre Fakıoğlu^{1*}, Hüseyin Özbilgin^{1,2}, Elisabetta Betulla Morello³

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³General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean, Food and Agriculture Organization of
the United Nations, Rome, Italy

Background/Introduction

Sturgeons are worldwide critically endangered and incidental capture in fisheries remains one of the main threats to their survival. To combat the persistent lack of information on the marine phase of their life cycle in the Black Sea, the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) established a pilot project on sturgeons, following the recommendation of the Working Group on the Black Sea (WGBS) at its ninth session and in line with Resolution GFCM/44/2021/5. The project has been implemented through the GFCM BlackSea4Fish programme, engaging fishers and stakeholders via Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) surveys and awareness-raising campaigns.

Purpose

The aim was to gather fisher-based knowledge to improve better understanding of bycatch, identify seasonal and spatial hotspots, evaluate gear-related mortality, thereby contributing to the effective management actions.

Methods

Over two consecutive years, structured interviews were conducted across Bulgaria, Georgia, Romania and Türkiye to explore fisher knowledge on bycatch, mortality and perception of non-compliant activities. LEK phase I (2023) consisted of 302 interviews. Phase II (2024) expanded the approach, conducting 329 questionnaires with 544 gear-specific records, complemented by participatory mapping of 641 bycatch hotspots. Trip-level data were then digitized into seasonal maps.

Results

Fishers reported sturgeon bycatch across all countries, with spring showing the highest frequency, (~1 sturgeon/10 fishing days), dropping seven-fold in summer. Mapping revealed concentrated hotspots in southeastern, southern, and western coasts. Set gillnets caused the highest mortality (~20%, 0.03 deaths per trip-day), followed by pelagic trawls (9%) and trammel nets (6%).

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Conclusion

The pilot project fostered a regional expert network linking scientists, administrations, and fishers, laying the basis for long-term cooperation. The findings led to a GFCM binding recommendation banning marine sturgeon fisheries in the Black Sea and supported their listing among vulnerable species of GFCM Data Collection Reference Framework. Complementary actions, including multilingual safe-handling and release guidelines and fisher training are underway to further reduce mortality. Building on this work, tagging studies have been highlighted as future priorities by the network to clarify habitat use and identify areas overlapping with fisheries.

Acknowledgements

The pilot project is implemented under the BlackSea4Fish programme in partnership with FAO and funded by the European Union (for work in Bulgaria and Romania) and the Global Environment Facility (GEF) in the context of the FishEBM BS project (for work in Georgia and Türkiye). The project activities are carried out in cooperation with the Executive Agency of Fisheries and Aquaculture (EAFA) from Bulgaria, the National Environment Agency (NEA) and the Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources Protection from Georgia, the National Institute for Marine Research and Development (NIMRD) and the National Agency for Fisheries and Aquaculture (NAFA) from Romania, and the Central Fisheries Research Institute (SUMAE) and the General Directorate of Fisheries and Aquaculture (BSGM) from Türkiye, under the supervision of the GFCM Black Sea Technical Unit.

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IP10

CAN AWARENESS-RAISING ACTIVITIES CONTRIBUTE TO THE RECOVERY OF STURGEON STOCKS IN THE BLACK SEA?

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Karapaça, Volkan Örnek**

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Sturgeon species in the Black Sea, including *Acipenser gueldenstaedtii*, *A. nuidiventris*, *A. stellatus*, *A. sturio*, and *Huso huso*, represent ancient lineages of high ecological and economic importance. However, their populations have been subjected to severe pressures throughout history. Formerly, these species migrated to the Yeşilırmak, Kızılırmak, and Sakarya rivers for spawning, but such migrations have now disappeared. Since the mid-20th century, rapid urbanization, technological developments, and habitat loss have accelerated population decline. Overfishing, especially during reproductive periods, critically affected late-maturing species such as *H. huso*. Intensive caviar production persisted until the 1970s, followed by the introduction of seasonal and size-based restrictions. Despite restocking efforts, natural stocks remain vulnerable. This study evaluates the multifaceted threats currently facing sturgeon in the Black Sea, including illegal fishing and black-market caviar trade, incidental bycatch in commercial gears, habitat degradation from sand and gravel extraction, the expansion of aquaculture on riverbeds, benthic habitat destruction by bottom-contact fishing gears, and the compounding effects of climate change on hydrological regimes. At the same time, this study highlights the contribution of awareness-raising and monitoring activities implemented in the southern Black Sea. These initiatives have demonstrated notable success, particularly in the release of smaller individuals back into the wild, while underscoring the need for alternative approaches to protect larger specimens. Importantly, the findings reveal that continuing awareness programs holds significant potential to mitigate threats and support the recovery of sturgeon stocks, providing a constructive basis for regional conservation strategies

Keywords: Black Sea, sturgeon, awareness-raising activities, conservation strategies, illegal fisheries, stock recovery

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HARNESSING SULFUR-OXIDIZING BACTERIA FOR SUSTAINABLE PLANT SULFATE NUTRITION

ZAEEMA KHAN

OP2-Plant Biotechnology

EFFECTS OF DUCKWEED AMENDMENT ON CUCUMBER SHOOT GROWTH UNDER VARYING SOIL BORON CONDITIONS

RIFAT BUĞRA BİLDİRİ

OP3-Plant Biotechnology

THE ROLE OF SOIL MICROBIOTA IN ECOSYSTEM HEALTH AND SUSTAINABLE TEA CULTIVATION: INSIGHTS FROM eDNA AND METAGENOMIC APPROACHES

ATAKAN YILDIZ

OP4- Plant Biotechnology

MOLECULAR DIALOGUE BETWEEN MAIZE (ZEA MAYS) AND FUSARIUM VERTICILLIODES: A CROSS-KINGDOM RNAi PERSPECTIVE FOR SUSTAINABLE DISEASE RESISTANCE

SENA KIZILBOĞA

OP5- Plant Biotechnology

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SUSTAINABLE BIOCOMPOSITE PLANT GROW PLUGS FOR SOILLESS AGRICULTURE

ABDULLAH HİLMİ COŞAR

OP6- Plant Biotechnology

MODULATION OF RESVERATROL PRODUCTION BY METHYL JASMONATE AND MELATONIN IN CALLUS AND ORGANOGENIC CULTURES OF MORUS SPECIES

ESMA KOCA

OP7-Medical Biotechnology

IDENTIFICATION OF NOVEL LONG NON-CODING RNAs AS DIAGNOSTIC AND PROGNOSTIC BIOMARKERS IN NSCLC

ABDULLAH KARADAĞ

OP8-Medical Biotechnology

IMMUNOMODULATORY EFFECT OF GRAPE SEED EXTRACT ON IMMUNE CELLS

TZONKA GODJEVARGOVA

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OP9-Medical Biotechnology

METABOLISM-ASSOCIATED TRANSCRIPTOMIC ALTERATIONS REVEAL NOVEL
THERAPEUTIC TARGETS IN A PARKINSON'S DISEASE CELLULAR MODEL

BÜŞRA BIÇAK

OP10-Medical Biotechnology

EXPLORING THE SUITABILITY OF TI-NB-ZR ALLOYS FOR LOAD-BEARING IMPLANTS
THROUGH MICROSTRUCTURAL, MECHANICAL, AND BIOLOGICAL ANALYSES

YÜKSEL ÇETİN

OP11-Medical Biotechnology

UNCOVERING THE MECHANISMS OF KOREAN GINSENG IN ATOPIC DERMATITIS VIA
NETWORK PHARMACOLOGY AND MOLECULAR DOCKING

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OP1

HARNESSING SULFUR-OXIDIZING BACTERIA FOR SUSTAINABLE PLANT SULFATE NUTRITION

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Sulfur (S) is essential for plant nutrition, influencing protein synthesis, enzyme activation, and chlorophyll formation. However, declining atmospheric sulfur dioxide deposition has caused widespread S deficiencies, reducing crop yield and quality. Many S sources, including elemental sulfur (eS), reduced sulfides, thiosulfate (S₂O₃), manure, and compost, have low availability, often necessitating additional mineral S fertilizers. Converting these forms into plant-accessible sulfate (SO₄²⁻) is crucial for reducing fertilizer dependence while sustaining productivity. This study explores the potential of sulfur-oxidizing bacteria (SOB) as biofertilizers converting eS and S₂O₃ into SO₄²⁻. SOB were isolated from water, sediment, and soil samples from a pond, an artificial lake, and a natural lake in the Marmara region. Cultures were grown in Starkey and NCL broth supplemented with 1% (w/v) eS. After 30 days, significant pH reductions indicated active S oxidation. The lowest pH (3.16) was recorded in NCL broth from pond water, with artificial and natural lake sediments also showing acidification. Sulfate production, measured by the barium chloride turbidity method, was highest in artificial (355 mg L⁻¹) and natural lake (358 mg L⁻¹) sediments. Microbial isolation and biochemical characterization identified gram-negative short rods with biotin-dependent growth, variable sugar utilization, and both chemoautotrophic and chemoheterotrophic traits. S₂O₃ medium containing pond water isolates exhibited the highest S oxidation efficiency and was used in growth trials. SOB-treated canola (*Brassica napus*) seeds exhibited a 96% germination rate, 16% higher than that of the controls. To confirm the S oxidation efficiency, the isolated SOB was co-cultured with Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*) seeds in three Murashige and Skoog (MS) media: (i) standard MS containing SO₄²⁻, (ii) sulfur-deficient MS, and (iii) MS supplied with eS as the sole S source. The SOB enhanced plant growth under S-limited conditions. This study highlights SOB as a sustainable biofertilizer, enhancing S nutrition in conventional and organic agriculture.

Keyword: *sulfur nutrition, plant-microbe interactions, biofertilizers, Brassica, sulfur-oxidizing bacteria*

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OP2

EFFECTS OF DUCKWEED AMENDMENT ON CUCUMBER SHOOT GROWTH UNDER VARYING SOIL BORON CONDITIONS

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Common duckweed (*Lemna minor* L.) is an aquatic macrophyte recognized as a sustainable bioresource with potential applications in biofertilizer production in circular bioeconomy systems. This study evaluated the effects of duckweed on the shoot growth of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L. cv. K1tır F1) grown in alkaline and acidic soils with varying boron (B) concentrations (0, 2, and 10 ppm) under greenhouse conditions. Duckweed biomass was incorporated into both soil types at rates of 0%, 0.25%, and 0.50% (w/w), and cucumber shoot growth was monitored in response to changing B levels. In alkaline soil, duckweed application enhanced shoot biomass, with increases of 44% and 28% over the control in the absence of B. While higher B concentrations reduced shoot biomass in untreated alkaline soil, duckweed application mitigated this decline. At the toxic B level (10 ppm), shoot biomass decreased by 26% in control but only by 3% with 0.25% duckweed treatment, and even increased by 13% with 0.50% treatment. Conversely, in acidic soil, duckweed consistently suppressed cucumber growth, regardless of dose. Increasing doses of B application could not alter shoot dry weight in control acidic soil while duckweed introduction at both application rates severely suppressed crop growth. These findings suggested that duckweed application under alkaline conditions might enhanced B adsorption, thereby mitigating B toxicity in plant tissues. In acidic soil, however, duckweed might acted as a B fertilizer, which could aggravate B toxicity symptoms in plants with increasing B levels. Further research is required to elucidate tissue mineral composition and crop yield performance across different environmental conditions.

Keyword: *duckweed, cucumber, boron, fertilizer, soil amendment*

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OP3

THE ROLE OF SOIL MICROBIOTA IN ECOSYSTEM HEALTH AND SUSTAINABLE TEA CULTIVATION: INSIGHTS FROM EDNA AND METAGENOMIC APPROACHES

Atakan Yıldız

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Soil microbiota are vital drivers of ecosystem processes, facilitating nutrient cycling, organic matter turnover, and plant–microbe interactions that underpin soil health and ecological stability. In tea agroecosystems, conserving microbial diversity is essential not only for sustainable crop productivity but also for preserving the ecological integrity of cultivated landscapes. This study explores the taxonomic composition and functional potential of soil microbial communities in tea plantations using a combination of environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding and shotgun metagenomic approaches.

These high-resolution, culture-independent methods allowed us to profile microbial assemblages and infer ecosystem functions across seasonal and environmental gradients. Dominant phyla detected included Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, Actinobacteriota, Acidobacteriota, and Chloroflexi. Notably, winter samples exhibited elevated relative abundances of Proteobacteria and Actinobacteriota, suggesting seasonal shifts in microbial community structure and function likely driven by environmental conditions and cultivation practices.

By characterizing native microbial populations, our findings highlight the critical role of belowground biodiversity in enhancing soil resilience, nutrient availability, and ecological stability under varying environmental pressures. The results support the integration of microbial diversity monitoring into sustainable land management frameworks, especially in biodiversity-rich agricultural systems such as tea cultivation. This study contributes to a growing understanding of how soil microbial ecosystems support long-term agroecological sustainability and the health of terrestrial environments.

Keyword: *Soil microbiota, eDNA, Metagenomics*

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OP4

MOLECULAR DIALOGUE BETWEEN MAIZE (ZEA MAYS) AND FUSARIUM VERTICILLIOIDES: A CROSS-KINGDOM RNAI PERSPECTIVE FOR SUSTAINABLE DISEASE RESISTANCE

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Maize is a globally significant cereal crop and a vital food and economic resource for millions. Among its most threatening pathogens is *Fusarium verticillioides*, which causes a variety of destructive diseases such as root rot, stalk rot, and ear rot. This study aims to investigate the molecular mechanisms underlying the interaction between *F. verticillioides* and maize, with a specific focus on the role of cross-kingdom RNA interference (RNAi) in host-pathogen communication. Two maize lines with contrasting resistance, one resistant and one susceptible, were used to assess differential responses. Inoculation was performed via a leaf inoculation method before the emergence of the first true leaves. Morphological traits such as leaf length, width, and area, along with physiological parameters like chlorophyll content and cell length, were measured. Notably, significant differences in leaf length were observed in the third and fourth leaves of the resistant line under infection. Biochemical assays revealed increases in phenolic compounds and changes in antioxidant enzyme activities, suggesting oxidative stress and activation of plant defense mechanisms. At the molecular level, RT-qPCR analysis indicated the presence of cross-kingdom interactions. In RI tissue, the expression level of Zm-miR398a and Zm-miR1432 did not significantly change compared to RC ($p>0.05$), but their target genes (including 26S proteasome subunit Rpn-1, a stress response component, and sphingolipid delta-4 desaturase) were significantly upregulated by 3-fold, 152-fold, and 22-fold, respectively ($p<0.01$). Although Zm-miR528a expression decreased by 89% ($p>0.05$), its target gene increased by 129%. Fungal miRNAs Fv-miR8764, Fv-miR5855, and Fv-miR7214 showed significant increases in expression by 2,214-fold, 22,000-fold, and 3,400-fold, respectively ($p<0.05$). The findings highlight RNAi-based approaches' potential to improve maize disease resistance. Enhancing these mechanisms supports sustainable crop protection and yield stability under biotic stress and climate change. This study was supported by TUBITAK (Grant number: 221O321).

Keyword: *Cross-Kingdom RNAi, Plant-Pathogen Interaction, Maize, Fusarium verticillioides, Biotic Stress*

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OP5

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SUSTAINABLE BIOCOMPOSITE PLANT GROW PLUGS FOR SOILLESS AGRICULTURE

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Soilless agriculture, or hydroponics, is a cultivation method in which plants receive nutrients directly from water rather than soil. With the rising global population, the demand for soilless agriculture, seedling production, and personalized smart farming systems is expected to increase [1,2]. However, current plant grow plugs—the substrates that hold seeds—are largely imported, costly, and often of unknown composition. They may contain harmful additives and are typically non-biodegradable. To enable sustainable farming, the plugs made from safe, biodegradable, and environmentally friendly materials are essential.

This study focuses on developing two novel plant grow plugs, designed as biocomposites with both matrix and reinforcement phases for enhanced performance. Cocopeat, a coconut husk byproduct, was selected as the main component in both designs. The binding matrix was created either from mushroom mycelium or the biodegradable polymer poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) [3]. Mycelium, the fibrous root system of fungi, grows into cocopeat under proper conditions, forming a natural network within molds [4]. In the second approach, PBAT was converted into fibers that physically interlocked with cocopeat, stabilizing the plug structure.

Comprehensive characterization techniques were applied. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis revealed sufficient porosity for root development, while Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) confirmed the absence of toxic heavy metals. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra displayed intense OH peaks, indicating hydrophilicity. Compression testing showed adequate strength, and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) confirmed thermal stability. Plant growth experiments conducted in smart garden systems demonstrated effective performance compared to that of their commercial alternatives.

When compared to a commercial plug (reference plug), the developed plugs offered competitive properties while being fully biodegradable and made from agricultural residues. The valorization of cocopeat further enhances sustainability by reducing waste. Overall, these biodegradable and non-toxic plugs provide an eco-friendly alternative that supports both healthy plant growth and sustainable agricultural practices.

Keyword: *soilless agriculture, mycelium, cocopeat, plant grow plug*

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OP6

MODULATION OF RESVERATROL PRODUCTION BY METHYL JASMONATE AND MELATONIN IN CALLUS AND ORGANOGENIC CULTURES OF MORUS SPECIES

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Mulberry species grown in Turkey (*Morus alba*, *Morus nigra*, and *Morus rubra*) are significant for their agricultural value and rich bioactive compounds. Among these, resveratrol, important for its anticancer and antioxidant properties, has potential in treating diseases. However, environmental and seasonal changes can limit resveratrol production. Therefore, plant tissue culture, especially callus cultures, provides a controlled, sustainable method and enables standardization of phenolic compounds. The limited research on mulberry tissue culture in Turkey underscores this study's contribution to the literature.

In this study, callus cultures from young leaf and nodal explants were treated with methyl jasmonate and melatonin, and their effects on resveratrol production were evaluated. In *Morus nigra* (MN), the most efficient callus from nodal explants was achieved with 200 μ M MeJA in a medium containing 2 mg/L 2,4-D and 2 mg/L NAA, yielding 0.594 ± 0.034 resveratrol, about 3.4 times higher than the control (0.174 ± 0.109). In *Morus rubra* (MR), the highest callus from leaf explants was obtained with 10 μ M melatonin in a medium containing 2 mg/L 2,4-D and 2 mg/L IBA, reaching 2.779 ± 0.061 resveratrol, 28.36 times higher than the control (0.098 ± 0.033). Callus cultures in *Morus alba* (MA) developed in 1 mg/L BAP + 0.5 mg/L NAA medium, but 10 μ M melatonin had no significant effect. Nodal explants of MN and MR produced fruit in 3 mg/L 2,4-D + 1 mg/L IBA. MR leaf explants exhibited organogenesis in 1 mg/L BAP + 0.5 mg/L NAA. Transferring these leaves to 2 mg/L 2,4-D + 1 mg/L NAA induced extensive adventitious root growth.

This study showed that resveratrol production in mulberry callus cultures can be increased with MeJa and melatonin. Root growth and organ formation were also observed under certain plant growth regulator treatments, supporting plant tissue culture as a controlled and sustainable method.

Keyword: *Mulberry, Resveratrol, Callus Culture, Methyl Jasmonate, Melatonin*

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OP7

IDENTIFICATION OF NOVEL LONG NON-CODING RNAS AS DIAGNOSTIC AND PROGNOSTIC BIOMARKERS IN NSCLC

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Background/Introduction: Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is the most common lung cancer subtype and a leading cause of mortality among cancers. Survival depends on tumor stage and early diagnosis, however, over 75% of patients are metastatic at diagnosis, limiting treatment options. Long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), transcripts longer than 200 nucleotides without protein-coding potential, are implicated in cancer progression, but many remain poorly understood in NSCLC.

Purpose: We aimed to identify lncRNAs exhibiting significant differences across three NSCLC subtypes (lung adenocarcinoma-LUAD, squamous cell carcinoma-SCC, and large cell lung carcinoma-LCLC) and clinical groups (tumor, grade, stage, smoking status) using next-generation sequencing (NGS), to elucidate their roles in diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment monitoring, and to contribute to identifying novel molecular targets.

Methods: Samples were collected from 51 lung cancer patients who underwent lobectomy, including normal lung tissue, primary tumors, adjacent normal tissues (TME), lymph nodes, and peripheral blood. Total RNA was extracted and sequenced on the Illumina HiSeq 2500 and Novaseq 6000 platforms. Differentially expressed lncRNAs were identified across subtypes and followed by functional enrichment analysis using lncAR and DAVID.

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Results: In tumor samples, one LUAD, six SCC, and five LCLC-specific novel upregulated lncRNAs were identified, while three LUAD and one SCC-specific novel downregulated lncRNAs were detected. Three upregulated lncRNAs were consistently expressed across all NSCLC subtypes, highlighting their potential as NSCLC biomarkers. GO enrichment associated several lncRNAs with cell adhesion, immune regulation, and apoptosis, while pathway analysis revealed roles in MAPK and JAK-STAT signaling. Furthermore, 22 subtype-specific upregulated (3 LUAD, 2 SCC, 17 LCLC) and 12 downregulated lncRNAs (5 LUAD, 3 SCC, 4 LCLC) were detected in blood. Consistent with previous reports, 176 upregulated and 215 downregulated lncRNAs were observed, supporting findings.

Conclusion: Novel lncRNAs with potential prognostic and biomarker roles were identified, offering opportunities to guide future diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK for the support (115S113).

Keyword: *NSCLC, lncRNA, early diagnosis, screening, biomark*

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OP8

IMMUNOMODULATORY EFFECT OF GRAPE SEED EXTRACT ON IMMUNE CELLS

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In recent years, grape seed extracts have been used as a food additive, antimicrobial agents and lipid oxidation inhibitors in food products. It has been found that grape seed extract (GSE) is extremely rich in polyphenols and has anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, anti-obesity, and etc. actions. It is believed that various polyphenolic compounds also have an effect onto the immune system. There is evidence that they direct the immune response to the so-called T-helper type 1 (Th1) cells, which are essential for combating intracellular microorganisms and malignant diseases. Lupus erythematosus (SLE) is one of the severe autoimmune diseases. In recent years, it has become clear that in patients with SLE, the balance between two of the main T-helper populations Th1 and Th2 is disturbed in favor of Th2. The effect of GSE on the growth of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) of patients with SLE and healthy controls was monitored. The effect of GSE on the percentage of Th1 and Th2 populations was studied. The obtained results unequivocally show that GSE has an activating effect on the Th1 immune response. The used extract of Syrah grape seeds, rich in proanthocyanidins, not only increases the percentage of Th1 cells, but also significantly increases the expression of the late activation marker - HLA-DR on them. This indicates that the obtained Th1 are highly differentiated effector cells that can effectively perform the functions associated with this type of immune response. The results also show a lack of influence on Th2 cells, and in healthy donors even a suppressive effect on the IL-2 receptor - CD25 of these cells. This indicates suppression of their activation and proliferation. From the results obtained, it can be concluded that the action of GSE is promising, especially in conditions with a dysregulated immune system in the Th2 direction.

Keyword: *grape seed extracts, immune cells, Lupus erythematosus*

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OP9

METABOLISM-ASSOCIATED TRANSCRIPTOMIC ALTERATIONS REVEAL NOVEL THERAPEUTIC TARGETS IN A PARKINSON'S DISEASE CELLULAR MODEL

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Background/Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by dopaminergic neuronal loss, oxidative stress, and mitochondrial dysfunction. Evidence highlights that metabolic alterations, including impaired energy homeostasis and mitochondrial dynamics, play a central role in PD pathogenesis. Thus, targeting metabolism-specific pathways may provide novel therapeutic strategies.

Purpose

This study aimed to investigate transcriptomic alterations in metabolism-related genes in a PD cellular model and to identify potential drug targets associated with metabolic pathways, thereby contributing to metabolism-focused therapeutic interventions.

Methods

SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells were differentiated and exposed to 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) to induce PD-like neurotoxicity. Transcriptomic profiling (GSE198009) was performed on samples collected post-treatment, with four replicates per group. Data were normalized, and differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified. A workflow including enrichment analyses (GO and KEGG) was applied to uncover metabolic pathways and biological processes linked to PD. Candidate genes were evaluated for their roles in mitochondrial regulation, oxidative stress response, neurotransmitter metabolism, and epigenetic control.

Results

Transcriptomic analysis revealed significant alterations in metabolism-associated genes. Key regulators involved cellular detoxification, lipid metabolism, oxidative stress modulation, dopamine metabolism, and epigenetic control of mitochondrial function. Additional processes such as neurotransmitter metabolism, NAD regulation, and Wnt-related metabolic signaling were identified as mediators of PD-associated metabolic dysfunction. Enrichment analyses highlighted

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pathways related to mitochondrial bioenergetics, oxidative stress defense, and energy metabolism as central contributors to neuronal vulnerability.

Conclusion(s)

Our findings demonstrate that metabolic dysregulation is a hallmark of PD pathogenesis and that transcriptomic profiling can uncover metabolism-specific therapeutic targets. Identifying such targets may enable development of novel strategies aimed at restoring metabolic balance and protecting neuronal function. Future studies will extend this approach to astrocytes and microglia to further clarify cell-type-specific metabolic contributions.

Acknowledgements

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Keyword: *Parkinson's disease, metabolic dysregulation, transcriptomic profiling, mitochondrial dysfunction, therapeutic targets*

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OP10

EXPLORING THE SUITABILITY OF TI–NB–ZR ALLOYS FOR LOAD-BEARING IMPLANTS THROUGH MICROSTRUCTURAL, MECHANICAL, AND BIOLOGICAL ANALYSES

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Titanium–Niobium–Zirconium (TiNbZr) alloys are widely used in implantable devices; however, their application in implantology is limited by the biomechanical mismatch between implant materials and host tissue. To address this issue, TiNbZr alloys with varying porosities were produced using powder metallurgy in combination with a space-holder technique, aiming to optimize the mechanical compatibility of load-bearing implants with bone. The microstructure and phase composition were analyzed through scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), and X-ray diffraction (XRD). Mechanical performance was assessed via uniaxial compression, while corrosion resistance was examined through potentiodynamic polarization. In vitro assessments, including cell viability and proliferation, adhesion potential, and genotoxicity were conducted using methods such as MTT assays, live/dead assay, SEM analysis, fibronectin adsorption, and plasmid-DNA interaction assays to evaluate the biological performances of the materials. The alloys exhibited both open and closed pores with uniform distribution, facilitating cell adhesion and related biological functions. Alloys with lower porosity achieved compressive strengths whereas those with higher porosity demonstrated reduced strength. The results revealed that the alloys exhibited superior cellular activities and integrated well into bone tissue, attributed to their optimized porous structure and favourable surface characteristics. Microscopic analysis of L929 and Saos-2 cell lines showed enhanced cell viability, proliferation, and cell adhesion as well as no toxic or allergic reaction was found. These findings revealed that TiNbZr alloys possessed favourable potential as next-generation bone implant, addressing limitations of permanent titanium-based biomaterials.

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Keyword: Powder metallurgy, Space holder technique, Biocompatibility, Biomaterial, Bone implant

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OP11

UNCOVERING THE MECHANISMS OF KOREAN GINSENG IN ATOPIC DERMATITIS VIA NETWORK PHARMACOLOGY AND MOLECULAR DOCKING

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A topic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder characterized by recurrent eczematous lesions and severe pruritus, significantly reducing patients' quality of life. Current treatments rely heavily on corticosteroids and immunosuppressants, which often show limited long-term efficacy and adverse effects. Thus, identifying safer therapeutic alternatives is critical. Panax ginseng (KG) has demonstrated anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties, yet its molecular mechanisms in AD remain unclear. This study aimed to systematically elucidate the potential molecular targets, core signaling pathways, and bioactive compounds of KG in the treatment of AD using an integrative network pharmacology approach. Active compounds of KG were retrieved from the TCMSP database based on pharmacokinetic criteria (OB \geq 30%, DL \geq 0.18). Potential targets were predicted via SwissTargetPrediction and cross-referenced with AD-related genes from GeneCards. Overlapping targets were analyzed using STRING for protein-protein interactions (PPI) and visualized in Cytoscape. GO and KEGG enrichment analyses were conducted with DAVID and ShinyGO. Molecular docking was performed to validate the interactions between key bioactive compounds and hub targets using AutoDock Vina. From 190 compounds, 22 bioactive molecules were identified. Target prediction yielded 394 unique protein targets, of which 200 overlapped with AD-related genes. PPI analysis revealed 199 nodes and 2,874 edges, and 77 core targets were extracted. Six hub genes (TNF, AKT1, SRC, STAT3, EGFR, CASP3) were identified as key regulators. Top compounds included Gomisins B, deoxyharringtonine, suchilactone, kaempferol, and ginsenoside Rg5. GO and KEGG analyses highlighted enrichment in kinase activity, inflammatory regulation, and PI3K-Akt and EGFR-related pathways. Molecular docking demonstrated strong binding affinities between selected compounds and hub targets, supporting their potential functional relevance in modulating AD-associated signaling pathways. This integrative analysis suggests that KG exerts therapeutic effects against AD through multi-target and multi-pathway modulation. Network pharmacology combined with molecular docking provides systems-level evidence supporting KG as a potential adjunctive therapy for AD.

Keyword: *Atopic dermatitis, Network pharmacology, Bioactive compounds, multi-target therapy, Molecular Docking*

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OP12

INVESTIGATION OF THE TOXICITY OF OSIMERTINIB AND/OR ENZALUTAMIDE AS POTENTIAL DRUG CANDIDATES FOR GLIOBLASTOMA IN CAENORHABDITIS ELEGANS

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Glioblastoma (GBM) represents one of the most aggressive forms of glioma, with current therapies offering only limited survival benefit. A potential interaction between the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) and androgen receptor (AR) have been reported in GBM cells. Osimertinib (OSI), a third-generation EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor, blocks the downstream signaling pathways activated by EGFR. Enzalutamid (ENZ), a second-generation androgen receptor inhibitor with anti-proliferative effects in cancer cells. This study aims to investigate the toxic effects of OSI and/or ENZ on lifespan in N2 and DAF-2 strain of the model organism *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*). Based on our previous findings demonstrating the in vitro efficacy of the drug combination in GBM cells, the liquid culture of the synchronized L4 larvae of the N2 and DAF-2 strain was treated with OSI (2.5 and 5 μ M) and/or ENZ (30 and 50 μ M). The potential acute toxic effect of OSI and/or ENZ and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation were examined using DCFH-DA staining. Following the optimization experiments conducted to determine the optimal concentration of 5-Fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (FUDR) treatment, a final concentration of 0.08 mM was determined to be the appropriate dose. The effect of the OSI and/or ENZ on acute toxicity and lifespan was analyzed. While no toxic effects were observed for OSI, statistically significant toxicity was observed for N2 on day 7 and for DAF-2 on day 6 in ENZ and combinations. These findings suggest that OSI and/or ENZ treatment may be evaluated as potential therapeutic candidates against GBM. The results obtained from this study should be supported by using different *C. elegans* strains. Consequently, *C. elegans* is a valuable model for drug toxicity studies due to its genetic and functional similarities to humans. Acknowledgements: This project was supported by TÜBİTAK within the scope of the 2209-A program undergraduate research projects (1919B012405728).

Keyword: *Caenorhabditis elegans, Enzalutamide, Glioblastoma, Lifespan Analysis, Osimertinib*

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OP13

STRUCTURE-BASED VIRTUAL SCREENING FOR NOVEL GLTP INHIBITORS

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Glycolipid Transfer Protein (GLTP) is a small cytosolic α -helical protein responsible for the transfer of glycosphingolipids between membranes. Its dysregulation has been implicated in several cancer, metabolic and neurodegenerative disorders. In this study, we tried to identify potential inhibitors of Glycolipid Transfer Protein (GLTP) through a structure-based virtual screening approach. A ligand library was created from the ZINC20 database using physicochemical and pharmacokinetic filters to ensure drug-like properties. The prepared compounds were docked into the natural ligand binding pocket of GLTP (PDB ID: 3S0K) using Schrödinger's Glide. Post-docking refinement and binding free energy estimation were performed using the Prime/MM-GBSA approach. Binding stabilities of predicted high affinity complexes were further validated through molecular dynamics (MD) simulations conducted with Desmond for 500 ns under physiologically relevant conditions, including TIP3P water model, POPC bilayer membrane, and neutralizing ions. To account for dynamic flexibility, post-MD MM-GBSA rescoring was applied. During the analysis, last 250 ns portion of the simulation was considered and binding free energy (ΔG_{bind}) values were obtained from conformations selected every 10 frames. The results revealed that several ZINC20-derived compounds exhibited stronger predicted binding affinities compared to the co-crystallized natural ligand, a glucosylceramide (beta-D-glucosyl-N-(oleoyl)sphing-4-enine), consistently interacting with key residues such as Asp48, Asn52, Trp96 and His140. These findings suggest that the top candidates could act as potential GLTP inhibitors, which would provide a structural basis for further experimental validation and potential therapeutic development.

Keyword: *Glycolipid Transfer Protein (GLTP), Molecular Docking, MM-GBSA, Molecular Dynamics Simulation, Lipid Transfer Inhibitors*

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OP14

PROTEOMIC PROFILING IDENTIFIES NOVEL NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER (NSCLC) BIOMARKERS

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Background: Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with non–small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) comprising ~85% of cases. Despite advances in therapy, most patients are diagnosed at advanced stages, underscoring the urgent need for early detection and novel biomarkers. Proteomics offers a powerful strategy to identify molecular alterations driving tumor initiation, progression, and metastasis, with potential to inform diagnostics, prognostics, and treatment.

Purpose: This study aimed to profile protein expression patterns across NSCLC subtypes and tissue microenvironments, integrating tissue and serum samples, to identify differentially expressed proteins that could serve as biomarkers or therapeutic targets.

Methods: Samples were obtained from 51 patients (25 adenocarcinoma, 19 squamous cell carcinoma, 7 large cell carcinoma). 204 tissue samples (normal lung, tumor, reactive stroma, metastatic lymph nodes) were analyzed using 4-plex tandem mass tag (TMT)–based proteomics. Serum samples (n=51) were analyzed by label-free quantification following immunodepletion of abundant proteins. Mass spectrometry was performed on a Thermo Q Exactive HF-X platform, and data were processed with Proteome Discoverer 2.4 against the Homo sapiens database.

Results: Tissue proteomics identified thousands of proteins across subtypes, with distinct expression patterns in normal, tumor, stroma, and lymph nodes. In adenocarcinoma, 37 proteins were upregulated and 85 downregulated, while squamous cell carcinoma showed 48 upregulated and 53 downregulated proteins, and large cell carcinoma revealed 50 upregulated and 40 downregulated proteins (fold-change >2, p<0.05). Serum proteomics identified 104, 158, and 88 upregulated proteins for adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and large cell carcinoma.

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Functional enrichment linked these alterations to pathways regulating cell adhesion, immune responses, metabolism, and metastatic progression.

Conclusions: This integrative proteomic profiling highlights subtype- and tissue-specific alterations in NSCLC. The identified candidates represent promising biomarkers for early detection, monitoring, and **therapeutic intervention**, providing a valuable resource for translational lung cancer research.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK (115S113).

Keyword: *Non-small Cell Lung Cancer, NSCLC, Proteomics, Biomarker*

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OP15

PHOTOELECTROCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF PERFLUOROOCTANOIC ACID (PFOA) UTILIZING A NOVEL TiO₂/WO₃ NANOSTRUCTURED PHOTOANODE ENHANCED WITH CARBON QUANTUM DOTS (CQDS)

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Background/Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are persistent environmental pollutants that pose significant health risks. Among the various PFAS, Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) is recognized as the most frequently detected compound in environmental samples. Traditional methods for PFOA removal are often ineffective, requiring more advanced treatment technologies. Photoelectrocatalysis (PEC) has emerged as a promising approach for degrading PFAS compounds, leveraging the synergistic effects of light and electrical energy.

Purpose

This study aims to investigate the efficiency of titanium nanorods doped with tungsten trioxide (WO₃) and enhanced with carbon quantum dots (CQDs) in the photoelectrocatalytic removal of PFAS from contaminated water.

Methods

Titanium nanorods were synthesized and doped with WO₃ to enhance their photocatalytic properties. CQDs were incorporated via spin coating to improve light absorption and charge separation. The structural and optical properties of the photoanodes were characterized. The performance of the nanocomposite photoanode was evaluated under various conditions. The degradation efficiency was monitored using liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS-MS).

Results

The findings indicated that the innovative TNR-WO₃-CQD composite photoanode significantly enhanced the degradation of PFOA compared to both pure TNR and TNR-WO₃ alone. TNR and TNR-WO₃-CQD photoanode achieved a removal efficiencies of 45%, and 80.7% respectively. Remarkably, the TNR-WO₃-CQD photoanode attained over 90% degradation within a three-hour treatment period. Optimal conditions for PFOA removal were also identified. Mechanistic studies revealed enhanced charge carrier dynamics and increased reactive oxygen species generation in the presence of CQDs.

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Conclusion

The study highlights the potential of titanium nanorods doped with WO₃ and enhanced with CQDs as an effective photoelectrocatalytic material for PFOA removal. This approach offers a viable solution for addressing PFAS contamination in water, pioneering for future research and application in environmental remediation technologies.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our gratitude to the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TUBİTAK) for their financial support, provided under project number 121C069.

Keyword: *PFAS, Carbon Quantum Dots, PFOA, Photoelectrocatalysis, Nanostructures*

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OP16

OPTIMIZATION OF MEDIUM CHAIN FATTY ACID (MCFA) PRODUCTION VIA CO-CULTURE MICROBIAL FERMENTATION USING PLACKETT–BURMAN DESIGN

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Background/Introduction: Medium Chain Fatty Acid (MCFAs) are a high-value intermediate used in biofuels, flavors, perfumes, and plasticizers. Sequential systems that combine syngas fermentation and chain elongation reactions are commonly used for MCFA production. However, co-culture fermentations would be a cost-reducing alternative to sequential reactor systems.

Purpose: The primary objective of this study was to optimize the medium composition to produce MCFAs in a co-culture medium of *Clostridium ragsdalei* (for syngas fermentation) and *Clostridium kluveri* (for chain elongation).

Methods: Plackett–Burman experimental design methodology was used for 11 factors and modeled using Design Expert 7.0 software. The factors used in the model are; NH₄Cl, K₂HPO₄, KH₂PO₄, NaOH, NaCl, potassium acetate (K-acetate), MgSO₄·7H₂O, yeast extract, and ethanol which are the most costly chemicals in the fermentation medium composition. The suggested medium compositions were prepared in small scale bioreactors and inoculated with *Clostridium ragsdalei* and *Clostridium kluveri*. Microbial growth dynamics were regularly monitored, and metabolite production was evaluated via HPLC analysis.

Results: The analysis conducted using Design Expert software demonstrated that the model was significant, with a high R² (0.997) value. Certain medium components showed a statistically significant and positive effect on MCFA production. The study identified key parameters that directly influence production efficiency.

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Figure 1. PARETO chart for effects of medium components

Conclusion: This study effectively demonstrates a promising, cost-effective method for producing MCFAs by combining syngas fermentation and chain elongation in a co-culture system. The use of a Plackett–Burman experimental design showed precise optimization of key components, providing valuable insights to significantly enhance production. The high R^2 value of the model strongly validates the findings, confirming that this approach is a viable and efficient alternative to traditional sequential reactor systems.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge the support of TÜBİTAK-TEYDEB- “1507 KOBİ Ar-Ge Başlangıç Destek Programı” Project number: 72498017. Ege Teknopark and D-Tech Factory.

Keyword: *Syngas fermentation, Chain Elongation, Medium Chain Fatty Acid, Experimental Design, Plackett Burman Design*

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OP17

FROM HUMAN PERCEPTION TO COMPUTER VISION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON TITRATION ANALYSIS

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Titration analyses conducted in laboratory environments are subject to variability due to reliance on human visual perception, which can produce systematic errors on results. These errors arise from inter-individual differences in the density of color-sensitive cone cells within trichromatic vision of individuals, ambient illumination conditions, and the recorder's level of experience. Such variability is well-documented in vision science, where differences in the ratio of long- to medium-wavelength cones, as well as spectral sensitivity polymorphisms, are known to affect chromatic discrimination. In this preliminary investigation, we propose the standardization of titration endpoint detection through computer vision (CV) techniques.

Investigators were categorized by experience level, and their gaze patterns during titration were tracked using a customized version of the WebGazer open-source pupil-tracking toolkit. The findings revealed that technicians with differing experience levels focused on distinct regions of the sample during titration, suggesting experience-dependent perceptual bias. Traditional titration practices therefore lack full reproducibility, particularly when carried out by novices or under inconsistent lighting conditions, which undermines reliability in both educational and analytical laboratory contexts.

In parallel, saliency-based analyses conducted under the computer vision framework—tested across various graphics processing units and central processors—demonstrated consistent focal regions irrespective of hardware variability. Unlike human observers, CV analysis showed hardware-agnostic reproducibility, focusing on identical sample regions across trials. This indicates that computer vision can attenuate the impact of human-related variability derived from experience, environmental lighting, and perceptual differences.

These preliminary results show the potential of computer vision to reduce subjective error in titration endpoint determination. Integrating CV into laboratory titration workflows could enhance accuracy, reproducibility, and robustness across operators. Such standardization may be particularly valuable in educational laboratories, where novice users introduce variability, and in industrial quality-control settings that demand rigorous precision.

Keyword: *Titration analysis, Human visual perception, Computer vision, Eye-tracking, Saliency analysis*

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OP18

THE EFFECT OF GRAPE SEED EXTRACT ON LIPID OXIDATION IN A BEEF- PORK SAUSAGE MODEL SYSTEM

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The effect of various natural antioxidants—grape seed extract (GSE), ascorbic acid (AA), α -tocopherol (TP), a combination of GSE and AA, and a combination of GSE and TP on pH, water activity, color change, lipid oxidation, antioxidant capacity, total bacterial count, protein content and free fatty acids was studied in sausages during the drying process. The model sausage system was prepared according to a traditional Bulgarian recipe for “lukanka”. AA and KNO₃ were used in the recipe as antioxidants and preservatives, respectively. The results obtained with natural antioxidants were compared with the results of samples prepared according to the traditional recipe and with a synthetic antioxidant, butylated hydroxytoluene. The samples with a combination of GSE and AA showed the highest antilipid potential, the lowest malondialdehyde values (0.41 mg/kg MDA), the highest antimicrobial capacity (TBC 78.50×10^3 cfu/g), the lowest color change, and the lowest change in antioxidant activity (17.74%), through the sausage drying process. There was an obviously synergistic effect between GSE and AA, and their antioxidant activity was highly effective. The sample with 0.05% GSE ranked second. The samples with a synthetic antioxidant and a combination of KNO₃ and AA gave similar results, but KNO₃ had a toxic effect. The samples with α -tocopherol had lower results. It was found that grape seed extracts and the combination of GSE and AA were the most effective and could successfully replace synthetic antioxidants, improve the quality of sausages, and provide healthier foods to consumers.

Keyword: *grape seed extract, beef-pork sausage, lipid oxidation*

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OP19

CHITOSAN–ALGINATE BASED EDIBLE COATINGS REINFORCED WITH GREEN-SYNTHESIZED ZNO NANOPARTICLES FOR SHELF-LIFE EXTENSION OF BANANAS

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Food packaging is essential for maintaining the quality and safety of fresh produce by reducing moisture loss, delaying ripening, and preventing microbial contamination. However, conventional plastic-based materials such as polyethylene and polypropylene are non-biodegradable, causing long-term environmental pollution. This has driven the need for sustainable alternatives that combine biodegradability with active functionalities. Biopolymer-based edible coatings have emerged as promising candidates due to their eco-friendly nature and ability to carry functional agents. Incorporating nanotechnology into these coatings further enhances their barrier and antimicrobial properties. Among nanomaterials, zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles stand out for their strong antimicrobial activity, and UV-blocking capability. To ensure environmental sustainability, green synthesis using plant extracts offers an eco-friendly route for producing ZnO nanoparticles without hazardous chemicals.

In this study, ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized using *Helichrysum arenarium* extract as a natural reducing and capping agent, following green chemistry principles. Characterization via X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), UV–Vis spectroscopy, and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) confirmed the formation of hexagonal wurtzite ZnO nanoparticles with sizes ranging from 50–80 nm. Antimicrobial activity was assessed using the disk diffusion method against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as fungi, demonstrating significant inhibition zones at concentrations from 25% to 100%.

For practical application, ZnO nanoparticles were incorporated into chitosan–alginate (CH/AG) coatings at varying concentrations (0.2%, 0.5%, 0.8%, and 1.0%) and applied to fresh bananas. Quality parameters, including weight loss, firmness, and colour stability, were monitored during storage. Results revealed that ZnO-enriched coatings significantly reduced weight loss (up to ~49% reduction compared to uncoated samples), maintained firmness (up to 5× higher retention), and preserved colour stability over 20 days, with 1.0% ZnO providing the best performance. These findings demonstrate the potential of green nanotechnology-based edible coatings as sustainable alternatives to conventional plastic packaging for extending the shelf life of fresh produce.

Keyword: *Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles, Green Synthesis, Biopolymer Coatings, Shelf Life, Sustainable Packaging*

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OP20

NUTRITIONAL AND FUNCTIONAL VALUES OF GRAPE SEED EXTRACTS FOR PRODUCTION OF ANTIOXIDATIVE DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS

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The potential of the seed extracts of the red grapes Pinot Noir and Marselan for application as food additives and antioxidative dietary supplements was determined. The differences between the quality characteristics of the seed extracts of the two grape varieties were examined. The polyphenol composition and antioxidant potential of the two extracts were compared. The extracts were rich in polyphenols, especially flavonoids (52.01 mg QE/g DW) and procyanidins (152.18 mg CE/g DW). The nutritional composition of the extracts was determined - the content of ash, crude protein, crude fat, and total dietary fibers, and the carbohydrate content. The content of macro and microelements in the seed extracts was determined. The inhibitory potential of the two seed extracts on three key enzymes affecting diabetes and obesity - α -amylase, α -glucosidase, and pancreatic lipase was studied. The highest degree of extract inhibition against α -glucosidase was determined ($IC_{50} - 2.53 \pm 0.24 \mu\text{g/mL}$). A real inhibitory assessment of the extracts was made by implementing an in vitro digestion simulation method. It was found that the percentage of inhibition of the enzymes with the digested extract was higher compared to those with the undigested extract in buffer and salt solution. Our study proves that the high content of flavonoids and procyanidins in the two extracts determines their high inhibitory capacity against the three enzymes and their potential managing diabetes and obesity.

Keyword: *Grape seed extract, antioxidant, dietary supplements*

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OP21

BENCHMARKING OF PROTEIN-RICH CROPS GROWN IN TÜRKİYE: FUNCTIONAL, TECHNOLOGICAL AND ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF INNOVATIVE EXTRACTION APPROACHES

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As the demand for sustainable protein alternatives increases, Türkiye's plant-based crops offer promising potential to support a transition toward local, functional, and economically viable protein ingredients. This study presents a comprehensive literature-based benchmarking of selected protein-rich crops cultivated in Türkiye, with a focus on their extraction potential, techno-functional properties, and economic feasibility.

The analysis synthesizes national agricultural data, scientific literature, and technical reports to assess the suitability of crops such as chickpeas, lentils, and sunflower seeds for protein isolate production. Comparative evaluation included key parameters such as protein content, reported extraction yields using conventional and novel methods (e.g., ultrasound-assisted, membrane filtration), functional properties (solubility, emulsification, foaming), and in vitro digestibility values from published studies. Additionally, economic indicators — such as average crop yield per hectare, processing costs, and functional protein output — were benchmarked based on available sectoral and academic sources.

Findings suggest that certain underutilized crops, including pumpkin seeds, show competitive performance in terms of both functional quality and yield, particularly when processed via innovative extraction technologies. Türkiye's diverse agro-ecological zones and crop portfolio represent a strong foundation for developing a sustainable protein production strategy aligned with circular bioeconomy goals.

This benchmark provides a knowledge base to guide national-level decisions in crop selection, processing technology investment, and local protein valorization. The study also sets the groundwork for future research integrating in vitro digestibility studies and environmental assessments through life cycle analysis (LCA).

This study was supported by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 101186662

Keyword: *Protein crops, Functional properties, Digestibility, Sustainable protein production*

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OP22

POTENTIAL HEALTH BENEFITS OF POTATO PROTEIN-DERIVED PEPTIDES

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Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) is the third most important food crop worldwide, with a global production of 375 MT in 2022. Potatoes contain several health-promoting compounds including resistant starch, phenolics, biguanides, fibre, insulin-like agents and protein & peptides. Despite the relatively low protein content of potatoes (1.8% protein/fresh weight) in comparison with carbohydrates, the protein quality of potatoes is remarkably high. In addition, increasing evidence highlights the potential health benefits of potato protein-derived peptides, which have been associated with antioxidant, antihypertensive, antidiabetic, and anti-inflammatory activities. These health effects have been evaluated using in vitro assays, cell cultures and animal models.

Overall, the findings highlight the diverse therapeutic potential of potato protein-derived peptides in promoting overall health and underscore significant potential for the development of innovative functional foods.

This study was supported by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 101158968 and the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK) under Grant Number 222O375.

Keyword: *Plant protein, potato protein-derived peptides, antioxidant, antihypertensive, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory*

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OP23

SILENT BIOCONVERSION FORCE OF NATURE

Fatih Yılmaz, Furkan Yeneroğlu*, Semanur Erdoğan, Simge Yıldız
Innofeed Biotechnology

Founded in 2023, Innofeed Biotechnology carries out R&D activities to develop innovative and sustainable protein sources for human and animal nutrition by harnessing the extraordinary potential of insects. Within the framework of sustainability principles and the circular biotechnology approach, Innofeed Biotechnology aims to obtain high value-added protein through upcycle (advanced transformation) of agricultural industry by-products and food industry residues. Insect-based high-quality proteins, which serve as an alternative to conventional feed components such as fishmeal, comply with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) on a global scale due to their low carbon footprint and environmentally friendly features, and support the zero waste approach.

For the first time in Türkiye, the rearing of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae with food residues was achieved, and protein-rich products obtained from this process were developed as high-quality feed additives for pets and aquaculture. By optimizing incubation–larva rearing systems and developing advanced processing methods, protein yield and quality were enhanced. Thus, the upcycling of food residues into functional protein supplements contributed to reducing environmental impact and to the development of innovative biotechnological solutions providing competitive advantage.

The findings demonstrate that insect-based high-quality proteins can be used as sustainable nutritional additives and that agricultural by-products and food residues can be transformed into valuable products through biotechnological upcycle processes. In this way, both biotechnological knowledge and competence have been increased, and solution-oriented contributions have been provided to critical issues such as resource scarcity, environmental footprint, and sustainability in food systems. The project presents a scalable circular model in the field of biotechnology, supporting the transition to environmentally friendly and zero waste-oriented protein production systems.

Keyword: *Insect Protein, Sustainability, Upcycle, High-Quality Feed Additives, Zero Waste*

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Abstracts for Poster Presentations

PP1-Red Biotechnology

INVESTIGATING THE ANTIFUNGAL EFFECTS OF LACTOBACILLUS HELSINGBORGENSIS ISOLATED FROM THE GUT MICROBIOTA OF APIS MELLIFERA ON NOSEMA CERANAE

FARUK BARBAROS KALYONCU

PP2-Red Biotechnology

INVESTIGATION OF THE ANTICANCER ACTIVITY OF HYPERTHERMIA AND/OR SORAFENIB TREATMENT IN HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA CELLS

MUHAMMET DOLU

PP3-Red Biotechnology

ALLOGENEIC CHIMERIC ANTIGEN RECEPTOR-T CELL THERAPY TARGETED CD19 WITH CRISPR-CAS9 FOR ACUTE LYMPHOBLASTIC LEUKAEMIA AND NON-HODGKIN LYMPHOMA

ZEYNEP TASCI

PP4-Red Biotechnology

TRANSCRIPTOMICS-BASED VALIDATION OF RESVERATROL IN AN RA-DIFFERENTIATED SH-SY5Y MODEL OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE

SÜMEYYE ONAT

PP5-Red Biotechnology

COMPARATIVE PROTEOMIC ANALYSIS OF CELL MODEL FOR HUNTINGTON'S DISEASE

ÇINLA ÖZLEVENT

PP6-Red Biotechnology

ANTICANCER POTENTIAL OF EXTRA VIRGIN OLIVE OIL EXTRACTS AGAINST HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA CELLS

ÜLKÜ İREM BEYAZ

PP7-Red Biotechnology

DISSECTING TUMOR IMMUNE MICROENVIRONMENT IN HOSPITALIZED LUNG CANCER PATIENTS

ABDULLAH KARADAĞ

PP8-Red Biotechnology

REASSESSING THE ROLE OF ANTIGEN PROCESSING MACHINERY IN NEXT-GENERATION PRECISION MEDICINE

IKA NURLAILA

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PP9-Red Biotechnology

INDUCTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CAFs IN HUMAN FIBROBLASTS VIA TGF-
B SIGNALING

BEYZA YILMAZ

PP10-Red Biotechnology

INTEGRATED CELL MODELS FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASES AND
SENESCENCE

SELEN ÖZGE ALMAMIS

PP11-Red Biotechnology

INVESTIGATION OF THE MOLECULAR EFFECTS OF STEVIA ON COLON CANCER
CELLS

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PP12-Red Biotechnology

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PP1

INVESTIGATING THE ANTIFUNGAL EFFECTS OF LACTOBACILLUS HELISINGBORGENSIS ISOLATED FROM THE GUT MICROBIOTA OF APIS MELLIFERA ON NOSEMA CERANAE

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Honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) are crucial pollinators for agriculture and biodiversity, yet colony losses are increasingly associated with *Nosema ceranae*, an obligate intracellular parasite that disrupts gut physiology, shortens lifespan, and reduces honey yields. Chemical antifungals such as **Fumagillin-B** which is the only effective agent against *Nosema* sp. have been banned due to toxicity and residue concerns in honey, highlighting the need for safe and sustainable alternatives.

In this study, we investigated the probiotic potential of a novel **Lactobacillus helsingborgensis_GTU1** (LAB_GTU1) strain, isolated from the gut microbiota of healthy honeybees, against *N. ceranae*. The strain was characterized by biochemical assays and **16S rDNA** sequencing, and in vivo feeding experiments were conducted using different bacterial concentrations (0.3–0.7 McFarland) formulated in **50% sucrose** solution. Preliminary results revealed that GTU1 supplementation at 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 McFarland concentrations of isolate improved median survival compared to controls, with the 0.3 McFarland group showing the strongest effect, increasing median survival. In the other hand, higher concentrations (0.6 and 0.7 McFarland) displayed toxicity, reducing survival rates relative to healthy controls. These findings suggest that optimal dosage of LAB_GTU1 can enhance honeybee viability under infection stress, whereas excessive dosages may show adverse effects. Ongoing experiments are anticipating the strain's ability to reduce *N. ceranae* **spore loads**, improve **gut histology**, and modulate **immune-related gene expression**.

This study provides the first in vivo evidence of LAB_GTU1's potential as a probiotic for honeybee health, offering an eco-friendly strategy for managing *N. ceranae* infections, final product which produce with biotechnological approach and contributing to sustainable apiculture.

Keyword: *Honeybee, Lactobacillus, Nosema ceranae, Probiotic, Prebiotic*

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PP2

INVESTIGATION OF THE ANTICANCER ACTIVITY OF HYPERTHERMIA AND/OR SORAFENIB TREATMENT IN HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA CELLS

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Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a major cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. The current systemic therapies are limited due to the drug resistance, usually mediated by the ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters. Sorafenib, a first-line tyrosine kinase inhibitor for advanced HCC, frequently exhibits reduced therapeutic efficacy due to increased extracellular drug transport via ABC transporters. The present study investigates the anti-cancer efficacy of combining hyperthermia and/or sorafenib treatment in HepG2 cells. The optimal condition for hyperthermia was selected as 1h at 43°C. The effect of hyperthermia and/or sorafenib on cell viability and colony formation was determined using the MTT and colony formation assays. DNA fragmentation, mitochondrial membrane potential, and cell death were investigated using DAPI, DioC₆, and PI staining. The expression levels of the ABC transporter proteins were investigated by immunoblotting. Cell migration was analyzed by a wound-healing assay. The IC₅₀ value of sorafenib cells was determined to be 12.38 µM after 48 h. This value decreased to 8.662 µM with the combined treatment. The hyperthermia resulted in a statistically significant decrease in cell viability at decreasing concentrations of sorafenib. Colony formation assay confirmed that combination therapy further reduced clonogenic potential compared to sorafenib alone. Significant results were observed in both the wound healing and fluorescence analyses. Sorafenib alone induced the expressions of ABCB1 and ABCC2. In contrast, hyperthermia, alone or in combination with sorafenib, resulted in a further reduction in the expression levels of ABCB1 and ABCC2 (*p<0.05). It can be hypothesized that hyperthermia may enhance intracellular sorafenib accumulation by inhibiting efflux transporters and increasing drug uptake, thereby sensitizing cancer cells to chemotherapy and offering an effective strategy against advanced HCC. Acknowledgments: This project received support from TÜBİTAK (2209-A, 1919B012403044) and Marmara University via ADEP (ADT-2023-10837).

Keyword: ABCB1, ABC transporters, Hepatocellular carcinoma, Hyperthermia, Sorafenib

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PP3

ALLOGENEIC CHIMERIC ANTIGEN RECEPTOR-T CELL THERAPY TARGETED CD19 WITH CRISPR-CAS9 FOR ACUTE LYMPHOBLASTIC LEUKAEMIA AND NON-HODGKIN LYMPHOMA

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Introduction/Background: Chimeric antigen receptors (CARs) are engineered on T cells with an scFv for antigen recognition, a transmembrane domain, and intracellular signaling domains. Autologous CAR-T therapy is safer than chemo- or radiotherapy but requires patient T cells and long manufacturing. Allogeneic CAR-T cells from healthy donors can be stored and used as needed. CD19 is highly expressed in ALL and NHL, making it an ideal target.

Purpose: This study aims to develop a third-generation allogeneic CAR-T system targeting CD19 for universal use in ALL and NHL. To prevent graft-versus-host disease (GVHD) or host-versus-graft disease (HVGD), we target the first exon of the endogenous T-cell receptor alpha (TRAC) locus using CRISPR-Cas9, ensuring only the engineered CAR is expressed on T-cell surfaces.

Methods: The CAR construct, containing a CD8 α signal peptide, FMC63 scFv, Whitlow peptide, CD8 α hinge, CD29 transmembrane domain, CD28, 4-1BB, CD3 ζ intracellular domains, and homology arms, was cloned into pGenLenti vector. gRNAs were designed in silico and cloned into PX459 under a U6 promoter. CAR plasmids were packaged into lentiviral particles, stored at -80°C, and used to transduce JURKAT cells alongside CRISPR/Cas9 plasmids. Edited cells will be characterized by NGS, FACS, and cytotoxicity assays against CD19⁺ NALM-6 cells.

Results: The third-generation CAR construct with homology arms has been successfully cloned, and lentiviral particles have been produced. Cloning and vector integrity were confirmed via agarose gel electrophoresis. We are currently developing gRNA and Cas9 plasmids. Subsequent studies will include CRISPR-mediated TRAC editing, CAR surface expression analysis, and cytotoxicity assays against target B-cell lines to validate functionality.

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Conclusion: We aim to establish a safe and effective allogeneic CAR-T therapy targeting CD19 for ALL and NHL. Following in vitro validation, clinical studies are planned to advance this therapy as an alternative to conventional cancer treatments.

Keyword: *Allogeneic CAR-T, CD19, CRISPR/Cas9, Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia, Non-Hodgkin lymphoma*

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PP4

TRANSCRIPTOMICS-BASED VALIDATION OF RESVERATROL IN AN RA-DIFFERENTIATED SH-SY5Y MODEL OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE

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Introduction: Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by dopaminergic neuron loss, oxidative stress, and mitochondrial dysfunction. The World Health Organization projects that neurodegenerative diseases, including PD, will become the second leading cause of death worldwide by 2040. Reliable in vitro PD models are crucial for mechanistic studies and preclinical drug evaluation. Guided by integrated transcriptomic analyses of SH-SY5Y and LUHMES cells treated with 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) and 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium (MPP⁺), resveratrol was identified as a candidate therapeutic modulator.

Purpose: This study aims to investigate the potential of resveratrol in mitigating neurotoxic insult-induced neurotoxicity using a retinoic acid (RA)-differentiated SH-SY5Y model of PD.

Methods: Transcriptomic datasets (GSE196190, GSE229460, GSE203522, GSE198009) from SH-SY5Y and LUHMES cells exposed to 6-OHDA and MPP⁺ were analyzed in R to identify differentially expressed genes and drug-target interactions. Candidate molecules were mapped using DrugBank. For experimental validation, RA-differentiated SH-SY5Y cells (10 µM RA) were treated with MPP⁺ (1 mM, 24 h) or 6-OHDA (100 µM, 12 h), and viability was assessed following resveratrol application.

Results: Phase-contrast imaging confirmed successful neuronal differentiation of SH-SY5Y cells following RA exposure, as evidenced by neurite formation. Both MPP⁺ and 6-OHDA treatments significantly reduced cell viability within 12-24 hours compared to controls. Transcriptomic mapping and drug-target analysis highlighted resveratrol as a promising candidate capable of enhancing cell survival under neurotoxic stress.

Conclusion: Integrated transcriptomic analyses identified resveratrol as a potential therapeutic modulator in PD. Preliminary in vitro findings support its protective effect against toxin-induced neurotoxicity, providing a strong basis for further pathway validation and exploration of advanced delivery systems, including resveratrol-loaded exosomes.

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Keyword: *Transcriptomic analysis, Parkinsons disease, neuroprotection, resveratrol*

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PP5

COMPARATIVE PROTEOMIC ANALYSIS OF CELL MODEL FOR HUNTINGTON'S DISEASE

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Background: Huntington's disease (HD) is a neurodegenerative disorder caused by expanded glutamine (CAG) repeats in the HTT gene, leading to toxic protein aggregates. To investigate proteomic alterations associated with HD, we compared healthy cells carrying 23 glutamine repeats (23Q) with disease model cells carrying 74 repeats (74Q).

Purpose: This study aimed to identify proteins that are differentially expressed in disease state by comparing healthy (23Q) and diseased (74Q) cells to unravel the molecular changes and related pathways involved in Huntington's disease.

Method: Proteomic analyses were carried out for 23Q and 74Q cell samples employing ThermoFisher Orbitrap Q Exactive coupled to Dionex Ultimate 3000 RSLCnano system. Raw data were processed with MaxQuant and subsequently analyzed in R. Data preprocessing included log₂ transformation, normalization with median or quantile, and missing value imputation using a minimum value approach. Differential expression analysis was performed using both limma and DEqMS packages with normalization methods, resulting in four complementary analytical workflows.

Result: Differential expression analysis revealed consistent patterns across all workflows. Using median normalization with either limma or DEqMS, seven proteins were discovered to be significantly up-regulated and thirteen of them were determined to be down-regulated in disease model cells. Quantile normalization combined with limma / DEqMS demonstrated eight overpressed candidates while reporting fifteen repressed proteins. The altered proteins were mainly associated with cellular processes such as protein folding and stress response, RNA processing and splicing, transcriptional regulation, proteasome-mediated degradation, cytoskeletal organization, nuclear transport, and immune-related pathways.

Conclusion: This study identified reproducible proteomic alterations in Huntington's disease model cells (74Q vs 23Q). These findings provide insight into the molecular mechanisms underlying Huntington's disease and highlight proteins that may serve as potential markers of disease-related cellular changes.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK (2247-C), Kocaeli University and Gebze Technical University (BAP3890, YÖK-ADEP 2024-A-113-10) for the support.

Keyword: Huntington's Disease, HTT, Proteomics, Mass spectrometry

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PP6

ANTICANCER POTENTIAL OF EXTRA VIRGIN OLIVE OIL EXTRACTS AGAINST HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA CELLS

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Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a type of liver cancer that poses a significant global health burden as the third leading cause of cancer-related deaths. Recent studies have highlighted the potential anticancer properties of olive oil polyphenols against HCC cells. Extra virgin olive oil contains bioactive phenolic compounds, including oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol, and tyrosol, which exhibit significant antiproliferative, proapoptotic, and anti-inflammatory effects. In this study, methanol extracts from six different extra virgin olive oil cultivars (Gemlik, Beylik, Tavşan Yüreği, Memecik, Hanım Parmağı, and Ayvalık) from Turkey were evaluated for their anticancer activity against HepG2 cells. Total phenolic content was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method, revealing significant differences among cultivars. Hanım Parmağı showed the highest total phenolic concentration with 533.8 µg/mL. The MTT method determined IC₅₀ values ranging from 33.9 ± 7.2 µg/mL for the Ayvalık variety to 47.7 ± 4.0 µg/mL for the Gemlik variety. In particular, the Ayvalık, Memecik, and Tavşan Yüreği varieties exhibited the strongest antiproliferative activity, demonstrating the potential of Turkish olive oil varieties as sources of natural bioactive compounds with therapeutic applications against hepatocellular carcinoma.

Keyword: *hepatocellular carcinoma, extra virgin olive oil, polyphenols*

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PP7

DISSECTING TUMOR IMMUNE MICROENVIRONMENT IN HOSPITALIZED LUNG CANCER PATIENTS

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Backgrounds: Lung cancer remains a leading cause of cancer mortality worldwide, with the tumor immune microenvironment and immune evasion mechanisms playing important roles in disease progression and patient outcomes. Understanding the immune landscape in lung cancer is critical for identifying prognostic biomarkers and potential immunotherapy targets.

Purpose: This study aims to identify and characterize immune cell populations and immune checkpoint protein expression in lung cancer, and to assess their association with disease progression, prognosis, and potential as biomarkers for personalized immuno-oncology therapies.

Methods: Advanced techniques including flow cytometry, PCR and multiplexed immunohistochemistry on tissue microarrays were employed to analyze peripheral blood, tumor tissues, and immune microenvironment cells from cancer patients. Quantitative analyses of immune cell phenotypes and B7-Molecule's expression were statistically correlated with clinical parameters such as tumor stage, grade, lymph node involvement, recurrence, and survival.

Results: To assess the plasticity and phenotypes of immune cells within the Lung Tumor Immune microenvironment at single-cell level, we identified distinct immune cell populations and B7-molecule's expression ratios within different lung cancer stages. First, we recognized that the Treg population in the peripheral blood was significantly increased in cancer patients compared to pre cancer patients and healthy donors. Quantitative multiplexed immunohistochemistry revealed that an increase in the number of tumors infiltrating Tregs and B7-molecule's expression are associated with unfavorable classical risk parameters of advanced disease stage and stromal invasion. Further validation of this finding in lung cancer across the global population is currently underway.

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Conclusions: Elevated frequencies of Tregs, and B7-molecule's overexpression serve as potential biomarkers indicating aggressive tumor phenotypes. However, further validation precisely in lung cancer need to be done internationally. These immune-related markers can be used for stratifying cancer patients and guiding personalized immuno-oncology therapeutic approaches across different malignancies.

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Keyword: *Lung cancer Markers, Tumor Immune Microenvironment, Cancer Patients, B7-molecule's*

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PP8

REASSESSING THE ROLE OF ANTIGEN PROCESSING MACHINERY IN NEXT- GENERATION PRECISION MEDICINE

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Introduction: The antigen processing machinery (APM) plays a pivotal role in processing tumor-derived antigens. A significant limitation of this notion is that researchers have conducted only partial analyses of APM leading to difficulties in establishing generalizable conclusions. Hitherto, the function of APM has been largely compartmentalized into tumor immunogenicity, immune evasion, and more recently, anticancer drug resistance. Nevertheless, the actual functions of APM extend beyond the conventional paradigm. Understanding the interactions between APM and elements within the tumor microenvironment (TME) could reveal opportunities for utilizing APM variability as predictive biomarkers or therapeutic targets, particularly for those who have developed resistance to mainstream therapies including immunotherapy itself.

Purpose: We aim at elucidating the function of APM in influencing tumor-immune interactions beyond the traditional mechanisms of antigen presentation.

Methods: Considering the somewhat restricted array of recognized anticancer treatments that specifically target APM, in light of its significant role, we systematically compiled and scrutinized transcriptomic metadata sourced from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) repository (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>) and relevant registries by employing the search terms “antigen processing+machinery+carcinoma+cancer.” We utilized RStudio (with the metapackage) for the analysis of metadata and subsequently visualized the results using Galaxy.

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Results: Our search resulted in 12 inclusive metadata which included carcinoma in the breast, brain, melanoma and the blood. Our findings indicate that APM dynamics are evident at the transcriptomic level, intersecting with more prevalent pathways in tumorigenesis, such as mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), thus suggesting that APM may be further investigated and manipulated to reactivate immune cells that have been reprogrammed within TME.

Conclusion: Reevaluation of APM presents opportunities for the discovery of innovative strategies that may transcend existing limitations and significantly impact the future of cancer immunotherapy.

Acknowledgement: This publication was created by benefiting from the 2236-B Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Cofund Scholarship Programs Contribution Fund Program (TUBITAK project ID: 123C460) and Horizon Europe MSCA Cofund Postdoctoral Program (EU project ID: 101126492). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or TUBITAK. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Keyword: *antigen processing machinery, immune evasion, immunogenicity, next generation medicine, precision medicine*

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PP9

INDUCTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CAFs IN HUMAN FIBROBLASTS VIA TGF- β SIGNALING

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Cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs) are key components of the tumor microenvironment that promote cancer progression. They contribute to the remodeling of the extracellular matrix, enhance tumor spread, and suppress immune function. The transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β) signaling pathway plays a key role in the conversion of normal fibroblasts into CAFs. TGF- β is a multifunctional cytokine that plays a critical role in cancer cell progression; this pathway promotes cell proliferation and the secretion of tumor-supporting molecules. This study aims to systematically optimize the protocol for differentiating Human Dermal Fibroblasts (HDFs) into CAFs via TGF- β . The study examined the change in CAF markers expression at the protein level in HDF cells stimulated with TGF- β . Our results showed that the expression levels of CAF markers, particularly alpha-smooth muscle actin (α -SMA) and vimentin, were increased in the treated groups compared to the control group. Additionally, the levels of SMAD2/3, the primary effectors of the TGF- β signaling pathway, were also increased. Furthermore, the increase in SMAD2/3 levels, which are key transduction molecules in the TGF- β signaling cascade, confirmed the activation of the canonical SMAD pathway. This study demonstrated an optimized TGF- β -based strategy for generating CAF-like cells from HDFs. The results provide a useful *in vitro* model for understanding the biological mechanisms of CAFs. This optimized model will be used in future studies to investigate the roles of CAFs in tumor progression. In co-culture systems with cancer cells, we aim to examine the functional effects of these cells on tumor progression. In this regard, modeling CAFs has the potential to form a valuable basis for developing and testing new treatment strategies for cancer.

Keyword: *Cancer associated fibroblasts, tumor microenvironment, TGF- β signaling pathway, in vitro model*

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PP10

INTEGRATED CELL MODELS FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASES AND SENESCENCE

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Background: Neurodegenerative diseases, particularly Parkinson's disease (PD), amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), and Huntington's disease (HD), are characterized by progressive neuronal loss, protein aggregation, and impaired cellular homeostasis, ultimately leading to motor and cognitive decline. Furthermore, age is the predominant risk factor for neurodegenerative illnesses, as it triggers protein misfolding, mitochondrial dysfunction, and cellular stress mechanisms that contribute to neuronal susceptibility. Cellular models provide a controlled platform to investigate disease mechanisms by engineering human cell lines with disease-relevant genetic changes and treatments.

Aim: This study aimed to establish cell models displaying protein aggregation, mitochondrial stress, and altered cellular integrity. The factor of ageing will be integrated to advance the in vitro models in the presence of cellular senescence.

Method: We established in vitro cell models for PD, ALS, and HD by designated plasmids through the PeiPro system or treated with specific agents (6-OHDA, MPP) at different time periods (24-72h). In addition to these models, senescence will be introduced through the exposure to D-Gal, advancing the relatable disease features with ageing.

Results: The expression levels for the corresponding plasmids were recorded through the GFP signal by using fluorescence microscopy. Immunoblotting assays were performed to confirm the molecular sizes of the expression products with anti-GFP or related antibodies. The cellular effect of the model was determined through viability assays.

Conclusion: This study will be followed by including the D-gal-based senescence to relate ageing with the corresponding cell model and to check protein aggregation and progressive neuronal loss after the exposure.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK (124Z229 and 124Z680) and Gebze Technical University (ADEP 2024-A-113-10 and 2025-A-113-22) for the support.

Keyword: *Neurodegeneration, Parkinson's Disease, ALS, Huntington's Disease, Senescence*

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PP11

INVESTIGATION OF THE MOLECULAR EFFECTS OF STEVIA ON COLON CANCER CELLS

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Background/Introduction

Colorectal cancer was among the most common cancers, affecting 240,000 people in Türkiye and 1.9 million individuals worldwide. Plant-derived bioactive compounds have gained interest for their anticancer potential, with Stevia rebaudiana emerging as a promising source.

Purpose

This study investigated the molecular effects of a defined mixture (SteX) from purified compounds obtained through the fermentation of Stevia rebaudiana on colon cancer cells.

Methods

Stevia extracts were used as carbon sources and inoculated with *Aspergillus niger* A42 strain (ATCC 204447). Fermentation was conducted at 30 °C in a shaking incubator (250 rpm), and products were purified with chromatographic methods. Healthy (HEK293T) and colon carcinoma (HCT116) cells were cultured and treated with 5% (v/v) SteX for 24 h. Cell viability and death were assessed with MTS assay and Annexin V-FITC with flow cytometry. ROS levels and total antioxidant capacity were measured by DCFDA staining and a colorimetric method, respectively. Cells were analyzed using antibodies against apoptotic and OXPHOS proteins by immunoblotting to determine the molecular changes induced by SteX treatment.

Results

SteX showed strong cytotoxicity against HCT116 compared to HEK293T cells. The antioxidant capacity increased 2.5-fold in HEK293T cells, with no significant change observed in HCT116 cells. Late apoptosis and necrosis in HCT116 rose by 60% and 116%, respectively. Alterations were detected in apoptotic markers (Caspase-3/9, cleaved forms, PARP, Bcl-2) and oxidative phosphorylation proteins, revealing reorganization of respiratory chain supercomplexes.

Conclusion(s)

SteX demonstrated anticancer potential against colon carcinoma by oxidative stress elevation, apoptosis induction, and metabolic reprogramming. Future work will involve mitochondrial dynamics to unravel physiological changes in terms of bioenergetics.

Acknowledgements

This study was partially supported by the TUBITAK 1001 project (120M507).

Keyword: *Fermentation, Fructooligosaccharide, Colorectal Cancer, Stevia, ROS*

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PP12

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF PVA–ZNO NANOCOMPOSITE CRYOGELS FOR POTENTIAL WOUND DRESSING APPLICATIONS

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Many people suffer from wounds ranging from small, acute cuts to large, chronic ulcers, creating a significant clinical challenge and socioeconomic burden. There is a growing need for advanced biomaterials that effectively promote wound healing and support tissue regeneration. Hybrid nanocomposites such as polymer incorporating metal oxide nanoparticles, have recently emerged as promising candidates for developing bioactive wound dressings, as they combine the structural benefits of polymers with the bioactive and antimicrobial properties of nanoparticles. This study aims to fabricate a nanocomposite consisting of poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) cryogel matrices embedded with zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles. PVA cryogels were obtained through physical crosslinking via repeated freeze-thaw cycles, thereby avoiding the use of toxic chemical crosslinkers. ZnO nanoparticles, on the other hand, were synthesized through a green, biologically mediated approach. Extracellular secretions of a local thermophilic fungus served as reducing, nucleating and capping agent, ensuring nanoparticle formation under mild conditions while minimizing hazardous chemical use. The prepared cryogels, including undoped and ZnO nanoparticle loaded PVA cryogels were characterized by FTIR spectroscopy, while X-ray diffraction confirmed the formation of ZnO nanoparticles. PVA-ZnO nanocomposites will undergo further characterization through SEM and TGA analyses, and their biomedical performance will be assessed in terms of water sorption and deswelling behavior, mechanical strength, blood compatibility, and antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens. In addition, cytocompatibility with skin-relevant cell lines and preliminary wound-healing assays will provide insights into their therapeutic potential. Overall, integrating green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles into PVA cryogels prepared without chemical crosslinkers provides a highly promising, sustainable approach to bioactive nanocomposite wound dressings that enhance wound healing.

Keyword: *Wound dressing, PVA cryogel, Zinc oxide nanoparticles, Polymer nanocomposite, Wound healing*

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PP13

ENGINEERING POLYELECTROLYTE EDIBLE FILMS FOR TREATMENT OF LACTOSE INTOLERANCE

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INTRODUCTION

Lactose intolerance has emerged as a widespread global health concern, adversely affecting the digestive system in relation to both the consumption and daily intake levels of milk and dairy products. This disease substantially diminishes quality of life, manifesting as gastrointestinal disturbances including abdominal pain, bloating, flatulence, and diarrhea. It arises from an insufficient or absent production of lactase, the intestinal enzyme responsible for lactose hydrolysis.

PURPOSE

This experimental work aims to mitigate lactose intolerance-associated complications by replicating the physiological digestion process observed in individuals with normal lactase activity.

METHODS

This research introduces a novel formulation in which lactase is delivered through an edible coating incorporated directly with the product. Specifically, the enzyme is encapsulated within liposomes and subsequently applied to small, spherical cheese portions (~2 cm diameter). The coated surface is then engineered via layer-by-layer (LbL) electrostatic self-assembly of polyelectrolyte biopolymers using a layer-by-layer coating method.

RESULTS

We have successfully formed polyelectrolytic edible films on spherical cheese surface. FTIR analysis confirmed the development of layer-by-layer polyelectrolytic films on cheese surface nicely, while SEM imaging revealed two distinct layers characteristic of the layered polysaccharide layers achieved.

CONCLUSIONS

Polyelectrolyte edible film formation and cheese coating were successfully established, with forthcoming evaluations encompassing shelf-life stability, sensory profiling, and in-vitro digestion performance.

Keyword: *Lactose intolerance, Edible coating, Encapsulation*

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PP14

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF SUSTAINABLY SYNTHESIZED BORON-DOPED ZNO NANOPARTICLES AS PROMISING ADDITIVES FOR WOUND DRESSINGS

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the greatest health challenges worldwide (Prestinaci et al., 2015), pointing to the urgent need for novel antimicrobial agents. Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) are promising because they are biocompatible and generally recognized as safe (GRAS) by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). In this study, boron-doped ZnO nanoparticles (B-ZnO) were sustainably synthesized using the extracellular matrix of *Aspergillus niger* (*A.niger*) as a natural reducing and stabilizing agent. Undoped, 5% and 10% (w/w) boron-doped ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized and their structural, morphological, and optical properties were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy. XRD confirmed the hexagonal wurtzite ZnO structure in all samples. SEM images revealed distinct morphological differences between undoped and boron-doped ZnO nanoparticles. With 5% boron doping, the particles became more uniform, spherical, and smaller, while still tending to agglomerate. UV-Vis-NIR spectra showed strong UV absorption, shifting from 360 nm (undoped) to 356 nm (5% boron-doped) and 350 nm (10% boron-doped), indicating blue shift. Consistently, the band gap energies increased with boron doping as 3.11, 3.16, and 3.18 eV, respectively.

In antimicrobial activity tests, samples were exposed to UV light for 15 minutes. ZnO NPs demonstrated notable efficacy against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida parapsilosis*, as indicated by low MIC and MBC/MFC values. Boron doping significantly enhanced antimicrobial activity of ZnO NPs, reducing MIC values by up to 100-fold against Gram-positive (*S. aureus*, *E. faecalis*), Gram-negative (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*), and fungal (*A. niger*) strains, while undoped ZnO showed limited efficacy. 5% B-ZnO exhibited the most consistent broad-spectrum activity. Overall, sustainably synthesized boron-doped ZnO nanoparticles are promising candidates for advanced biomedical applications, particularly in wound healing and antimicrobial coatings.

Acknowledgement: This study is supported by TÜBİTAK 2210-C Yurt İçi Öncelikli Alanlar Yüksek Lisans Burs Programı.

Keyword: *Boron-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles, Antimicrobial resistance, Sustainability, Antimicrobial activity, Aspergillus niger*

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PP15

MODELING A-SYNUCLEIN AGGREGATION AND NEURODEGENERATION FOR PARKINSON'S DISEASE

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Background: Neurodegenerative disorders are characterized by progressive neuronal dysfunction and cell loss. Parkinson's disease (PD) is one of the most prevalent of these disorders, with its pathology closely associated with the misfolding and aggregation of α -synuclein. Despite the extensive studies, the molecular mechanism of α -synuclein aggregation in neurodegeneration remains incompletely understood. Thus, there is a critical need for reliable *in vitro* disease models to examine PD-associated neuropathology.

Purpose: This study aimed to develop and evaluate an *in vitro* model of PD using NSC-34 motor neuron-like cells by transfecting with α -synuclein and administering pre-fibrillar α -synuclein.

Methods: Initially, NSC-34 cells were transfected with wild-type (WT) α -synuclein and mutant (mut) α -synuclein-A53T plasmids. Cell viability was assessed qualitatively by Hoechst/PI staining up to 168 hours (h), by fluorescence microscopy imaging. Transfection with pEGFP was included as a control for transfection efficiency. Next, pre-fibrillar α -synuclein application will be followed by Western blotting to characterize α -synuclein expression, while XTT assays will provide quantitative measurement of cell viability.

Results: Hoechst/PI staining showed that NSC-34 cells transfected with α -synuclein remained viable for up to 168h post-transfection. However, the proportion of non-viable cells increased over time. In comparison of WT and mut groups, Hoechst/PI staining revealed that NSC-34 cells transfected with WT α -synuclein remained viable for up to 168h post-transfection, with only a moderate increase in PI-positive cells. Whereas mut α -synuclein-A53T-transfected cells displayed a distinct profile.

Conclusions: This study presents a preliminary framework for modeling the neuropathology of α -synuclein *in vitro*. Future research will generate a pre-fibrillar α -synuclein-applied model to assess the reproducibility and relevance of the PD model. Characterization and comparison of these models may enable a more precise evaluation of α -synuclein aggregation and associated neurotoxicity, while advancing the understanding of the mechanisms underlying PD pathophysiology.

Acknowledgements: We gratefully acknowledge funding from TÜBİTAK through projects 124Z680 and 124Z229.

Keywords: NSC-34, neurodegeneration, Parkinson's disease, α -synuclein

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PP16

ELECTROSPINNING BASIL-INSPIRED NANOMATERIALS FOR MANUFACTURING NEXT-GENERATION MEDICAL BANDAGES

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Chronic wounds, characterized by prolonged healing processes and a high risk of infection, remain a significant challenge in modern healthcare systems. Conventional wound dressings often exhibit limited effectiveness, may induce toxic side effects, and raise environmental concerns. In this study, an eco-friendly, biocompatible, and multifunctional smart wound dressing was developed by combining zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles synthesized via green methods with basil extracts and incorporating them into electrospun nanofiber structures. Extracts of the *Ocimum basilicum* (basil) plant were used in experimental studies for the bioreduction of ZnO nanoparticles. Furthermore, an extract of red fruit containing anthocyanin was integrated into nanofibers as a natural pH indicator that allows visual and non-invasive monitoring of wound healing, while waste fruit peel ash (calcined at 650°C for 2 hours) was used as a sustainable additive to accelerate wound healing.

According to the comprehensive characterization analyses performed, X-ray diffraction results revealed the formation of crystalline ZnO with a hexagonal wurtzite structure, while scanning electron microscopy images revealed that the nanofibers exhibited homogeneous distribution, high porosity, and nanometer-scale diameters. Furthermore, the synthesized basil-doped ZnO nanoparticles were determined to have an average diameter of 20 nanometers and a rod-like shape. Energy-dispersive X-ray analysis further confirmed the elemental composition by detecting Zn, O, and plant-derived elements doped into the nanofibers. Furthermore, MTT cytotoxicity analyses and scratch assay analyses were performed on ZnO-doped, ash-doped, and undoped nanofibers to compare their biological behavior using human fibroblast cells.

In conclusion, the findings demonstrate that green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles integrated into electrospun nanofibers exhibit high crystallinity, biocompatibility, and functional properties. The incorporation of natural pH indicators and sustainable biowaste-derived additives highlights the potential of the developed smart wound dressing for non-invasive monitoring, infection control, and environmentally conscious biomedical applications. This work was carried out with the support of TUBITAK 2209-A.

Keyword: *Smart wound dressing, green synthesis, pH indicator, sustainable materials*

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PP17

UNDERSTANDING TCAB1 MUTATIONS IN TELOMERASE FOR SUSTAINABLE HEALTH: INSIGHTS FROM MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS

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Telomeres are repetitive nucleotide sequences that safeguard the ends of linear chromosomes and are maintained by the ribonucleoprotein enzyme telomerase. Proper telomerase function is essential for the faithful transmission of genetic information, yet its activity is tightly regulated in somatic cells. Dysregulation, particularly loss of function, can lead to severe disorders such as Dyskeratosis Congenita (DC), which affects multiple organ systems and significantly reduces quality of life. Until recently, detailed structural insights into telomerase and its accessory proteins were lacking, limiting the ability to investigate disease-causing mutations at the molecular level.

In this study, molecular dynamics simulations were performed on the wild-type and mutant forms of TCAB1, a key protein of the telomerase H/ACA RNP lobe, using the structure with PDB ID 7bgb. Mutants analysed included G435R, R398W, H376Y, F164L, as well as the double variants H376Y/G435R and F164L/R398W. Simulations at physiological temperature and pH revealed that these mutations compromise the structural stability of TCAB1 and, critically, disrupt its interactions with the RNA component of the telomerase complex. The observed weakening of protein–RNA contacts suggests impaired assembly and function of the holoenzyme, thereby providing a mechanistic explanation for reduced telomerase activity in DC patients.

From a sustainability perspective, such molecular-level understanding has important implications. By elucidating how specific mutations interfere with RNA interactions, this work supports the development of precision diagnostics that enable earlier identification of high-risk individuals. Moreover, insights into the structural consequences of TCAB1 mutations facilitate the design of targeted therapies, reducing the need for trial-and-error approaches. These advances contribute to more efficient use of healthcare resources and improved patient outcomes, aligning with long-term goals of sustainable healthcare systems.

Keyword: *Telomerase, TCAB1 Mutations, Protein-RNA binding, Molecular Dynamics, Sustainability in Healthcare*

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PP18

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF N-GLYCOSYLATION IN INFLUENZA A (H3N2) HEMAGGLUTININ BY COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

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BACKGROUND

Influenza A virus (IAV) surveillance is vital for tracking resistance, zoonotic transmission, and vaccine design. Pigs act as “mixing vessels” for human, avian, and swine IAVs, as seen in the 2009 H1N1 pandemic. N-glycosylation shields epitopes and promotes immune escape, with H3 viruses gaining new sites every 5–7 years. ColabFold models with predicted glycosylation near the receptor-binding site and antigenic region A were generated, providing the basis for MD simulations to explore N-glycosylation mechanisms.

PURPOSE

The purpose of this study is to clarify the structures of the A/H3N2 virus strains non- glycosylated and glycosylated hemagglutinin (HA) proteins that were discovered between 2019 and 2024.

METHODS

A total of 2,944 HA protein sequences of A/H3N2 isolates were aligned to identify amino acid variations at antigenic sites. N-glycosylation sites were predicted with NetNGlyc-1.0, and HA structures were modeled in ColabFold.MD simulations in GROMACS 2024 compared glycosylated and non-glycosylated proteins, with RMSD, RMSF, and SASA analyses assessing structural stability and flexibility.

RESULTS

RMSD analyses revealed that glycosylation did not cause significant global conformational changes across all strains. SASA analyses indicated that amino acids located in antigenic regions were more buried upon glycosylation. This observation was consistent with RMSF analyses, where flexibility of amino acids within antigenic sites decreased following glycosylation.

CONCLUSION

N-glycosylation did not alter equilibration of HA structures but reduced fluctuations and solvent exposure at antigenic sites, indicating a localized stabilizing effect. PCA analysis revealed that glycosylation altered HA dynamics in an isolate-specific way; it increased conformational diversity for most isolates and provided stabilization by restricting movements in strain WEU85467.1.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Keyword: *Swine Influenza A Virus, Viral Evolution, Molecular Dynamics Simulations, Glycan modifications, Hemagglutinin*

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PP19

BIOINFORMATICS FOR SIRT1–SNCA RELATIONSHIP IN PARKINSON’S DISEASE

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Background: Parkinson’s disease is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the loss of dopaminergic neurons and the accumulation of α -synuclein, and it is associated with processes such as mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress. SIRT1 is a deacetylase involved in cellular energy metabolism and neuroprotection, and it has been reported to reduce α -synuclein accumulation in Parkinson’s pathology.

Purpose: This study aims to investigate the role of SIRT1 in Parkinson’s disease and its association with α -synuclein, to define the disease-specific molecular signature, and identify potential therapeutic targets.

Method: In this study, RNA-Seq and microarray PD datasets were obtained from GEO, preprocessed with Galaxy, and analyzed in R. SIRT1 and SNCA expression profiles were systematically compared between healthy and disease groups. Differentially expressed genes were identified, followed by Gene Ontology enrichment. Protein–protein interactions were mapped using STRING, hub genes were determined by network topology, and potential therapeutic agents were screened via DGIdb.

Results: Transcriptome datasets of PD demonstrate heterogeneous expression patterns of SIRT1 and SNCA. In iPSC and postmortem datasets, SIRT1 expression was increased while SNCA decreased, which may represent a protective or compensatory response. In contrast, in another postmortem dataset (GSE114918), SIRT1 was decreased, and SNCA showed an increasing trend in the SNc, consistent with classical Parkinson’s pathology reported in dopaminergic neurons. In NPC and other postmortem datasets (GSE114918VTA/GSE20291), both SIRT1 and SNCA were reduced, which may reflect differences in cell types or post-transcriptional regulation rather than general expectations in the literature. Additionally, drug screening of genes identified through network analysis indicated that resveratrol may act as a potential therapeutic agent.

Conclusion: These findings demonstrate that SIRT1 and SNCA exhibit heterogeneous expression patterns in PD, support the protective role of SIRT1, and suggest that natural activators such as resveratrol may have potential therapeutic value.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK-124Z229 for the support.

Keyword: Parkinson’s disease, SIRT1, SNCA, potential agents, resveratrol

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PP20

AIR-LIQUID INTERFACE CULTURE AS A PHYSIOLOGICALLY RELEVANT 3D MODEL FOR SKIN RESEARCH AND REGENERATIVE APPLICATIONS

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The air-liquid interface (ALI) culture technique has become a key method in developing advanced three-dimensional (3D) in vitro skin and mucosal models. Unlike traditional submerged cultures, ALI culture allows the basal surface of cells to remain in contact with nutrient-rich culture medium, while the apical surface is directly exposed to air. This unique setup promotes oxygenation, stratification, and cellular differentiation, resulting in tissue constructs that closely resemble the anatomical and physiological properties of native human skin. The strength of ALI culture lies in its ability to generate functional, multilayered epidermis along with a collagen-based dermal compartment, thereby replicating the barrier properties, morphology, and regenerative capacity of human tissue. Such models serve as robust platforms for studying wound healing, tissue regeneration, and drug delivery, as well as for assessing cosmetic and pharmaceutical safety. Importantly, ALI-based models provide an ethical and reproducible alternative to animal testing, aligning with current international regulations and the principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement). Applications of ALI culture extend across toxicology, dermatology, and regenerative medicine. In drug delivery research, ALI-derived 3D models allow precise evaluation of nanoparticle penetration, bioactive compound release, and their impact on tissue repair processes. The integration of nanotechnology with ALI culture systems offers an innovative approach to exploring novel therapeutic strategies while maintaining physiological relevance. Overall, ALI culture represents a transformative advancement in tissue engineering and biomedical research. By combining physiological relevance with ethical responsibility, ALI-based 3D models stand as an indispensable platform for the next generation of preclinical studies in skin biology, wound healing, and targeted drug delivery.

Keyword: *Air-liquid interface, 3D skin model, Tissue engineering, Drug delivery, Wound healing*

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PP21

COMPREHENSIVE MIRNA LANDSCAPE IN NSCLC SUBTYPES IDENTIFIES NOVEL BIOMARKER CANDIDATES

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Background/Introduction: Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) accounts for nearly 85% of lung cancer cases and remains the leading cause of cancer-related death worldwide. Its poor prognosis is largely due to late diagnosis and tendency of NSCLC to metastasize. MicroRNAs (miRNAs), small non-coding RNAs responsible for post-transcriptional regulation of gene expression, play crucial roles in cancer biology. However, comprehensive characterization of miRNA expression across NSCLC subtypes and hence their potential use as biomarkers remains limited.

Purpose: This study aimed to find differentially expressed miRNAs (DEmiRNAs) in three NSCLC subtypes and evaluate their potential prognostic biomarkers by integrating enrichment and survival analyses.

Methods: Samples from lung adenocarcinoma (LUAD, n=25), squamous cell carcinoma (SCC, n=19), and large cell lung carcinoma (LCLC, n=7) patients, including normal lung tissue, primary tumor, tumor microenvironment, lymph node, and peripheral blood, were analyzed using Illumina HiSeq 2500 and NovaSeq 6000 platforms. Differential expression analysis was used to identify DEmiRNAs (adjusted-p < 0.05). Target genes and enrichment analyses were performed using miRNet and DAVID, and survival analyses were conducted using OncoMiR.

Results: Of the 43 DEmiRNAs with $|\log_2FC| > 4$, 28 had been previously reported in non-small cell lung cancer, confirming our findings. We identified the remaining 10 down-regulated and 5 up-regulated miRNAs as novel biomarker candidates. Pathway enrichment of the 10 genes most frequently targeted by the novel DEmiRNAs revealed significant associations with the MyD88 cascade, Toll-like receptor signaling, and viral infection pathways. Kaplan-Meier curves demonstrated prognostic significance for three of the novel DEmiRNAs.

Conclusion: Our findings highlight 15 novel DEmiRNAs potentially involved in the NSCLC molecular mechanism. These DEmiRNAs also may serve as non-invasive biomarkers for prognosis and could inform the development of targeted therapeutic strategies.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK for the financial support (115S113).

Keyword: Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), differentially expressed miRNAs, novel biomarkers.

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MUMIO ENHANCES TEMOZOLOMIDE RESPONSE AND INDUCES APOPTOSIS AND FERROPTOSIS IN GLIOBLASTOMA CELLS

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Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is the most aggressive primary brain tumor, characterized by limited treatment options and rapid resistance to the standard chemotherapeutic agent, temozolomide (TMZ). Novel adjunctive therapies are urgently needed. Mumio (Shilajit), a natural substance rich in fulvic acid, humic compounds, and bioactive metabolites, possesses documented antioxidant, neuroprotective, and anticancer properties, yet its potential in GBM remains unexplored. The study aimed to evaluate the activity of Mumio in both TMZ-sensitive (U87) and TMZ-resistant (LN18) GBM cell models. Mumio extract was chemically characterized and applied to GBM cells at varying concentrations. Cell viability was assessed by MTT and colony formation assays, while fluorescent staining was used to examine mitochondrial activity, reactive oxygen species (ROS), and lipid accumulation. Western blotting measures apoptotic markers (PARP, Caspase-3, PTEN), ferroptosis-related proteins (NRF2, FTH1), and Akt pathway signaling. The combination effects of Mumio with TMZ were also investigated. Mumio reduced cell viability in a dose- and time-dependent manner, with stronger effects observed in U87 cells. MTT and colony formation assays confirmed its cytotoxic and anti-proliferative activity. Fluorescent staining revealed mitochondrial dysfunction, increased ROS, and lipid accumulation. Western blot analysis showed activation of apoptotic markers (cleaved PARP, Caspase-3, PTEN) and modulation of ferroptosis-related proteins, including reduced FTH1 and altered NRF2 expression, particularly in LN18 cells. Additionally, Mumio suppressed Akt signaling and enhanced TMZ cytotoxicity, reducing clonogenic survival in both cell lines. Mumio induces pro-apoptotic and ferroptosis-related effects in GBM cell lines and enhances the activity of TMZ, including in TMZ-resistant models. These results emphasize Mumio's potential as a complementary adjunct to conventional GBM treatment and support its further evaluation in preclinical studies and future translational research. We gratefully acknowledge TÜBİTAK (1002/223S506) for financial support, the Kutman Lab and Institute of Biotechnology for access to ICP facilities, and special thanks to Burak Tuncbas for performing the ICP analyses.

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Keywords: Glioblastoma multiforme, Temozolomide, Mumio, Apoptosis, Ferroptosis, Reactive Oxygen Species

PP23

ANTIVIRAL AND IMMUNOSUPPRESSOR PROPERTIES OF ELETTARIA CARDAMOMUM AS A PHYTOTHERAPEUTIC CANDIDATE AGAINST SARS-COV-2

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Phytotherapeutic agents constitute an essential and urgent therapeutic approach in the fight against the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Their broad spectrum of bioactive compounds, particularly antioxidative, antiviral, and immunomodulatory agents, offers a promising alternative or adjunct to conventional therapeutics. The primary objective of this study was to comprehensively evaluate the antiviral activity and immunomodulatory potential of *Elettaria cardamomum* (cardamom) extract from Mediterranean region against SARS-CoV-2 infection using high-throughput screening and in vitro assays. Four sensitive HEK293T, Vero E6, Caco-2, and Calu-3 cell lines were used to evaluate both the bioefficacy and safety profile of *E. cardamomum* extract. Cell viability was determined via the MTT assay, while Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) staining was carried out to examine morphological features. Apoptosis was assessed through Annexin V/PI/Hoechst staining, and its antioxidative potential was determined using the DCFDA assay. The antiviral potential of the extract was further explored through high-throughput screening, including an ELISA-based assay measuring inhibition of the SARS-CoV-2 receptor-binding domain (RBD) interaction with ACE2, and a FRET-based assay targeting inhibition of the viral main protease (Mpro). Additionally, a pseudovirus S1 neutralization assay utilizing ACE2-transfected HEK293T cells was conducted to assess viral entry blockade. The extract demonstrated 54% inhibition of RBD-ACE2 binding (ELISA) and achieved approximately 31% suppression of SARS-CoV-2 pseudovirus S1 entry into HEK293T cells. The extract exhibited strong inhibitory activity against the viral main protease (Mpro), achieving 76% suppression at 100 µg/ml in the FRET-based assay. Immunomodulatory analysis further indicated marked suppression of cytokines IL-1β (77%) and TNF-α (65%) evaluated by ELISA within a SARS-CoV-2 pseudovirus S1-infected co-culture model of THP-1 and HEK293T cells using a transwell insert system. The results highlight the substantial antioxidant, antiviral, and immunosuppressor properties of *E. cardamomum* extract, underscoring its promise as a phytotherapeutic candidate against SARS-

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CoV-2. This study is supported by the TUBITAK-MALTA Bilateral Cooperation Project No.221N094.

Keyword: *Elettaria cardamomum*, Antiviral activity, Immunomodulatory effect, SARS-CoV-2

PP24

IDENTIFICATION OF METABOLITE AND LIPID BIOMARKERS IN NSCLC THROUGH LC-MS/MS ANALYSIS

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Abstract Background: Lung cancer remains a leading cause of cancer mortality worldwide, primarily due to late-stage diagnosis and limited treatment options. Metabololipidomics, the comprehensive profiling of metabolites and lipids, provides a powerful approach to identify molecular signatures associated with tumor development and progression. Such signatures hold promise for improving early detection, screening, and personalized therapeutic strategies, as well as for establishing novel biomarkers that can support diagnosis and disease monitoring. **Purpose:** This study conducted a comprehensive analysis of metabolomics data from the LUNGMARK project, aiming to identify metabolite- and lipid-based signatures associated with NSCLC. Identified signatures will be evaluated and prioritized for translation into screening assays, early-detection diagnostics, and systems for disease monitoring. **Methods:** Blood and tissue samples from healthy volunteers and lung cancer patients were stored at -80°C until analysis. Tissues were homogenized in methanol, centrifuged, and supernatants reconstituted for Q-TOF MS/MS (Sciex X500R) using a Kinetex C18 column with gradient elution. QC pools and blanks were included. Both MS1 and MS2 spectra were acquired with SWATH-DIA, and data were processed in XCMS for peak detection, alignment, and filtering. **Results:** Metabolomic profiling distinguished normal, primary, and metastatic lung tissues, with 5,826 features separating groups by PLS-DA ($R^2 = 0.92$). Permutation and ROC analyses ($\text{AUC} > 0.96$) confirmed high sensitivity and specificity. Pathway enrichment revealed major alterations in lipid and amino acid metabolism, particularly arachidonic acid, linoleic acid, arginine, and tryptophan pathways. Subtype comparisons (adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, large cell carcinoma) also showed distinct metabolic reprogramming. Key annotated metabolites included arachidonic acid, linoleic acid, lysine, arginine, prostaglandins, and sphingolipids, implicating oxidative stress, inflammation, and amino acid

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biosynthesis. Conclusions: These findings demonstrate distinct metabolomic and lipidomic signatures associated with NSCLC progression and subtypes, highlighting their potential as diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers. Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK for the support (115S113).

Keyword: Lung cancer, Metabolipidomics, multi-omics, biomarkers, NSCLC

PP25

ASSESSMENT OF A DECELLULARIZED BOVINE PERICARDIUM SCAFFOLD FOR TISSUE REGENERATION APPLICATIONS

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The increasing demand for organ and tissue transplantation, combined with the shortage of suitable donors and the limitations of immune rejection and biocompatibility, has encouraged the development of biomimetic, anti-immunogenic, and functional three-dimensional (3D) organoids. Decellularized extracellular matrix (dECM)-based biomaterials with preserved structural and biochemical components have emerged as promising scaffolds in tissue Engineering applications. The aim of this study was to optimize the decellularization of bovine pericardium in order to obtain a biocompatible, anti-immunogenic, and durable biomaterial capable of supporting tissue regeneration and reconstruction. For this purpose, five different decellularization protocols combining mechanical, physical, and chemical approaches were applied. The characterization of dECM was performed by histological staining (Hematoxylin–Eosin for cellular residues, Safranin O for proteoglycans, Fast Green for collagen, and Alcian Blue for glycosaminoglycans), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for morphological evaluation, and biochemical assays for DNA, RNA, collagen, and GAG quantification. Additionally, DNA/protein release from the bovine pericardium during decellularization was monitored with nanodrop measurement, while the scaffold weight changes were measured to evaluate ECM preservation. Biocompatibility was tested using L929 fibroblasts through MTT cell viability assay. The results showed that Method 1 (Triton X-100 + SDC) and Method 2 (SDS + Triton X-100) achieved the highest DNA removal efficiencies (89.34% and 91.37%) and superior collagen preservation ($158 \pm 23.82 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ and $120.89 \pm 13.42 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$), respectively. SEM analysis revealed the porous and homogeneous ECM structures in both groups, indicating effective and balanced decellularization. Biocompatibility analysis demonstrated that provided the highest cell viability (91.41%) without cytotoxic effects. In conclusion, The most efficient DNA removal and the preserved essential ECM components were obtained via application of the decellularization Method 2. The resulting dECM scaffolds

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exhibited structural integrity and biocompatibility, suggesting their potential as candidates for dECM-based bioinks in tissue engineering. This study supported by TUSEB Project No: 33390.

Keyword: *Decellularization, dECM, Bovine Pericard, Biocompatibility*

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PP26

SERUM-FREE AND SUSPENSION ADAPTATION STRATEGIES FOR CHO-DG44 CELLS

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Background: Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells, particularly the DG44 lineage, are a cornerstone of recombinant protein production, renowned for their exceptional productivity, robust safety profiles. Traditional cultivation methods depend on fetal bovine serum (FBS), which presents significant drawbacks including high costs, variability, and risks of contamination. Transitioning to serum-free suspension culture is essential for achieving scalable, reproducible biomanufacturing processes.

Purpose: This study aimed to adapt CHO-DG44 cells to serum-free and suspension culture conditions by systematically evaluating a diverse array of media and innovative supplementation strategies, with the goal of enhancing scalability, consistency.

Methods: CHO-DG44 cells were initially expanded in Alpha-MEM supplemented with 10% FBS, followed by a gradual reduction to 1% FBS over multiple passages to facilitate a controlled adaptation process. Cells stabilized in the 1% FBS environment were subsequently prepared for testing across a range of media, including DMEM F12, CD-CHO, CDM4MAb, and ActiPro. These media were enriched with a carefully selected combination of supplements—insulin-transferrin-selenium, polyamines, antioxidants, and HT supplement—to optimize cell growth and survival. Cell viability and growth rates were monitored across numerous passages, with successfully adapted clones cryopreserved.

Results: All media except ActiPro, when supplemented with insulin-transferrin-selenium, polyamines, and antioxidants, failed to maintain viability under low-serum conditions. CHO-DG44 cells cultured in ActiPro achieved greater than 90% viability, demonstrated stable suspension growth, and exhibited doubling times of approximately 24 hours across 10 passages. Cryopreservation of adapted clones revealed high recovery rates.

Conclusion(s): ActiPro medium provides a robust and effective platform for the serum-free suspension adaptation of CHO-DG44 cells, effectively overcoming the inherent limitations of serum-dependent cultures. The established method offers a reproducible and reliable approach for developing production-ready cell lines, suitable for both academic research and industrial biomanufacturing applications.

Acknowledgements: We thank Dr. Lawrence Chasin, Columbia University, USA, for kindly providing the CHO-DG44 cells.

Keyword: *serum-free, suspension, cell line adaptation*

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PP27

CHARACTERIZATION AND BIOCOMPATIBILITY OF PLA/SPIRULINA-BASED NANOPARTICLES

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Nanoparticle-based carrier systems offer enhanced therapeutic efficacy, prolonged circulation, and reduced systemic toxicity as alternatives to traditional drug delivery systems. Microalgae are preferred in these systems due to their simple structure, high protein content, low-cost production, and biological sustainability. *Spirulina platensis*, a microalga rich in protein and antioxidants, is a promising bioactive ingredient; however, its limited stability limits its direct biomedical use. This study aims to produce poly(lactic acid) (PLA), an FDA-approved biodegradable polymer, and *Spirulina*-based nanoparticles using the double emulsion (W/O/W) method to evaluate their physicochemical properties and cytocompatible activity to develop nanocarriers. Nanoparticles were synthesized by double emulsion (W/O/W) technique using 0.5% PLA and different *Spirulina* concentrations (0.125%, 0.25%, and 0.5%) which are optimized. Characterization studies confirmed the production of spherical nanoparticles below 500 nm with a uniform size distribution, while FTIR confirmed the integration of *Spirulina* into the PLA matrix. In vitro evaluations demonstrated that PLA/*Spirulina* nanoparticles were non-cytotoxic and supported cell proliferation. Studies performed on Human Dermal Fibroblasts (HDF) and Human Umbilical Vein Endothelial Cells (HUVEC) showed that the nanoparticles demonstrated positive responses by providing higher viability and supporting cell growth compared to controls. These results demonstrate strong biocompatibility and suitability for advanced biomedical applications. In conclusion, PLA/*Spirulina* nanoparticles demonstrated favorable physicochemical stability and strong in vitro biocompatibility, demonstrating their potential as sustainable nanocarriers for future drug delivery and tissue engineering applications. This study was supported by TÜBİTAK through the TÜBİTAK 1001 project, coded 124M100, and their support is gratefully acknowledged.

Keyword: *Nanoparticles, poly(lactic acid), Spirulina platensis, Double Emulsion, Biocompatibility*

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PP28

TRANSCRIPTOMIC PROFILING REVEALS SUBTYPE-SPECIFIC MOLECULAR SIGNATURES IN LUNG CANCER

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Background/Introduction: Lung cancer is one of the most common malignancies worldwide and accounts for nearly one-fifth of cancer-related deaths. Early diagnosis remains a major challenge due to the lack of effective diagnostic tools, leading to most cases being detected at advanced or metastatic stages with poor survival outcomes. Although advances have been made in lung cancer biology, the molecular mechanisms driving tumor initiation, progression, metastasis, and therapy resistance remain incompletely understood.

Purpose: We aimed to elucidate the transcriptional differences between tumor and non-tumor tissues across subtypes of lung cancer-lung adenocarcinoma (LUAD), squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), and large cell lung carcinoma (LCLC)-by performing comparative differential gene expression profiling.

Methods: Samples from 51 lung cancer patients undergoing lobectomy, including normal lung, primary tumors, adjacent tissues, lymph nodes, and peripheral blood, were sequenced using Illumina HiSeq 2500 and NovaSeq 6000. In parallel, transcriptome data from TCGA (539 LUAD tumors with 59 normal samples and 502 SCC tumors with 51 normal samples) were analyzed with the same pipeline. Differential expression analysis was performed using DESeq2. DEGs were defined by adjusted p-value $< 1 \times 10^{-20}$ (tumor, metastasis, blood) or < 0.05 (stroma) and $|\log_2FC| \geq 1$. Functional enrichment of DEGs was conducted via ConsensusPathDB with adjusted p-value < 0.05 .

Results: In tumor samples, 461 LUAD, 493 SCC and 33 LCLC-specific upregulated mRNAs were identified, while 168 LUAD and 244 SCC and 37 LCLC-specific downregulated mRNAs were detected. Comparing our dataset with the analysis of TCGA, we differentially identified 193 DEGs for LUAD and 274 DEGs for SCC.

Conclusion: Our integrative analysis reveals both shared and subtype-specific gene expression signatures in lung cancer, uncovering novel DEGs and pathways with potential diagnostic and therapeutic relevance.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK for the financial support (115S113).

Keyword: Lung cancer, transcriptomic analysis, differentially expressed genes, novel mRNAs, integrative multiomics

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CROSSTALK OF POST-TRANSLATIONAL MODIFICATIONS OF ELK-1

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Background: ELK-1, an ETS-domain transcription factor, plays essential roles in neuronal plasticity, stress signaling, and cell survival. Its activity is modulated by a complex network of post-translational modifications (PTMs) including phosphorylation, SUMOylation, ubiquitination, and acetylation. Dysregulation of these PTMs has been implicated in neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's, Huntington's, ALS, and Alzheimer's, where ELK-1 contributes to both protein aggregation and neuroprotective gene expression.

Purpose: This study aimed to investigate the interplay between phosphorylation, SUMOylation, and acetylation on ELK-1, and to assess how these PTMs regulate ELK-1 function in neuronal cells.

Methods: PTM sites on ELK-1 were first identified through in silico analysis. Site-directed mutagenesis was then used to generate phospho-mutants (S303A/E, S304A/E, S324A/E, S326A/E, T417A) and a SUMO-deficient variant (K230R/K249R; K2R). NSC-34 motor neuron cells were transfected with either wild-type or mutant pCMV-ELK-1 plasmids. Following transfection, protein isolation was performed, and the samples were analyzed by western blotting with ELK-1, Phospho (S/T), SUMO1, and Acetyl-Lysine antibodies.

Results: Phospho-mutants altered ELK-1 phosphorylation profiles and protein stability, while the SUMO-deficient K2R mutant enhanced S383 phosphorylation, supporting a phospho-SUMO crosstalk. SUMO assay results confirmed that SUMOylation patterns were modulated by specific phosphorylation events. Together, these results demonstrate that phosphorylation, SUMOylation, and acetylation dynamically interact to modulate ELK-1 activity.

Conclusion: This study provides the first integrated mapping of phosphorylation, SUMOylation, and acetylation on ELK-1, highlighting their cooperative role in regulating its stability, activity, and modification status. These findings underline the importance of ELK-1 PTMs in neuronal regulation and suggest their potential contribution to neurodegenerative disease mechanisms. Importantly, the effects of the identified ELK-1 peptides on aggregation kinetics will be further investigated to assess their potential neuroprotective roles.

Acknowledgements: We thank grants TÜBİTAK 1001-124Z680, and the YÖK ADEP 2024-A-113-10 for providing funding for this study.

Keyword: *ELK-1, Post-translational modifications (PTMs), Neurodegeneration*

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PP30

PHOSPHOPROTEOMIC PROFILING IDENTIFIES NOVEL BIOMARKERS AND THERAPEUTIC TARGETS IN NSCLC

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Background: Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) constitutes 85% of lung cancers and remains the leading cause of mortality. Tumor heterogeneity and therapy resistance limit efficient treatments. Since phosphorylation regulates key oncogenic pathways, large-scale phosphoproteomics offers a unique opportunity to uncover molecular vulnerabilities and therapeutic targets.

Purpose: This study aimed to comprehensively characterize the phosphoproteomic landscape of NSCLC across multiple tissue compartments and serum, to identify subtype-specific signaling alterations, novel phosphorylation events, and potential therapeutic targets.

Methods: We analyzed 255 clinical samples from 51 NSCLC patients, including adenocarcinoma (LUAD), squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), and large cell carcinoma (LCLC). Specimens included normal lung, primary tumors, tumor microenvironment, lymph nodes, and serum. Samples underwent TMT-based LC-MS/MS with phosphopeptide enrichment. Data processing, which was optimized through AI-based tools by CimenLAB at the Institute of Biotechnology, GTU, included differential phosphorylation analysis, functional enrichment, kinase-substrate inference, protein-protein interaction (PPI) networks, and drug-gene interaction mapping.

Results: Distinct subtype-specific phosphorylation patterns were identified. LUAD was characterized by dysregulation of lipid metabolism and RNA splicing machinery, SCC by

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coagulation and immune-related signaling, and LCLC by replication stress and spliceosomal dysfunction. Novel phosphorylation events were detected, including DDX46 in AD and F5 in SCC. Kinase enrichment analysis highlighted CSNK2A1 as a central regulator in LCLC, while APOB, VTN, HSP90AA1, and HSP90AB1 emerged as hubs in subtype-specific PPI networks. Cross-referencing with drug–gene interaction databases revealed therapeutic potential for targeting lipid regulators, coagulation factors, HSP90, and replication stress kinases.

Conclusions: This first large-scale phosphoproteomic atlas of NSCLC across multiple tissues and subtypes provides critical insights into oncogenic signaling heterogeneity. Identified phosphoproteins and pathways represent promising biomarkers and therapeutic vulnerabilities, supporting the development of precision oncology strategies in NSCLC.

Acknowledgements: We thank TÜBİTAK (115S113) and Gebze Technical University (ADEP 2024-A-113-10 to CimenLAB) for the support.

Keyword: *Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), Phosphoproteomics, Biomarkers, Therapeutic targets, Tumor heterogeneity*

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PP31

In Silico Screening and Inhibition of *P. aeruginosa* β -Carbonic Anhydrase by Coumarin Derivatives

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INTRODUCTION

The opportunistic pathogen *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* causes severe infections and is known for its remarkable adaptability and high antibiotic resistance, rendering many existing treatments ineffective. Depending on its colonization state, *P. aeruginosa* can survive under various CO₂ conditions, increasing its pathogenicity and persistence. Many pathogenic bacteria can sense environmental CO₂ levels and adjust their metabolic pathways accordingly. Therefore, identifying CO₂-sensitive biomolecules involved in survival and virulence has become an important target in drug discovery. In this context, carbonic anhydrases (CAs), metalloenzymes responsible for CO₂ conversion, play a critical role in bacterial survival and pathogenicity.

PURPOSE

This study aims to investigate the inhibitory potential of coumarin derivatives against *P. aeruginosa* β -carbonic anhydrase (psCA3, PDB ID: 4RXY) using in silico molecular docking analysis.

METHODS

Coumarin derivatives were drawn using ChemDraw and energy minimized using Avogadro software. The crystal structure of psCA3 (PDB ID: 4RXY) was prepared in Discovery Studio 2021 by removing water molecules and optimizing the active site. Docking simulations were performed with AutoDock Tools, focusing on the catalytic Zn²⁺ site. Docking scores and ligand–protein interactions were analyzed to identify potential inhibitory interactions.

RESULTS

Docking analyses revealed binding energies ranging from -5.4 to -5.5 kcal/mol. The lactone carbonyl oxygen of coumarin derivatives formed strong coordination with the catalytic Zn²⁺ ion, while additional hydrophobic and van der Waals interactions with VAL66, ILE116, GLY102, and GLY103 contributed to complex stability. These findings indicate stable ligand accommodation in the enzyme's active site.

CONCLUSION

The selected coumarin derivatives exhibited stable and specific binding to carbonic anhydrase (4RXY), suggesting their potential as lead structures for novel antibacterial agents. Further derivatization and in vitro studies are planned to enhance inhibitory efficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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PP32

CAN BACTERIA TURN RICE STRAW INTO A BIOFERTILIZER FOR RICE?

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As a staple crop, rice grows in our country's Black Sea and Thrace regions. After harvesting the rice, straw is left behind as waste, so the most convenient way to eliminate is burning. This leads to air and land pollution, while resulting in the loss of potentially valuable organic matter. Rice straw is difficult to decompose because it contains high amounts of lignin and hemicellulose, as well as silica in its shoot and husk. Therefore, its incorporation into soil as an organic soil amendment is not common practice. In this study, three *Bacillus* sp. strains with the ability to break down the complex substances in the straw were used. Those strains isolated from Kırklareli and Samsun, regions where rice is cultivated. Rice straw was inoculated with bacteria, then incorporated into the soils and incubated without plants for two months. Plants were grown either in sterilized or native soil. At the end of the incubation, an approximately 50% increase in extractable potassium (K) was observed irrespective of the soil type. Although straw contains 0.2% Fe, its application together with isolates reduced the extractable iron (Fe) concentration in the soils by 5%. These changes in extractable mineral concentrations were not attributable to significant pH changes, regardless of soil sterilization. After 12 weeks of growth, no significant difference in vegetative yield was observed. Nevertheless, some significant changes in tissue mineral concentration were detected. Tissue K and P concentration increased by up to 15% to 36%, respectively. Although the study is still ongoing in the greenhouse, it can be concluded that certain nutrient concentrations were positively affected, and yield parameters will be further evaluated after harvest. This study was supported by Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under the Grant Number 123O668. The authors thank to TUBITAK for their supports.

Keyword: *Rice, Straw, Bacteria, Soil Amendment, Biofertilizer*

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PP33

FROM WASTE TO GROWTH: BIOCHAR-BASED SUBSTRATES AS COST-EFFECTIVE ALTERNATIVE TO COCOPEAT IN SOILLESS PEPPER CULTIVATION

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In controlled environment agriculture (CEA), soilless substrates such as cocopeat and coco coir are widely used for their favorable water retention and aeration; but temperate countries with large greenhouse sectors rely on imports. This study, conducted in collaboration with Mavruz Tarım, a commercial tomato producer in Çanakkale, Türkiye, investigates converting tomato vegetative biomass waste into biochar via gasification to develop a sustainable, locally sourced alternative substrate for soilless cultivation. A novel pre-treatment method has been developed to reduce biochar's salinity and alkalinity, with a patent pending. Seedling trials identified the optimal biochar–perlite ratio, with 15% biochar incorporation improving agronomic performance. A five-month Capia pepper trial compared optimized biochar–perlite mixtures with perlite and cocopeat across two seasons and cultivars. In the first season, biochar–perlite yielded 14% and 5% higher than perlite and cocopeat, respectively. In the second season, biochar–perlite had a statistically significant 23% yield increase over perlite and comparable yield to cocopeat. At four months, biochar–perlite plants yielded significantly more than both cocopeat and perlite, but by five months, cocopeat yields caught up, resulting in statistical equivalence. This underlines the importance of longer trials in substrate evaluation and general CEA cultivation. No significant differences were observed among substrates for leaf number or average fruit weight, though fruit weight varied between cultivars while consistent across substrates. Overall, biochar–perlite mixtures offer a viable, cost-effective, sustainable alternative to imported cocopeat. Substrate performance depends on crop species, cultivar, and trial duration, highlighting the need for tailored, long-term studies to advance CEA substrate technology.

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Keyword: *biochar, cocopeat, soilless agriculture, controlled environment agriculture, substrate*

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PP34

LONG NON-CODING RNA ASSOCIATED COMPETING ENDOGENOUS RNA (CERNA) INTERACTIONS MODULATE MAIZE LEAF GROWTH IN RESPONSE TO FUSARIUM VERTICILLIOIDES INFECTION

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Maize (*Zea mays*), the third most consumed crop worldwide, is vital for global food security. However, its productivity is threatened by biotic stress, particularly infections by fungal pathogen *Fusarium verticillioides*, which suppress leaf growth and impair development. For sustainable agriculture, maintaining photosynthetic efficiency and effective defense responses is essential to secure yield stability. Leaf growth relies on tightly regulated processes such as cell division and expansion, increasingly recognized to be influenced by non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs). Among these, microRNAs (miRNAs) and long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) interact through competing endogenous RNA (ceRNA) networks to regulate stress tolerance.

This study examined the impact of *F. verticillioides* on maize leaf growth zones, meristem (Me), elongation (El), and mature (Ma), with emphasis on ceR319 and ceR396 networks. Tolerant (R) and susceptible (S) lines were inoculated in soil and analyzed at six-leaf stage vs. controls (C). Infection reduced leaf length (FLL) by 26% in R and 16% in S plants, while leaf elongation rate (LER) declined 19% in S. Antioxidant assays showed zone-specific shifts: ascorbate peroxidase (APX) activity in RI Me increased 3-fold compared to El and Ma and was 2-fold higher than RC Me; catalase (CAT) activity in RI Me rose 2-fold compared to El and Ma; and peroxidase (POD) activity in SI El decreased relative to SC. Transcript profiling revealed strong regulatory dynamics. miR319 and miR396 were upregulated in El of infected plants by 4- and 8-fold, respectively, while miR319 was downregulated 9-fold in RI Ma relative to RC. GRF15 was elevated in Me, whereas lnc319 and TCP38 were upregulated in RI Ma, and lnc89 was downregulated in RC El.

Overall, ceRNA networks emerged as central regulators of maize leaf growth under fungal stress, providing molecular insights for breeding resistant cultivars to advance sustainable agriculture.

This study was supported by TUBITAK (Grant no: 221O321).

Keyword: *Leaf Growth Zones; Biotic Stress Tolerance; ceRNA Regulatory Network; miRNA; lncRNA*

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PP35

EFFECTS OF BORON ON THE GROWTH AND NITROGEN NUTRITION OF ALFALFA INOCULATED WITH ENSIFER MELILOTI

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Alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*) establishes a well-documented symbiosis with *Ensifer meliloti*, facilitating biological nitrogen (N) fixation and contributing to sustainable agriculture by reducing reliance on synthetic N fertilizers. Boron (B) is a micronutrient that plays a vital role in nodule development and nitrogenase activity; however, the mechanistic interplay between boron and nitrogen in regulating nodulation efficiency is not documented in alfalfa. This study hypothesized that sufficient B is critical for effective *E. meliloti*-mediated nitrogen fixation and that boron deficiency impairs alfalfa growth and forage quality, effects that can be mitigated through appropriate boron fertilization. To test this hypothesis, two *E. meliloti* strains were cultured and applied to alfalfa grown under greenhouse conditions. A total of 96 pots were used to set up experiments in two different soilless settings: deep water culture and perlite/vermiculite culture. Full factorial designs were used, combining two N levels, two B levels, and rhizobial treatments. Symptomatic B deficiency was observed in treatment groups that received higher N and was prevented by adequate B fertilization. Inoculation with rhizobia was effective in improving growth and the overall status of the plants. Ongoing research includes spectrophotometric analysis of chlorophylls and carotenoids and total nitrogen analysis to gain deeper insights into plants' responses to treatments. This study contributes to our understanding of the complex nutrient interactions influencing biological nitrogen fixation and highlights the potential of effective rhizobial inoculation to improve sustainable forage production, particularly in boron or nitrogen-limited soils.

The rhizobia strains were kindly provided by Asst. Prof. Onur Öztaş from Koç University. This study was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under the 2209-A Undergraduate Research Project Support Programme.

Keyword: *Biofertilizer, Biological Nitrogen Fixation, Boron, Ensifer meliloti, Medicago sativa (Alfalfa)*

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PP36

WHEAT GROWTH RESPONSE TO MYCORRHIZAL-BACTERIAL CONSORTIA AS BIOFERTILIZERS DEPENDS ON SOIL TYPE, PH, AND NATIVE MICROBIAL ACTIVITY

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Arbuscular mycorrhizae (AM) establish an often mutualistic symbiosis with most terrestrial plants. This symbiosis helps the roots of the host plant effectively explore a larger soil volume and extract different nutrients including but not limited to phosphorus (P). Mycorrhiza-helper bacteria, which may also have plant growth promoting characteristics, can result in a synergistic improvement of plant growth and resilience. However, interactions between plants and microbiota are often governed by several factors, such as soil type, availability of nutrients, host genotype, abiotic stress, developmental stage, and climate. Two pot experiments were conducted with the aim to observe the effects of different solid AM formulations with or without a bacterial consortium, consisting of *Paenibacillus polymxa*, *Bacillus mojavensis*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Pseudomonas vancouveren*, on wheat growth under different conditions. In the first experiment, two types of soil with different pH values, three different solid carriers, and seven microbial treatments (control; *Rhizophagus irregularis* and *R. irregularis* + bacteria; *Glomus versiforme* and *G. versiforme* + bacteria; *G. mosseae* and *G. mosseae* + bacteria) were tested. Growth responses were highly dependent on soil type. In acidic soil, plants inoculated with *G. mosseae* or *G. mosseae* + bacteria were found to have significantly higher dry weights compared to non-inoculated plants. However, responses in alkaline soil were less pronounced. In the second pot experiment, the same microbial biofertilizers were tested with two carriers in sterile and non-sterile alkaline soil conditions. In sterilized soil, the *G. versiforme* + bacteria formulation with one of the carriers, resulted in a 27% increase in dry weight of plants, highlighting the potential of microbial consortia. The results of both experiments demonstrated that the effects of biofertilizers were strongly influenced by soil traits and native microbial community.

This study was supported by Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under the Grant Number 222O498.

Keyword: *Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, plant growth promoting rhizobacteria, soil pH, soil sterilization, biofertilizer consortia*

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PP37

WHEAT GROWTH PROMOTION BY SEED-APPLIED LIQUID MICROBIAL FERTILIZERS: INFLUENCE OF SOIL PH AND NUTRIENT SUPPLY

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Liquid microbial fertilizers are increasingly recognized as sustainable alternatives to chemical fertilizers for improving crop growth under nutrient-limited conditions. However, their efficiency may depend on soil pH and nutrient availability. This study investigated the effects of microbial inoculants on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* cv. Nusrat) seed growth in acidic (pH 5.5) and alkaline (pH 8.3) soils under low (100 ppm N, 25 ppm P) and high (200 ppm N, 100 ppm P) fertilization regimes. The microbial consortium (B3), containing strains with N fixation, siderophore production, P solubilization, and IAA production, was applied as seed treatment in combination with three arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi (*Rhizophagus irregularis*, *Glomus versiforme*, and *Glomus mosseae*). A factorial design of 18 treatments, including controls, carriers (S1-S4), and microbial formulations, was tested with four replicates. Vegetative sampling at five weeks showed that under low fertilization, control plants exhibited stunted growth, whereas microbial inoculation substantially improved biomass. The strongest responses occurred in acidic soils with *G. versiforme*+B3 and *G. mosseae*+B3, which enhanced shoot dry weight by up to 67% compared to the control. In alkaline soils, growth promotion was more dependent on carrier performance, with S4-based formulations, particularly with *G. mosseae*+B3, which enhanced biomass by up to 55%. Under high fertilization, plants grew vigorously, and microbial contributions were present but less pronounced. ANOVA indicated that fertilization and microbial applications were the primary determinants of plant growth, with significant three-way interactions under acidic but not alkaline soils. Results suggest that liquid microbial fertilizers are most effective under nutrient-limited conditions, particularly in acidic conditions. The stronger response in acidic soils may be attributed to enhanced nutrient mobilization and symbiosis. In alkaline soils, the efficacy of microbial formulations was strongly influenced by carrier performance.

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Keyword: *arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, liquid microbial fertilizer, PGPR, sustainable agriculture, wheat*

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PP38

POTENTIAL CONTRIBUTION OF STEEL SLAG TO SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE LETTUCE PRODUCTION

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Sustainable waste management necessitates efficient evaluation of industrial by-products across different fields, including but not limited to agriculture. Steel slag, a by-product of steel manufacturing, is a promising material as fertilizer and soil amendment owing to its mineral composition and physicochemical characteristics. In this study, the effects of various electric-arc-furnace (EAF) slag treatments on the yield and mineral composition of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* cv. Papyon) grown under two different fertilization regimes were investigated in alkaline and acidic soil types under greenhouse conditions. The highest dose of ground EAF slag amendment (2.0%) into acidic soil increased the dry biomass by approximately 5-fold compared to control under lower fertilization condition (1X-NP). Non-ground EAF slag application at the highest dose also improved the dry biomass by 187% over control under the same conditions. The medium and the highest doses of ground slag treatment into acidic soil was also effective under higher fertilization (2X-NP), enhancing the lettuce dry biomass by 125% and 160%, respectively. Slag application gradually boosted the leaf Zn concentration in alkaline soil under low and high fertilization types, achieving 84% and 54% increases in response to the highest dose of ground slag treatment, respectively. In acidic soil, only the medium dose of slag significantly enhanced the leaf Zn level by 67% under 2X-NP condition. The leaf B concentration was also increased by the medium EAF slag dose up to 19% over control in acidic soil under 1X-NP fertilization. Potentially toxic non-essential elements (Cd, Cr, V, or Pb) were generally non-responsive to slag treatments, regardless of soil types. These findings highlighted the agricultural potential of EAF slag utilization in ensuring safe and sustainable lettuce production while supporting circular economy approach. Future studies investigating the long-term impact of slag on soil and various plant species should be carried out, particularly under field conditions.

Keyword: *lettuce, steel slag, soil amendment, fertilizer, sustainability*

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PP39

CAN NOVEL LIGNOCELLULOSE-BASED SUPERABSORBENT POLYMERS COMBINED WITH UREA ENHANCE WHEAT GROWTH BY IMPROVING FERTILIZER USE EFFICIENCY OR STRESS RESILIENCE?

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While nitrogen (N) fertilization is essential for achieving high yields, its use is often inefficient, resulting in nutrient losses and environmental pollution. Biodegradable superabsorbent polymers (SAPs) enriched with urea offer a promising strategy for sustainable agriculture by improving soil water retention and providing a controlled N supply. In this study, novel biodegradable SAPs with four different urea-to-polymer ratios (0:1, 1:4, 1:2, and 1:1) were synthesized and characterized. Greenhouse experiments were carried out on bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* cv Nusrat) under two irrigation regimes: control (80% field capacity) and leaching (regular excess irrigation). Five fertilization treatments were applied: urea only, urea + SAP (0:1) (applied separately), and three SAP-containing urea formulations (1:4, 1:2, and 1:1). Plant growth, chlorophyll content, photosynthetic performance, macro- and micronutrient concentrations, nitrogen use efficiency, and leachate composition were analyzed to assess the treatment effects.

Results demonstrated that the 1:2 urea:SAP complex consistently enhanced plant growth, biomass accumulation, chlorophyll content, and photosynthetic activity compared to urea alone, under both irrigation regimes. This treatment also optimized N assimilation, resulting in the highest shoot N concentration and highest N balance index. Pure SAP treatments further confirmed the role of SAP in enhancing water retention and nutrient availability. In contrast, the 1:4 and 1:1 complexes were less effective. Leachate analyses revealed that SAP-containing urea mitigated excessive urea and nitrate leaching compared to urea alone.

Overall, lignocellulose-based biodegradable SAP combined with urea represents a promising sustainable fertilization and soil management product for improving water and N use efficiency. Future experiments will reveal more about the mechanism of the observed benefits as well as their dependence on environmental conditions.

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Keyword: *Wheat, Superabsorbent polymers, Nitrogen use efficiency, Lignocellulose, Sustainable agriculture*

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PP40

INVESTIGATION OF THE BIOSTIMULANT EFFECT OF THE COLD PRESS EXTRACT OF THE BROWN SEAWEED *CYSTOSEIRA BARBATA* ON LETTUCE

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The increasing loss of arable land due to urbanization, industrialization, and soil degradation highlights the urgent need for innovative and sustainable agricultural solutions. Among these, plant biostimulants have gained significant attention for their ability to enhance plant growth, yield, and quality at low concentrations, regardless of their mineral content. Seaweed extracts, an important class of plant biostimulants, exert their effects through a variety of bioactive compounds, which significantly enhance plant growth and development, and root system architecture. *Cystoseira barbata*, a brown seaweed species common in the coastal regions of Mediterranean countries, is recognized as a promising source of biostimulant compounds; however, research on this species remains limited. In the present study, cold-pressing was employed to obtain extracts from *C. barbata*. The extracts were initially subjected to characterization assays, including auxin-like activity and mineral analysis. Subsequently, the biostimulant activity of different concentrations (low, medium, and high) of cold-pressed *C. barbata* extracts on the growth, yield, and quality of red lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* cv. Lollo Rosso) was evaluated under greenhouse conditions through application in both deep water culture and soil-based cultivation systems. The results of this study indicated that *C. barbata* extract can enhance shoot and root biomass, improve root parameters, and contribute to the overall quality of lettuce. This study constitutes an excellent example for the utilization of local marine bioeconomy resources for the production of an agricultural input, which can contribute to food security and sustainability.

This study was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK) under the 2209-A University Students Research Projects Support Program (Project No: 1919B012470282)

Keyword: *Biostimulant, Cystoseira barbata, Red Lettuce (Lactuca sativa cv. Lollo Rosso), Seaweed Extract, Sustainable Agriculture*

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PP41

ISOLATION, PURIFICATION, CHARACTERIZATION OF NITROGEN-FIXING BACTERIA FROM POTATO RHIZOSPHERE SOILS IN TÜRKIYE

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With the Green Revolution, the continuous increase in human population and food demand has transformed agriculture into a global industry, leading to the widespread use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides to improve product yield and quality. However, the excessive use of chemical fertilizers has led to serious environmental issues, including soil degradation, water pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions. As a sustainable alternative, biofertilizers offer a promising solution to reduce environmental impact of biofertilizers while maintaining crop productivity.

In this study, a total of 45 soil samples were collected from the rhizosphere of potato plants across major potato-growing regions in Türkiye. From these samples, 542 bacterial colonies were isolated using serial dilution and spread plate methods, and selected based on distinct morphological characteristics such as pigmentations, surface, and etc. The isolates were screened on nitrogen-free bromothymol blue (NFB) agar medium to identify potential nitrogen-fixing bacteria, resulting in the selection of approximately 150 promising candidates. These were further tested using Nessler's reagent to detect and quantify ammonium (NH₄⁺) production, and 30 isolates which reached to highest ammonium levels were selected for detailed characterization. Based on 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis, the isolates were identified as belonging to several genera including *Pseudomonas*, *Acinetobacter*, *Stutzerimonas*, *Enterobacter*, and *Citrobacter*. These taxa are known to inhabit plant rhizospheres and include strains with potential nitrogen-fixation and plant growth-promoting traits, supporting their relevance for further characterization. For further characterization biochemical tests were conducted to assess the metabolic properties of the 30 selected isolates and 16S rRNA gene sequencing is carried out for these 30 isolates.

This study was supported by the COST Action grant (124O159) -TÜBİTAK.

Keyword: *Potato rhizosphere, Nitrogen fixation, Soil bacteria, Characterization*

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PP42

COMPARING LIGNIN-BASED AND CONVENTIONAL FOLIAR FE FERTILIZER IN FE-DEFICIENT SOYBEAN

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Foliar fertilizers must overcome the hydrophobic, negatively charged leaf surface to deposit, adhere, and deliver nutrients efficiently. Lignin—a bio-based, amphiphilic macromolecule—can be formulated as particles and further rendered modified (M-lignin) to enhance physicochemical interactions with leaves and enable micronutrient complexation, offering a sustainable platform for iron (Fe) foliar nutrition. To develop lignin and M-lignin (M-lignin) Fe formulations and evaluate their performance under greenhouse conditions on soybean as a Fe-deficiency-sensitive model crop. Lignin and M-lignin were used to produce Fe-bearing particles and ligand–metal complexes by aqueous processing and spray drying. Materials were characterized by using standard spectroscopic and microscopic techniques to confirm successful Fe association. Greenhouse trials (soybean, alkaline soil) compared lignin-based Fe foliar formulations with conventional Fe fertilizers, with/without a non-ionic surfactant; responses were assessed by visual symptomology and routine plant/leaf readouts. Material analyses supported successful Fe association with lignin and M-Lignin. In greenhouse tests, M-lignin-based foliar Fe deposited on leaves effectively, surfactant co-application visibly improved spray coverage. M-Lignin–Fe treatments produced measurable plant responses in Fe-deficient soybeans, with trends indicating improved leaf status and biomass versus no-Fe controls and performance broadly comparable to conventional chelates under the studied conditions. Treatment-dependent differences among chelates and M-lignin-based formulations were observed in greenness metrics and growth, highlighting formulation and application-method sensitivity. M-lignin enables a bio-based foliar delivery platform for Fe that interacts favorably with the leaf surface and performs promisingly under greenhouse conditions. Ongoing optimization degree, Fe loading mode (particle vs. complex), and spraying parameters is expected to further improve adhesion, uptake, and agronomic benefits.

This study was financially supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under 1004 program LignoNANO (Grant No. 22AG045).

Keyword: *Micronutrient delivery, Foliar Fertilization, Sustainable Agriculture, Leaf Adhesion*

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BIOFORTIFICATION OF WHEATGRASS WITH SELENIUM AND INVESTIGATION OF THE INTERACTION BETWEEN SELENIUM AND SALT STRESS DURING GERMINATION

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This research aimed to enhance the nutritional value as well as the stress tolerance of wheatgrass (*Triticum aestivum* L.) through biofortification with selenium (Se). Functional foods can positively impact health and reduce the risk of chronic diseases. With its rich vitamin, mineral, antioxidant, and bioactive compound content, wheatgrass stands out in this area. Biofortification helps fight micronutrient deficiencies, known as hidden hunger. Selenium is an essential micronutrient involved in immune function, antioxidant defense, and cellular metabolism. However, Se intake is often deficient in plant-based diets, making Se-rich foods important. The project consisted of three main experiments: In the first experiment, the optimal growth medium and Se levels were determined, whereas in the second one, effects of different NaCl concentrations on wheatgrass were studied. To assess stress effects, lipid peroxidation and relative electrolyte leakage analyses were conducted. Despite reduced fresh weight under salinity, no significant changes in the other measured parameters were detected. The short 11-day growth period prevented ionic toxicity and limited salinity effects to osmotic stress. In the third experiment, Se biofortification and NaCl treatment were combined to evaluate growth, stress tolerance, and nutritional value. Increasing NaCl reduced FW, while biochemical analyses (TPA, ABTS, vitamin C) indicated that Se may ameliorate salinity stress. One serving of Se-biofortified wheatgrass can supply about 6% of the RDA for Se in adults, in addition to other valuable minerals, vitamins and antioxidants, offering a functional food that can benefit human health.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by TÜBİTAK under project number 1919B012314785 within the framework of the 2209-A program. The authors gratefully acknowledge TÜBİTAK for their support.

Keyword: *Biofortification, Selenium, Wheatgrass, Sodium Toxicity*

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EXPRESSION OF TOMATO PHYTOENE SYNTHASE IN MICROALGAE TO ENHANCE CAROTENOIDS

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Carotenoids are colorful pigments found in all photosynthetic organisms. While their color palette, which ranges from yellow to red, is useful as an industrial dye, their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects are important in the food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries. The carotenoid pathway starts with a colorless precursor pigment, phytoene, which is synthesized by the phytoene synthase (psy) enzyme. In tomato, there are three types of psy genes encoding this enzyme, and psy-1 is known to be the gene specific to the tomato fruit, where high quantities of lycopene pigment is accumulated. There have been several studies previously that perform the psy gene transfer to *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* from other carotenogenic microalgae species, such as *Dunaliella salina* and *Chlorella zofingensis*, which produce beta-carotene and astaxanthin, respectively. In this study, we are investigating the effect of heterologous tomato psy-1 gene expression on the accumulation of carotenoids in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. The tomato psy-1 (T:psy-1) construct was kindly provided by Dr. Catherina D'Ambrosio from Alsia-Metapontum Agrobios, Italy. T:psy-1 was inserted into the *C. reinhardtii* chloroplast transformation vector pBBY-2 by restriction endonucleases under PsbA promoter. Transformation of cell-wall deficient *C. reinhardtii* cell was performed by the glass beads method. The positive transformants will be investigated for carotenoid accumulation by HPLC analysis. The results to be obtained will reveal the ability of the plant-derived psy-1 gene, which is highly active in tomato fruit, to modify the microalgae carotenoid profile.

Keyword: *Carotenoids, tomato, psy-1, transformation, microalgae*

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THE INFLUENCE OF NANOSIZED ZERO-VALENT IRON ON THE MICROPROPAGATION, AND PHENOLIC COMPOUND CONTENT OF CHERRY LAUREL (*PRUNUS LAUROCERASUS* L.)

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Introduction: Cherry laurel (*Prunus laurocerasus* L.) is a natural antioxidant source, rich in phenolic and flavonoid compounds. These bioactive compounds protect plants and offer health benefits to humans, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anticancer effects. Nanosized zero-valent iron (nZVI), a highly reactive substance used in environmental remediation, has recently been shown to positively impact plant growth. This study investigates nZVI's effects on in vitro cherry laurel cultures.

Purpose: The aim of this research was to determine how different nZVI concentrations (12.5, 25, 50, and 75 mg L⁻¹) affect cherry laurel micropropagation and the production of phenolic and flavonoid compounds.

Methods: After seed germination, we performed micropropagation using 1 mg L⁻¹ of 6-benzyladenine (BA). We then evaluated nZVI's effect by calculating microshoot proliferation(%), the average number of microshoots and length, as well as shoot formation capacity (SFC index). Total phenolic and flavonoid contents were measured using spectrophotometry, and 15 specific phenolic compounds were quantified via UHPLC-Orbitrap®-HRMS/MS.

Results: All nZVI treatments improved proliferation, with the highest rate (85.15%) at 75 mg L⁻¹. However, the most effective concentration for the SFC index (1.66) and the highest total phenolic and flavonoid content was 25 mg L⁻¹. This concentration increased total phenolic content from 130.80 to 140.09 mg GAE g⁻¹ and total flavonoid content from 269.85 to 297.12 mg QE g⁻¹. We observed a 2.4-fold increase in eriodictyol and a 1.33-fold increase in chlorogenic acid. Quercetin and nicotiflorin, absent in the control, were found in all nZVI-treated groups.

Conclusions: This study shows that an optimal nZVI concentration of 25 mg L⁻¹ can enhance cherry laurel micropropagation and the production of bioactive compounds. These findings suggest that nZVI has potential as a nano-fertilizer in agriculture.

Acknowledgements: We thank Prof. Dr. Anatoli Dimoglo and his team for providing the nZVI, and Bingöl University for the UHPLC-Orbitrap®-HRMS/MS analysis.

Keyword: *Cherry laurel, Zero valent iron nanoparticle, In vitro micropropagation, Phenolic compounds*

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CHLAMYDOMONAS REINHARDTII MICROALGAE PRODUCTION FOR SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

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Background: Chlamydomonas reinhardtii are well-known microalgae with the capacity to produce high-value compounds and green energy by decreasing carbon footprint. C. reinhardtii cultivation is considered a sustainable, renewable, and natural solution to climate change and biodiversity loss.

Purpose: The purpose of the study is to examine the effects of different media on C. reinhardtii biomass and chlorophyll-a production.

Methods: In the first group, C. reinhardtii grew in TAP, TAP-N (nitrogen-deficient), and TAP-N+P (nitrogen-deficient, phosphorus-added) media. In the second group, the culture was produced in TAP, TAP+2.5 (2.5 g L⁻¹ sodium nitrate-added), and TAP+5 (5 g L⁻¹ sodium nitrate-added) media (Figure 1). The cultivations were performed at 21±1°C and 120 rpm under 15±1 µmol m⁻²s⁻¹ illumination.

Figure 1. The flowchart of the study.

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Results: In the first group, the biomass yields were $108.3 \pm 9.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ in TAP, $26.0 \pm 3.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ in TAP-N, and $16.3 \pm 2.6 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ in TAP-N+P. Their chlorophyll-a contents were $14.4 \pm 3.9 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $2.61 \pm 0.3 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and $2.23 \pm 0.6 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, respectively. In the second group, the highest amount of biomass was reported in TAP+2.5 medium ($264.0 \pm 1.3 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$), followed by TAP+5 medium ($253.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and TAP medium ($168.0 \pm 5.2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) with chlorophyll-a contents of $14.3 \pm 2.1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $16.4 \pm 2.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and $22.8 \pm 5.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, respectively. TAP+2.5 medium was suitable for biomass production, whereas TAP enhanced chlorophyll-a production.

Conclusions: Since *C. reinhardtii* biomass can be utilized in bioethanol and biohydrogen energy production, and its chlorophyll-a content can be involved in pharmaceuticals and nutraceuticals, it is crucial to find suitable conditions for *C. reinhardtii*. This study contributes to the strategy of utilizing one *C. reinhardtii* culture to reach multiple goals to create a more sustainable future.

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Keyword: *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*, microalgae, sustainable source, green production, renewable source

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INVESTIGATION OF THE FERTILIZER POTENTIAL OF THE LEACHATE OF BIOCHAR OBTAINED BY GASIFICATION OF AGRICULTURAL WASTE

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Climate change and the rapidly increasing global population are increasing the demand for sustainable agricultural solutions and food security. At the same time, the depletion of conventional mineral fertilizer sources and rising input costs have led to a growing interest in innovative and resource-efficient alternatives. Biochar produced via gasification of vegetative tomato waste, which is obtained by soilless greenhouse agricultural system, contains essential plant nutrients; however, its high electrical conductivity limits its direct agricultural use. To address this, a washing process is applied, during which nutrient-rich compounds - especially potassium (K) and phosphorus (P)- are transferred into the washing leachate.

This study investigates the potential of this leachate as a liquid fertilizer for K and P. After optimizing the pH for plant availability, the leachate was chemically characterized with a focus on macro- and micronutrient composition. Its fertilizer potential was evaluated in a deep-water culture hydroponic system using lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) as a model crop. Plant growth, yield, and root development were compared between treatments with leachate and a standard nutrient solution.

ICP-OES analysis of plant tissue mineral analysis revealed that the 10% biochar leachate solution was fully sufficient to meet the plant's K and P demands without causing any negative effects, proving its potential as a liquid fertilizer. Lettuce plants treated with 10% biochar leachate had similar fresh and dry biomass to those grown with the control solution. Root analyses revealed no major differences, indicating no clear positive or negative impact on root development. By evaluating nutrient recovery from biochar leachate, this study supports circular nutrient use and contributes to the development of eco-friendly, cost-effective fertilization strategies for sustainable agriculture and food security.

This project was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TUBITAK) through the 2209-A University Students Research Projects Support Program (Project No: 1919B0124324210).

Keyword: *biochar, leachate, lettuce, liquid fertilizer, sustainable agriculture*

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PATHOGENICITY RESPONSES OF LENTIL VARIETIES FOR BIOTECHNOLOGICAL-SUSTAINABLE PATHOGEN MANAGEMENT BASED ON HOST-PATHOGEN SPECIALIZATION

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Lentils, a valuable food product, are exposed to various stress factors in agricultural production, like many other legumes. Studies on the formae speciales (f. sp.) of wilt disease agent *Fusarium oxysporum* spp., one of the primary biotic stress factors, provide basic information on possible host-pathogen interactions within the scope of biotechnological-sustainable disease management. In this study, the pathogenicity responses of four different red lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) cultivars (cvs Fırat-87, Çağıl, Şakar and Tigris) against *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lentis* (Fol) isolates from four provinces (Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Kilis and Siirt) with different agroecological characteristics were investigated through pathogenicity analysis and cultivar-specific reaction profiles were revealed. The observed responses provide indirect but statistically significant information about the species specialization mechanisms within the *Fusarium oxysporum* Species Complex (FOSC). It was determined that the Fırat-87 variety was quite sensitive, and provided good discrimination in host-pathogen interactions, especially in terms of *Fusarium* wilt caused by Fol ($p < 0.05$). It was determined that the Fol isolate from Siirt province had the highest virulence within the provinces. A moderate correlation was observed between lentil varieties and Disease Severity Index% (DSI%) ($p < 0.01$). Comparative analysis of symptomatic development and resistance responses among lentil cultivars contributes to the understanding of the dynamics in different host species, highlights the need to utilize molecular-biotechnological techniques and supports the development of sustainable pathogen management strategies. It is also important for species-specific improvement practices that can contribute to the development of sustainable plant protection strategies and alternative host interactions. In summary, the study draws attention to biotechnology oriented approaches and solutions for plant protection and ecological resilience in modern model agricultural systems.

This study was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Management Unit of Gaziantep University (Grant Number: FEF.DT.23.16).

Keyword: *Lens culinaris*, *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lentis*, pathogenicity, molecular-biotechnological analyses, sustainability

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EVALUATION OF AN INNOVATIVE LIGNIN-DERIVATIVE ZINC COMPLEX ON SOYBEAN (*GLYCINE MAX*)

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Zinc (Zn) is an essential microelement for plants and human health. Zinc deficiency reduces soybean (*Glycine max*) growth and yield, which is a major protein source in human and animal diet. Conventional inorganic Zn fertilizers such as ZnSO₄ have limited efficacy in alkaline soils, whereas chelates like Zn-EDTA are costly and not necessarily more effective. As sustainable alternatives, lignin-derived Zn fertilizers from hazelnut shells (Lig/Zn-P, Lig/Zn-C, M-Lig/Zn-P, and M-Lig/Zn-C) were developed at Sabancı University SUNUM.

This study evaluated the efficacy of conventional and innovative Zn fertilizers in correcting Zn deficiency and enhancing Zn uptake in soybean. Three experimental conditions were applied: (i) soil application in Zn-deficient soil (<0.1 ppm DTPA-extractable Zn), (ii) foliar application in the same soil, and (iii) hydroponics with nutrient solution. Application rates were 3 mg Zn kg⁻¹ for soil, 0.1% (w/v) Zn for foliar, and 2 µM Zn for hydroponics. Before harvest, photographs were taken and chlorophyll content was measured non-destructively using ForceA. After harvest, shoot dry weights were recorded, and Zn and other essential mineral concentrations were analyzed by ICP-OES.

In soil application, all Zn forms improved plant growth and chlorophyll compared to control, with Zn-EDTA showing the highest Zn uptake. In foliar application, Lig/Zn-C produced the highest shoot biomass, while ZnSO₄ and Zn-EDTA resulted in the highest chlorophyll and Zn concentrations. In hydroponics, all fertilizers increased shoot and root biomass, with ZnSO₄ and Zn-EDTA providing the highest tissue Zn, while lignin-derived fertilizers also showed significant increases.

These results indicate that lignin-derived Zn fertilizers are effective in preventing Zn deficiency under different application methods, though further research is needed to improve cost-effectiveness.

This study was conducted through a collaboration between GTU and SUNUM within the LignoNano project supported by TUBITAK (Grant No. 22AG045) and the 2209-A University Students Research Projects Support Program (Project No. 1919B012431057).

Key words: Soybean, Zinc, Lignocellulose, Sustainable agriculture, Innovative fertilizer

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BIOFORTIFICATION POTENTIAL OF ZINC-ENRICHED DUCKWEED (LEMNA MINOR) AND ITS ROLE IN MITIGATING HEAVY METALS IN LETTUCE (LACTUCA SATIVA))

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Lemna minor (duckweed) is a fast-growing aquatic plant recognized for its remarkable efficiency in biomass production and potential applications in wastewater treatment. With its wide adaptability, high biomass productivity, and strong nutrient accumulation capacity, it holds potential for diverse applications, including wastewater phytoremediation, biofortification, and the production of animal feed and biofertilizers. This study investigated zinc (Zn) biofortification of duckweed cultivated in agricultural wastewater and its subsequent use as a biofertilizer in Zn-deficient and metal-contaminated soils containing cadmium (Cd, 3 ppm) and nickel (Ni, 10 ppm). Duckweed was grown for six days in agricultural wastewater supplemented with varying Zn concentrations. Maximum Zn accumulation (~1600 mg/kg) occurred at 5 ppm Zn, compared with only 80 mg/kg in the control. To test its fertilizing potential, Zn-biofortified and non-biofortified duckweed (equivalent to Zn application rates of 0.2 and 4 ppm) were applied to soils, and lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) growth was evaluated. In Cd-contaminated soils, Zn-biofortified duckweed reduced the adverse effect of Cd toxicity, as indicated by the relative preservation of fresh and dry biomass and chlorophyll content. Moreover, Zn-biofortified duckweed provided better growth performance compared to inorganic Zn fertilizers applied at equivalent doses. In Ni-contaminated soils, plants fertilized with Zn-biofortified duckweed also exhibited more stable growth than those treated with inorganic fertilizers. The highest growth and chlorophyll levels were recorded in control soils without heavy metals, particularly with low-dose Zn-biofortified duckweed application. Overall, these findings demonstrate that Zn-biofortified duckweed not only alleviates Zn deficiency but also enhances plant tolerance to heavy metal stress, highlighting its potential as a sustainable, environmentally friendly, and effective alternative to conventional fertilizers, especially in metal-contaminated soils.

Keyword: *Biofertilizer, sustainable agriculture, duckweed (Lemna minor), wastewater treatment, zinc biofortification*

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INVESTIGATION OF BORON NITRIDE–CHITOSAN HYDROGELS FOR ANTIBACTERIAL APPLICATIONS

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The rapid emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria presents a major challenge for infection management, underscoring the urgent need for innovative antibacterial strategies. Chitosan (CS), a biocompatible and biodegradable polymer, exhibits inherent antibacterial activity; however, its effectiveness against resistant bacterial strains is insufficient, and its thermal and mechanical stability are relatively weak. Incorporating boron nitride (BN), a nanomaterial renowned for its superior thermal conductivity and mechanical robustness, into chitosan hydrogels represents a promising strategy to improve structural integrity while enhancing antibacterial performance. In this study, we aimed to enhance the antibacterial, thermal, and crystalline properties of chitosan (CS) hydrogels by incorporating boron nitride (BN), a nanomaterial with excellent antibacterial activity, biocompatibility, bioadhesion, and structural stability. To achieve this, BN-blended CS hydrogels were fabricated using both the conventional casting method and a microfluidic approach, and subsequently characterised through XRD, DSC, TGA, SEM and FTIR analyses, alongside antibacterial evaluations against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The results demonstrated that BN incorporation significantly improved the thermal stability and crystalline structure of CS hydrogels. Furthermore, antibacterial assays revealed that microfluidic-fabricated hydrogels exhibited superior antibacterial efficacy compared to those produced by the traditional method. Overall, BN incorporation markedly enhanced the antibacterial performance of CS hydrogels against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, highlighting their potential as advanced antibacterial biomaterials.

Keyword: *Boron nitride; Chitosan, Nanobiocomposite hydrogels, Microfluidics, Antibacterial performance.*

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POTENTIAL UTILISATION OF POPPY CAPSULE PULP EXTRACT FOR THE CULTIVATION OF THE HETEROTROPHIC MICROALGAE SCHIZOCHYTRIUM SP.

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Agricultural by-products rich in lignocellulosic materials are increasingly utilized as sustainable substrates for microbial fermentation to lower production costs and support circular economy initiatives. Türkiye, as a leading producer of poppy capsule *Papaver somniferum*, generates more than 100,000 tons of residues annually after alkaloid extraction. Despite their abundance, these residues remain underutilized. Utilizing such materials for heterotrophic microalgal growth offers a promising pathway for omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acid production. In particular, the marine heterotrophic microalga *Schizochytrium* sp. is notable for its ability to accumulate docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), a compound vital for human health and widely used in the nutraceutical sector. We hypothesized that poppy capsule residues can be valorized as a low-cost substrate to sustain *Schizochytrium* growth, lipid and DHA production, offering both economic and environmental benefits.

Poppy capsule residues from the Afyon Alkaloid Factory underwent mechanical pretreatment followed by hydrolysis using thermal, acidic, and enzymatic (α -amylase and cellulase) methods. The most effective hydrolysate was directly employed as a culture medium without supplementary nutrients. For comparison, control media were prepared by adjusting glucose and total soluble protein to match those in the hydrolysates.

Hydrolysate-based cultures reached a biomass concentration of 5.1 g/L after 48 h, closely matching the 5.2 g/L obtained in the control medium. Total soluble protein in the hydrolysate medium increased from 8.92 to 10.92 g/L, while the control remained relatively constant at 12.6–13.0 g/L. Cell density exceeded 2.1×10^8 cells/mL, and pH levels were more stable in hydrolysate cultures. Notably, fatty acid analysis revealed a substantial enhancement in DHA levels in cultures grown on poppy hydrolysate (2.21 g/100 g) compared to the control (0.22 g/100 g), nearly a ten-fold increase. These results demonstrate that poppy capsule residues can sustain heterotrophic microalgal cultivation while significantly enriching DHA yield, providing a sustainable and economical alternative to conventional substrates.

Keyword: *Poppy capsule residues, heterotrophic microalgae cultivation, Schizochytrium sp., docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), waste valorization*

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A REVIEW ON GREEN SYNTHESIS OF SILVER AND ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES USING MICROALGAE FOR SUSTAINABLE NANOTECHNOLOGY.

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Background/Introduction: Nanotechnology is a significant component of modern science and technology, and it finds applications in optics, electronics, biomedical science, catalysis, energy, and environmental science. The production of nanoparticles, which have special qualities due to their nanoscale size, is a significant field of nanotechnology. The traditional chemical and physical methods of nanoparticle synthesis are expensive and utilise toxic substances with adverse environmental and health effects. Green synthesis is less toxic and eco-friendly. Among the biological agents, microalgae are gaining popularity as photosynthetic, metabolically rich organisms with high polysaccharide, protein, and phenolic content, making them ideal candidates for nanoparticle biosynthesis.

Purpose: This study aims to provide an overview of the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) using microalgae as reducing and stabilising agents, emphasising their potential in sustainable nanotechnology.

Methods: A literature review was conducted focusing on microalgae such as *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Spirulina platensis*, and their use in the green synthesis of AgNPs and ZnO NPs.

Results: Strong antibacterial, antioxidant, and photocatalytic properties are exhibited by microalgae-mediated nanoparticles, which are generally homogeneous in shape and nanoscale in size. The synthesis process is cost-effective, simple, and environmentally safe.

Conclusion(s): Microalgae-based green synthesis of AgNPs and ZnO NPs is a promising, sustainable method for nanomaterial production. However, long-term ecological and health impacts must be further investigated before large-scale application

Keyword: *green synthesis, microalgae, silver nanoparticles, zinc oxide nanoparticles, sustainable nanotechnology*

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SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION OF L-TYROSINE DERIVATIVES VIA WHOLE-CELL BIOCATALYSIS USING CORYNEBACTERIUM GLUTAMICUM

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L-Tyrosine (L-Tyr), one of the three aromatic amino acids, is a central metabolic intermediate and a versatile precursor for numerous bioactive and industrially relevant compounds across the food, pharmaceutical, and chemical industries. Among its derivatives, dopamine serves as a key precursor for the biosynthesis of plant alkaloids and other high-value products. Dopamine biosynthesis from L-Tyr can proceed via two alternative pathways: the canonical route involving hydroxylation of L-Tyr to 3,4-dihydroxy-L-phenylalanine (L-DOPA) followed by decarboxylation, and a second route starting with decarboxylation to tyramine followed by hydroxylation to dopamine. Since L-DOPA is chemically unstable under physiological conditions, the latter route may offer potential advantages for microbial production. In this work, two *Corynebacterium glutamicum* strains were employed: one expressing a tyrosinase and another co-expressing a tyrosinase and a tyrosine decarboxylase. Cells were cultivated in either defined or agro-industrial waste-based media, harvested. Then the work investigated the production of L-DOPA, dopamine, tyramine, and melanin using whole cells as biocatalysts for biotransformation. These findings demonstrate the feasibility of using *C. glutamicum* as a sustainable whole-cell catalyst and suggest that the tyramine route may represent a more stable and robust alternative to the L-DOPA pathway for microbial dopamine production.

Keyword: *L-Tyrosine, L-DOPA, Tyramine, Dopamine, Melanin, C. glutamicum, whole-cell biocatalysis, agro-waste*

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GROWTH OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA ON ORANGE PEEL HYDROLYSATE

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Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are beneficial microorganisms that inhabit a wide range of environments, from soil to the human gastrointestinal tract. Since ancient times, LAB have been employed in food fermentation processes. This bacterial group also includes probiotics capable of colonizing the human intestinal and reproductive tracts, thereby supporting the host's ecological balance. They exert their beneficial effects both directly, by competing with pathogenic microorganisms and indirectly, through the production of postbiotics, which include non-living microbial cells, their components, or metabolites that likewise promote host health. Agro-industrial waste hydrolysates serve as sustainable and cost-effective substrates for biorefineries, providing an alternative to traditional refined feedstocks. These wastes are typically rich in cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and proteins. In this work, the growth of two LAB strains, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* and *Pediococcus pentosaceus*, on orange peel extract has been studied. To this end, two different methods were employed to prepare the extract: acid hydrolysis of the orange waste and aqueous extraction of its soluble components. Then a top down approach was used to identify the medium components. In order to test the effect of orange waste extract on growth, cells were cultivated in different MRS media containing either glucose, orange waste extract (20%), both, or neither. Then, a top-down approach was utilized to identify the elements essential for growth in the orange waste extract. This work has demonstrated that orange waste may be valorized to promote beneficial lactic acid bacterial growth.

Keyword: *lactic acid bacteria, agro-industrial waste, orange peel, acid hydrolyzation, bacterial growth*

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IMPROVING LETTUCE GROWTH AND QUALITY IN DEEP WATER CULTURE SYSTEMS USING *CYSTOSEIRA BARBATA* EXTRACT-ENRICHED NUTRIENT SOLUTIONS

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Soilless agriculture, the fastest-growing sector in modern agriculture and a key technological component of greenhouse cultivation, offering solutions to many limitations of soil-based systems. Deep-water culture represent an efficient and cost-effective approach for the production of lettuce and other leafy greens. As a sustainable practice to boost crop performance and reduce reliance on chemical inputs, the use of seaweed-based biostimulants through nutrient solutions in hydroponic systems is gaining attention. However, research on their integration into hydroponic systems and modes of action remains limited. Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) is a widely cultivated leafy vegetable suitable for year-round hydroponic production. It is valued for its rapid growth, rich phytonutrient content, including antioxidants, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, vitamins, and minerals, and its role in human health. In this study, different concentrations of *Cystoseira barbata* extracts (water, alkali, and acid) were incorporated into nutrient solutions and applied in a deep-water culture system under greenhouse conditions. The treatments resulted in significant improvements in plant growth and quality traits.. The results of this study revealed that application of *C. barbata* extracts led to considerable improvements in hydroponically grown lettuce under greenhouse conditions, having positive effects on growth parameters such as yield, root morphology, mineral levels, and physiological quality factors, including phenolic and antioxidant capacity, carotenoid levels, glutathione, and vitamin C concentrations. These findings demonstrate that integrating the extracts into the nutrient solution can act as an effective biostimulant for leafy vegetables, enhancing plant performance and nutritional properties. Thus, the integration of hydroponics and seaweed-based biostimulants represents a viable, eco-friendly approach to vegetable crop cultivation.

Keywords- Biostimulant, Lettuce, Seaweed Extract, Sustainable Agriculture, Soilless Culture

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SEAWEED-BASED BIOSTIMULANTS DERIVED FROM CYSTOSEIRA BARBATA PROMOTE GROWTH AND STRESS RESILIENCE IN WHEAT

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Drought is a major environmental stress that limits crop productivity and threatens global food security. The growing demands of a rising population and climate change highlight the urgent need for sustainable agricultural practices. Seaweed-derived biostimulants have emerged as promising tools to enhance crop performance and stress resilience due to their complex bioactive composition. Among these, the brown seaweed species *Cystoseira barbata* (*C. barbata*) (syn. *Gongolaria barbata*), widely distributed along the Turkish coastline, represents a potential bioecenomy resource.

This study evaluated the effects of three *C. barbata* extracts; water, alkali, and acid; on durum wheat (*Triticum durum* cv. Sariçanak-98) under well-watered and drought conditions through soil drenching applications. The application of seaweed extracts increased biomass by up to 60% and dry matter accumulation by up to 20%, while also enhancing tolerance mechanisms under drought stress. Biostimulant-treated plants exhibited increased levels of compatible solutes, such as glycine betaine and proline, and higher activities of key antioxidant enzymes, including catalase and glutathione reductase. Furthermore, elevated malondialdehyde levels in treated plants indicated a protective role against oxidative damage. Moreover, soil microbial community profiling revealed notable differences, particularly in response to the water extract application, suggesting that *C. barbata* extracts may also influence rhizosphere microbiota.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report demonstrating the potential of *C. barbata* extracts to simultaneously enhance drought tolerance in wheat and modulate soil microbial communities. These findings highlight the potential of locally available seaweed resources as sustainable biostimulants. Depending on the extraction method used, *C. barbata* extracts can improve crop growth under water-limited conditions and contribute to physiological benefits that support stress resilience.

This study was supported by The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK 3501 Project number: 121Z215) and (YOK) 100/2000 Scholarship Program.

Keyword: *Biostimulant, Drought Stress, Microbial Community Analysis, Seaweed Extract, Wheat*

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SEAWEED-DERIVED EXTRACTS ALLEVIATE THE ADVERSE IMPACTS OF SALT STRESS ON WHEAT GROWN IN HYDROPONIC SYSTEMS

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Global climate change, together with the increasing frequency of drought, is expected to intensify salinity problems in agricultural lands and reduce wheat productivity. Given the significance of wheat for global food security, the use of plant biostimulants, including seaweed extracts, is emerging as a promising and sustainable approach to mitigate stress-related constraints and ensure wheat production in salt-affected areas. The application of seaweed extracts can alleviate the effects of salinity stress by promoting the accumulation of bioactive compounds, stimulating the synthesis of protective metabolites, and activating defense responses, thereby enhancing plant growth, yield, and quality.

This study evaluated the potential of seaweed extracts derived from *Cystoseira barbata*, a brown seaweed species abundant in the Mediterranean and collected from the Marmara Sea, as biostimulants for hydroponically grown wheat (*Triticum durum* cv. Sarıçanak-98) under non-saline (0 mM NaCl) and saline conditions (60 and 90 mM NaCl). The findings indicate that *C. barbata* extracts, particularly the water and acid extracts, alleviated the detrimental effects of salt stress. The addition of *C. barbata* extract to the nutrient solution resulted in enhanced growth parameters including shoot and root biomass, reduced electrolyte leakage, increased accumulation of compatible osmolytes like proline and glycine betaine, and resulted higher potassium levels. The stress-mitigating effects of *C. barbata* extracts are likely attributable to bioactive compounds that regulate salt tolerance mechanisms and enhance salinity tolerance. It can be concluded that the integration of *C. barbata*-based extracts into nutrient solutions can be a promising and sustainable strategy for alleviating salt-induced stress, particularly in soilless cultivation systems affected by salinity stress.

This study was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under the Grant Number 121Z215.

Keywords: Biostimulant, Salinity Stress, Seaweed Extract, Soilless Agriculture, Wheat

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METAGENOMIC MINING OF MARINE MICROBIOMES FOR NOVEL ANTIBIOTIC BIOSYNTHETIC PATHWAYS: A BIOINFORMATICS PIPELINE USING PUBLIC DEEP-SEA DATA

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Background: Research on novel antibiotics has increased due to the rapid rise in antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Marine microbiomes exhibit a largely untapped source of bioactive secondary metabolites, especially from rare or uncultured species. Currently, genome mining techniques facilitate the exploration of biosynthesis gene clusters (BGCs) in microbial genomes without the need for laboratory cultivation.

Purpose: This research seeks to identify and characterize biosynthetic gene clusters with antibiotic potential in the genome of *Salinispora tropica*, a recognized marine Actinobacterium, through a computational pipeline. The objective is to illustrate the capabilities of open-access bioinformatics tools in the initial phases of antibiotic discovery.

Methods: *Salinispora tropica* CNB-440's reference genome was retrieved from the NCBI RefSeq database. Biosynthetic gene clusters were predicted utilizing antiSMASH 7.0 with adjusted detection parameters to enhance sensitivity. Outputs were analyzed through custom Python scripts, resulting in a cluster summary and visualization of BGC type distribution. Clusters were compared to entries in the MIBiG database to evaluate their novelty and similarity to characterized natural products.

Results: There were 19 BGCs found, including four NRPS (nonribosomal peptide synthetases), six T1PKS (Type I polyketide synthases), and other hybrid and specialized clusters, including azole-containing, butyrolactone, and RiPP-like kinds. Salinosporamide A, sporolide A/B, lymphostin, and salinipostins were among the known antibiotic-related chemicals with which high-confidence matches were discovered. Multiple clusters showed no substantial similarity to current MIBiG entries, suggesting opportunities for the discovery of novel metabolites.

Conclusion: This research demonstrates the extensive biosynthetic diversity of *Salinispora tropica* and affirms the utility of bioinformatics pipelines as effective tools for natural product discovery. At an early research stage, such approaches can aid in identifying new leads to address antimicrobial resistance.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge the antiSMASH team and NCBI for access to open-source tools and data. This study was conducted as part of early-career training in bioinformatics.

Keyword: *Salinispora tropica*, biosynthetic gene clusters, antiSMASH, antibiotic discovery, bioinformatics

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LIGNOCELLULOSE–STARCH HYDROGELS FOR DYE REMOVAL FROM WASTEWATER

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Introduction: Water contamination is a critical environmental issue, driven by the continuous release of industrial effluents containing hazardous dyes, creating a demand for sustainable and low-cost adsorbents. Starch-based hydrogels provide biodegradability and high swelling capacity, while functional lignocellulose offers abundant groups for dye binding. Their integration yields an eco-friendly and efficient material for wastewater treatment, offering a promising alternative to conventional methods.

Purpose: This study aimed to design lignocellulose–starch hydrogels incorporating carboxyl-functionalized lignocellulose for effective dye removal from wastewater. Methylene blue (MB) was used as a model contaminant to assess adsorption performance. The focus was placed on achieving a stable hydrogel network with high swelling ability, while enhancing dye-binding efficiency through the introduction of carboxylic acid groups to the lignocellulose backbone.

Methods: Lignocellulosic biomass was functionalized with succinic anhydride (SA) to introduce carboxylic acid groups, thereby enhancing dye-binding ability. The modified lignocellulose was incorporated into a starch solution, and in the presence of low acrylamide content and initiator, hydrogel formation occurred under aqueous conditions. The modified lignocellulose was incorporated into hydrogel formulations at specific ratios to evaluate its effect on methylene blue removal, which will be measured using UV-Vis spectrophotometry.

Results: Lignocellulose was successfully functionalized with SA, as confirmed by FTIR and NMR spectroscopy. Hydrogels prepared from a 5% starch solution containing functionalized lignocellulose (LS-SA:S 3:5) exhibited a stable and homogeneous structure with swelling ratios exceeding 350%. The LS–S hydrogels demonstrated noticeable MB removal, evidenced by visible colour change, while UV–Vis studies continue to assess adsorption.

Conclusion: Lignocellulose shows strong potential for dye adsorption through electrostatic, π – π , and hydrogen bonding interactions, further enhanced by SA functionalization introducing carboxylic acid groups. In the LS–S hydrogel matrix, swelling and diffusion created a robust

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structure that enhanced MB adsorption. Thus, lignocellulose–starch hydrogels highlight their promise as sustainable adsorbents for wastewater dye removal.

Figure: A) Lignocellulose–Starch (LS-S) Hydrogel

B) 100 ppm Methylene blue solution

C) LS-S Hydrogel in 100 ppm Methylene blue solution for 3 hours

Keyword: *Starch hydrogel, Lignocellulose, wastewater treatment, dye adsorption*

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ELECTROSPUN LIGNIN COMPOSITE FIBERS FOR SUSTAINABLE DYE REMOVAL FROM WASTEWATER

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Introduction: Water pollution from industrial dyes remains a serious environmental challenge, highlighting the need for sustainable adsorbent materials. Lignocellulose (LS), with its aromatic backbone and diverse functional groups, can effectively interact with dye molecules, while polyacrylonitrile (PAN) is widely used in electrospinning for its excellent spinnability and mechanical stability. Combining these components provides a promising route to fabricate functional nanofibers with high bio-based content.

Purpose: The purpose of this study was to obtain electrospun LS–PAN composite fibers with a high bio-based content for sustainable dye removal from wastewater. Methylene blue (MB), commonly employed as a model contaminant, was chosen for adsorption studies. Emphasis was placed on maximizing lignocellulose incorporation while maintaining good fiber spinnability and stability.

Methods: Electrospun fibers were obtained from mixtures prepared by adding LS to prepared PAN solutions. Various LS/PAN ratios were studied, and electrospinning parameters were optimized to produce smooth and continuous fibers. Adsorption performance toward methylene blue is currently being analyzed by UV–Vis spectroscopy, with full results to be presented.

Results: Uniform fibers were successfully obtained at a high LS loading, (LS: PAN 3:1), by adjusting the electrospinning parameters, including an applied voltage of 20 kV. This composition demonstrated the most suitable compromise between spinnability and bio-based content. At the same fiber amount (30 mg in 10 mL of 100 ppm methylene blue solution for 3 h), pure PAN fibers exhibited no significant adsorption, while LS–PAN composite fibers rendered the MB solution nearly clear.

Figure. A: 100 ppm methylene blue solution
B: PAN fiber mixed with 100 ppm methylene blue solution for 3 hours
C: LS-PAN fiber mixed with 100 ppm methylene blue solution for 3 hours
D: SEM image of LS-PAN fibers

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Conclusions: This study demonstrates that electrospinning can produce uniform LS–PAN composite fibers with high lignocellulose content (up to a 3:1 ratio). Dye removal was confirmed to originate from the lignocellulose through electrostatic, π – π , and hydrogen bonding interactions, while the PAN matrix ensured fiber stability. These findings highlight the potential of bio-based nanofibers as sustainable adsorbents for wastewater treatment.

Keyword: *Lignocellulose fiber, Electrospun, wastewater treatment, dye adsorption*

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CONVERSION OF WASTE GENERATED IN THE FAST-MOVING CONSUMER GOODS SECTOR INTO BENEFICIAL PRODUCTS THROUGH A CIRCULAR ECONOMY APPROACH

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The rapidly growing fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector, particularly as a result of food processing, generates a significant amount of organic waste. The organic matter caused by these processes reaches treatment plants via wastewater, and high-organic-content sewage sludge is generated at the end of the treatment process. The aim of this study is to investigate the potential of utilizing these wastes as biofertilizers and energy sources for sustainable agriculture. Within the framework of circular economy principles, the study characterizes food production residues and treatment sludges originating from the FMCG sector, examining fertilizer quality criteria such as macro and micro nutrient content, heavy metal levels, C/N ratio, and pathogen load. An analysis of sectoral average values revealed pH values ranging from 4.9 to 8.7, dry matter contents of 71–99%, organic matter contents of 95–98%, and C/N ratios between 14 and 58. Based on the obtained data, these wastes are predicted to have significant potential for both organic fertilizer production and energy conversion processes. Organic-rich wastes from the FMCG sector should not be regarded solely as an environmental burden requiring disposal; they should be considered as inputs that can be integrated into sustainable agricultural production processes. In this context, holistic approaches that prioritize the recovery of such wastes without harming the environment and human health increase the applicability of circular economy principles and bring a new perspective to sectoral waste management. According to literature data, the value of food production residues and treatment sludges in terms of fertilizer and energy production will be demonstrated based on their characterization, and if these wastes are processed using appropriate methods, their potential to enhance agricultural productivity and energy potential will be evaluated. These evaluations demonstrate that the integrated management of waste types specific to the FMCG sector can simultaneously achieve environmental sustainability and economic benefit.

Keyword: *Treatment Sludge, Biofertilizer, Circular Economy, Sustainable Agriculture, Food Industry Waste*

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